

GREENGAGE

ENGAGING CITIZENS - MOBILIZING TECHNOLOGY - DELIVERING GREEN DEAL

GREEN Engine and manual 3

Work Package 4, Deliverable D4.9

AWAITING VALIDATION BY THE EUROPEAN COMMISSION

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Work package 4, Deliverable D4.9

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List of Acronyms

APK	Android Package Kit
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AIT	Austrian Institute of Technology
API	Application Programming Interface
AQI	Air Quality Index
AWS	Amazon Web Services
BE	Back-End
BLE	Bluetooth Low Energy
CBS	Central Bureau of Statistics
CE	Collaborative Environment
CLI	Command Line Interface
CMS	Content Management System
CO	Citizen Observatory
CSV	Comma Separated Value
CVAT	Computer Vision Annotation Tool
DB	Database
DQA	Data Quality Assessment
DQD	Data Quality Dashboard
EBLN	East Bristol Liveable Neighbourhood
ETL	Data integration process Extract, Transform, Load
EU	European Union
FE	Front-End
GATT	Generic ATtribute Profile
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GeoTIFF	Georeferenced Tagged Image File Format
GIS	Geographic Information System
GPS	Global Positioning System
GUI	Graphical User Interface
HDFS	Hadoop Distributed File System
HTTP	Hypertext Transfer Protocol
IDE	Integrated Development Environment
IP	Internet Protocol
JDBC	Java Database Connectivity
JOLT	JSON Language for Transform
JSON	Java Script Object Notation
KPI	Key Performance Indicators
KPI	Key Performance Indicators
LLaMA	Large Language Model Meta AI

LLM	Large Language Model
MQTT	Message Queueing Telemetry Transport
MVP	Minimum Viable Product
OGC	Open Geospatial Consortium
PM	Particulate Matter
PNG	Portable Network Graphics
POI (Pol)	Point of Interest
PST	Pilot Support Team
REST	Representational State Transfer
SaaS	Software as a Service
SDK	Software Development Kit
SPA	Single Page Application
SQL	Structured Query Language
SSR	Server-Side Rendering
TMS	Tile Map Service
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
TVOC	Total Volatile Organic Compounds
UB	Urban Belonging (app)
UrbanTEP	Urban Thematic Exploitation Platform
UWE	University of the West of England
VA	Visual Analytics
VISAT	Visual Analytical Toolboxes
VOC	Volatile Organic Compounds
WFS	Web Feature Service
WMS	Web Map Service
WMTS	Web Map Tiling Service

Glossary

Citizen Observatory	According to EU project WeObserve, "Citizen Observatories (COs) are community-based environmental monitoring and information systems, that invite individuals to share observations, typically via mobile phone or the web. Throughout these activities citizens become able to participate in environmental management/local governance." Reference: D2.1 - GREENGAGE Methodological Framework
Citizen Science	In Citizen Science, a broad network of people collaborates. Participants provide experimental data and facilities for researchers, raise new questions and co-create a new scientific culture. While they add value, volunteers acquire new learning and skills and gain a deeper understanding of the scientific work in appealing ways. As a result of this open, networked and transdisciplinary scenario, science-society-policy interactions are improved, leading in turn to a more democratic research, based on evidence and informed decision-making" (Socientize consortium, 2014, p. 10).
GREEN Engine	GREENGAGE's dedicated technological stack leveraging GREENGAGE's technical infrastructure. In combination with GREENGAGE's conceptual

	infrastructure and applied methods of narrative building for public engagement, the GREEN Engine supports the execution of Citizen Observatories via providing data gathering, analyses and visualisation, as well as Observatory planning, managing and monitoring capabilities.
Common Data Model	A Common Data Model (CDM) describes a standardised data model which allows for data and information exchange between different applications and data sources, in case of the GREENGAGE project, between all components of the GREEN Engine.

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Executive summary (publishable)

This document presents the third version of the GREEN Engine and Manuals document delivered by the GREENGAGE project in M32 (August 2025). Hence, this document provides the final summary of the technological assets offered by GREENGAGE's partners. As the GREENGAGE project was a so-called Innovation Action of the European Commission, it combined existing technologies and technology specifically created within the project to become an innovative technology framework that supports the execution of Citizen Observatories. This framework is called GREEN Engine, which is described in detail in this document. The combined technologies are divided into three categories:

1. **GREENGAGE tools** developed/adapted within the project (e.g., newly developed apps for data collection like the GREENGAGE app)
2. **Pilot specific tools.** These are external tools, neither developed by the GREENGAGE project, nor open-source tools, but used for additional data collection, due to familiarity of the tools to the citizens of a pilot and the broad audience already established. These tools provide additional/auxiliary data for the Citizen Observatories to compliment the Observatories' data pool to support the Observatories' understanding of a specific topic when combined with GREENGAGE's GREEN Engine.
3. **Open-source tools/platforms** adopted by GREENGAGE and either used in combination with the tools developed for the project (e.g., the data visualisation platform Apache Superset) or stand-alone (like the Collaborative Environment).

All the above evolved from a constant specification refinement during the project based on pilots' needs via a prototyping and collaborative reflection scheme within the GREENGAGE consortium.

This document shall serve as manual for these GREEN Engine technologies, but also provide a guide for re-using, tailoring or extending the GREEN Engine for specific needs of future Citizen Observatories to support their data collection, data curation, analysis and visualisation as well as their use in policy assessment based on the findings of the Observatories.

The deliverable aims to provide a consolidated overview, as well as technical manuals and shall serve as a workflow specification, too.

Furthermore, this document describes the common data model and APIs developed for the GREEN Engine.

Related documents

GREENGAGE Deliverable D1.12 Data Management Plan (Javed et al., 2025)

GREENGAGE Deliverable D2.3 Use Cases and Requirements Analysis (Soomro et al., 2025)

GREENGAGE Deliverable D2.5 Smart governance models 2 (Hall et al., 2025)

GREENGAGE Deliverable D2.7 GREENGAGE Technological Requirements (López-de-Ipiña et al., 2025)

GREENGAGE Deliverable D4.1 GREEN Engine and Manual 1 (Khrystodulov et al., 2023a)

GREENGAGE Deliverable D4.2 GREEN Engine and Manual 2 (Khrystodulov et al., 2023b)

GREENGAGE Deliverable D4.6 GREENGAGE experiment and monitoring system and manual 2 (Sanchez-Corcuera et al., 2025)

1 GREENGAGE summary

The pan-European Innovation Action, funded under the Horizon Europe Framework Programme, aimed to promote innovative governance processes, and tried to help public authorities in shaping their climate mitigation and adaptation policies. To achieve this aim, the GREENGAGE project leveraged citizens' participation and equipped them with innovative digital solutions that shall transform citizen's engagement and cities' effectiveness in delivering the European Green Deal objectives for carbon neutral cities.

Focusing on mobility, air quality and healthy living, the aim was to inspire citizens to observe and co-create their cities by sensing their urban environments. The idea was to complement, validate, and enrich information in authoritative data held by the public administrations and public agencies. This was facilitated by engaging with citizens to co-create green initiatives and to develop Citizen Observatories (CO). In GREENGAGE, Citizen Observatories were and are a place where pilot cities co-examine environmental issues integrating novel bottom-up processes with top-down perspectives. This provides the basis to co-create and co-design innovative solutions to monitor environmental problems at ground level with the help of citizens.

With two interrelated project dimensions, the project aimed to enhance intelligence applied to city decision-making processes and governance by engaging with citizen observations integrated with Copernicus, Global Earth Observation System of Systems GEOSS, in-situ, and socio-economic intelligence, and by delivering innovative governance models based on novel toolboxes of decision-making methodologies and technologies.

The Citizens Observatory campaigns were deployed and fully demonstrated in 5 pilot engagements in selected European cities and regions including: Bristol (the United Kingdom), Copenhagen (Denmark), Turano Valley (Italy), Gerace (Italy) and the region of North Brabant (the Netherlands). These innovation pilots aimed to highlight the need for smart city governance by promoting citizen engagement, co-creation, as well as gathering new data which should complement existing datasets and evidence-based decision and policymaking.

Figure 1: GREENGAGE Project structure

2 Introduction

The first iteration of this Deliverable, *D4.1 GREEN Engine and Manual 1*, documented the very first activity within WP4, which concentrated on the consolidated collection and analysis of existing GREENGAGE partners' technological assets to guide their later leveraging - re-use, tailoring or extending for specific needs for data collection, data curation, analysis, visualisation as well as policy use assessment, as identified by the needs of specific piloting use cases.

The second iteration, *D4.2 GREEN Engine and Manual 2*, progressed and further elaborated on GREENGAGE's service-oriented interoperability approach to be adopted to interlink all available technical solutions in a well-defined, organized and pilot focused manner.

This third and final version, *D4.9 GREEN Engine and Manual 3*, updates D4.2 by outlining major changes from the previous iteration, clarifying final tool names, depicting tool-to-pilot relationships, and describing the challenge-oriented use of the GREEN Engine.

In comparison to D4.2, Deliverable *D4.9, GREEN Engine and Manual 3* focusses on providing concise manuals for the whole range of technological tools highlighting the major updates compared to the previous iteration. These include open-source and partner-contributed technologies (together forming the GREEN Engine) as well as pilot-specific resources to be integrated (e.g. open data sets, other already existing tools, available infrastructure). The aim was to guide seamless integration and effective use for data handling, analysis, visualization tailored to specific piloting needs. This iteration emphasized service-oriented interoperability, ensuring a cohesive ecosystem. Additionally, an online collaborative platform finally empowered Citizen Observers to conduct experiments and share results in a guided and systematic way. This platform, customized for GREENGAGE Citizen Observers, is referred to as the "GREEN Engine". Hence, this document depicts the final technical results as a Key Exploitable Result of GREENGAGE to deliver the requested Innovation Action from the technological side.

To prepare this version of the document, WP4 activities cross-checked the pilots' requirements from WP2 with the existing capabilities of GREENGAGE technological assets and adjusted them based on the pilots' latest needs, distilled as functional and non-functional requirements. As main source it has used deliverable *D2.7. GREENGAGE technological requirement 2*, which was delivered in M27. Additionally, the GREENGAGE team analysed, again, the most suitable workflows and implementation roadmaps for integrating and managing the features available within its components. As a result, it generated the technical documentation item entitled "[Completion of a Citizen Science Loop with GREENGAGE](#)". The project is currently defining a deployment strategy and has created a collaborative environment to support the setup, configuration, operation, monitoring, and utilisation of Citizen Observatories (COs). This environment has also facilitated engagement from pilot users, supported technical discussions with partners, and enabled systematic issue registration and clarification beneficial to WP4 activities.

3 Reference to Requirements and Specification of the GREEN Engine

For the final Pilot requirements and specifications for the GREEN Engine technologies, please refer to GREENGAGE’s deliverables D2.3, D2.5 and D2.7 info “Related documents” section. These requirements and specifications build the base for the technologies created and combined during the lifetime of the project.

The above-mentioned deliverables can also be easily accessed on **Zenodo**, which serves as the central repository for project reports and documentation. You can access Zenodo via following link: <https://zenodo.org/communities/greengage/>

Figure 2: Referenced documents on Zenodo

4 Description of GREENGAGE's Citizen Observatory enabling technologies

GREEN Engine should manifest an interoperable and extensible toolbox covering the whole data-to-policy lifecycle. To understand and relate the tools and technologies of the GREENGAGE technical providers, a questionnaire had been created and shared among WP4 members. The aim of the tools' and technologies' specification was to provide a common template, which corresponded to a technical portfolio of the GREEN Engine and which enabled a detailed cross-check of the engine's technical stack with the pilots' requirements. The overall idea behind the GREEN Engine is depicted Figure 3.

Figure 3: GREEN Engine Architecture

The table below depicts the contribution of technical partners to the GREEN Engine as well as external tools integrated into GREEN Engine.

Table 1: Technological contribution to GREEN Engine

Technology	Developer	Hoster	Support/User
MODE (Travel Mode Detection)	AIT	SushiDev	GREENGAGE Consortium
Atmotube PRO	Atmotube		Libelium, GREENGAGE Consortium
DigiTwin	Argaleo		BUAS, Nord Brabant
Collaborative Environment (CE)	DEUSTO	DEUSTO	DEUSTO, KWMC, GREENGAGE Consortium
Apache NiFi	Apache Foundation	VRVis	DEUSTO, VRVis
Apache Superset	Apache Foundation	VRVis	DEUSTO, VRVis, AIT, GREENGAGE Consortium
Apache Druid	Apache Foundation	VRVis	DEUSTO, VRVis, AIT
Apache DataHub	Apache Foundation	VRVis	DEUSTO
Wordpress	WordPress Foundation	DEUSTO	DEUSTO, VRVis, AIT

Discourse	Civilized Discourse Construction Kit, Inc.	DEUSTO	DEUSTO, AIT, GREENGAGE Consortium
Zenodo	OpenAIRE-Consortium, CERN	OpenAIRE-Consortium, CERN	AIT, VRVis, DEUSTO
KeyCloak	WildFly	DEUSTO	DEUSTO, Sushi Dev, MindEarth, Digitalsunray, GREENGAGE Consortium
GREENGAGE app	Digitalsunray	App Store, Google Playstore	GREENGAGE Consortium
UrbanTEP / VISAT	GISAT	GISAT	GREENGAGE Consortium
Kepler.gl	Uber Visualization team	GISAT, MindEarth, GREENGAGE Consortium	
Portable Devices for environmental data capture			Libelium, Moondial, GREENGAGE Consortium
MindEarth for GREENGAGE app	MindEarth		MindEarth, GREENGAGE Consortium
Text analysis (sentiment / summarisation)	UWE		UWE, GREENGAGE Consortium
Video analytics	UWE		UWE, MindEarth, GREENGAGE Consortium
Data Quality Dashboard	VRVis	VRVis	VRVis, GREENGAGE Consortium

Notice that the nature and source of the datasets selected and used at the COs launched at each pilot site also influenced some adaptations for the suite of tools integrated within the Collaborative Environment. Hence, there are three forces that were aligned to give place to the GREEN Engine which acts as an enabler and supporting platform to enable effective Citizen Observation campaigns leveraging actionable knowledge to streamline the Green Deal-related urban solutions:

1. Features made available by the components contributed by WP4 partners.
2. Requirements extracted from analysing the focus of each of the GREENGAGE pilots.
3. Data workflows that should be configured by mixing authoritative and in-situ data at each pilot to configure and execute their associated COs.

This chapter focuses on the analysis of the features of the components made available by WP4 partners.

4.1 GREENGAGE tools

The GREENGAGE tools encompass a diverse range of technologies designed to support the entire data-to-policy lifecycle within the GREEN Engine. These tools have been carefully curated to ensure interoperability and extensibility. To facilitate a comprehensive understanding of these tools and their relevance to the GREENGAGE technical providers, a questionnaire was formulated and shared among WP4 members. The objective of this inquiry was to establish a common template that corresponds to the technical portfolio of the GREEN Engine, enabling a detailed cross-check of the engine's technical stack with the requirements of the pilots. Notice that all technical documentation of each of the

components of GREEN Engine has been made available at <https://greengage-project.github.io/Documentation/>.

4.1.1 MindEarth for GREENGAGE app (MindEarth)

MindEarth for GREENGAGE app is a dedicated mobile app available for Android (NB: An iOS version is available as a development version on request) (Figure 4), which enables users with little or no previous experience to collect and upload geo-tagged street-level imagery either by means of smartphones' built-in camera or using compatible devices, such as 360-degree cameras.

Figure 4: An illustration of the MindEarth for GREENGAGE app depicting the user interface and several of its functionalities.

Users collect and upload geo-tagged street-level photos. Specifically, they can browse among a range of available missions that are commissioned by a third party for research, urban planning, or commercial purposes. Survey missions might require the mapper (i.e., an active user):

- i) to move from one place to another following a predefined route (typically between 500m to 2km)
- ii) to take pictures of a targeted objects at given times of the day (i.e., a shopfront, a monument, a building facade)
- iii) to stand in position at a specific location for a certain amount of time (typically ranging from 15 to 30 minutes).

Some missions might have strict deadlines to be completed, whereas others might be carried out at any moment in time. Users can access individual mission briefs via the app, including location, duration, device to be used, deadline, and compensation, and finally pick one or more to perform based on interests, availability, and required skillset.

Once mappers initiate a mission, pictures are taken at uniform intervals (between 0.5 to 2 frames per second) and temporarily stored on the local drive in PNG/JPEG format. At the end of the mission, these are first encrypted, then transmitted (via REST interface) to secure cloud servers based in Europe (e.g., Bucket S3 Digital Ocean with AICPA SOC 2 Type II certificate) and ultimately deleted from the local drive. From this moment onward, stored imagery on the server is exclusively accessible by designated MindEarth personnel and from designated password-protected terminals at pre-authorized locations (identified by their IP Address). Being taken from public spaces, collected data may include personal information. Accordingly, once on the secure cloud server, images are anonymized by applying automatic blurring of faces and license plates according to the actual GDPR directions.

To analyse the collected street-level imagery, ad-hoc deep-learning-based pipelines were implemented for extracting **key information on people and the built environment** based on state-of-the-art public libraries. Among others, these include:

- GroundedSAM¹ a tool for semantic segmentation and object detection in images, used to perform 2D tree segmentation and subsequent mask generation,
- OpenSfM² a library for structure-from-motion, enabling feature extraction, image matching, and 3D reconstruction from image sets. Used to create the geo-referenced 3D point-cloud starting from pre-processed street level imagery.

Open3D³ is used to filter the point cloud (based on colour points and z-values), to remove statistical outliers and for clustering and centroid calculation.

In the context of GREENGAGE, this information has been exploited in a preliminary phase to derive several analytics and Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) that support the different case studies. As an example, these might include:

I. **Built Environment Analytics**

- Number of buildings in a specific area.
- Land use types (e.g., residential, commercial, industrial) in a specific area.
- Number and distribution of public amenities (e.g., parks, public facilities).
- Condition of public streets and sidewalks.
- Presence and condition of street furniture (e.g., benches and trash cans).

II. **Foot traffic analytics**

- Number of pedestrians per hour/day/week/month.
- Pedestrian volume in different streets/area.
- Foot traffic density in different streets/areas.
- Ratio of day-/night-time pedestrian activity.

III. **Public space usage analytics**

- Number of people using public space per hour/day/week/month.
- Type and number of activities engaged in public space (i.e., walking, standing, or sitting).
- Spatial distribution of users in public space.

IV. **Green space analytics**

- Number of trees and their distribution.
- Comparison of green spaces across different neighbourhoods.

V. **Graffiti and vandalism analytics**

- Number of instances of graffiti and vandalism.
- Locations with highest concentration of graffiti and vandalism.

VI. **Waste management analytics**

- Number of instances of littering and illegal dumping per hour/day/week/month.
- Locations with highest concentration of littering and illegal dumping.
- Types of waste found.

VII. **Parking occupancy analytics**

- Parking occupancy rate.
- Number of cars parked illegally or in restricted areas.

¹ <https://github.com/IDEA-Research/Grounded-Segment-Anything>

² <https://github.com/mapillary/OpenSfM>

³ <https://github.com/isl-org/Open3D>

The extracted information is either in the form of vector (e.g., spatial distribution of demographic features) or tabular (e.g., time-series of recorded quantities) data and can be retrieved by the GREEN Engine via web API offered by the MindEarth solution.

Figure 5: Spatial distribution of selected analytics and key performance indicators (KPIs) being derived for a sample case study area.

Selected features

Functional summary of the tool:

MindEarth for GREENGAGE app aims at automatically and systematically extract information on human presence and the built environment from distributed crowd-sourced street-level data.

Technical summary of the tool:

MindEarth for GREENGAGE app is composed of: i) a proprietary system to gather street-level imagery using smartphones or compatible 360° degree cameras; ii) advanced computer vision and artificial Intelligence techniques to automatically convert photographic images into features suitable for addressing the specific target of the end users; iii) ad-hoc solutions to derive the envisaged information layers (e.g., human presence, demographics, road condition, and other landmarks); iv) a web-platform to interactively analyse the output (e.g., Kepler.gl). Currently, the mobile application is ready for use and deployment in the Pilots. However, so far, the application has been used to generate and test trial missions and preliminary maps for identifying trees in urban environments.

Role of the tool within the GREEN Engine:

- Data curation & storage (validating and storing data)

- Data analysis (processing and analysing the data to generate new insights and knowledge)

Tool interoperability with other GREENGAGE tools:

The tool can be a valuable source of data and extracted information to be integrated into the GREEN Engine. The rewarding system has also been implemented as an integral part of the mobile application currently used to allocate tasks to the crowd. Reference data derived from in-situ surveys can become valuable training information for supporting larger scale analyses by means of satellite imagery.

Technology description

Table 2: MindEarth for GREENGAGE app technology description

Property	Value
GDPR compliancy	Compliant
Technology Readiness Level (TRL) of the tool	7 (system prototype demonstration in operational environment)
Deployment strategy of the tool	Cloud (AWS)
Main license type of the tool	Private license
Programmatic interfaces of the tool	(Web Services) REST, (Native library) JavaScript
Data types and vocabularies	(Database technology) SQL, (Open Data) Public admin datasets
User interfaces of the tool	(GUI) Graphical User Interface
Supported platforms for the user interfaces	Android, iOS and web browser

4.1.2 Atmotube PRO (Atmotube)

Atmotube PRO is a small and compact wearable sensor which can collect data on PM1, PM2.5, PM10, VOCs (Volatile Organic Compounds) and weather conditions like temperature, humidity and pressure. This sensor is designed to provide the information related the air quality (by air quality index in the range 0-100) to the citizen in real time and on the move (e.g., while walking).

Figure 6: Atmotube PRO device

Selected features

Functional summary of the tool:

Atmotube PRO is a portable, wearable air quality sensor that provides real-time information on particulate matter (PM1, PM2.5, PM10), VOCs, and weather conditions such as temperature, humidity, and pressure.

Technical summary of the tool:

The device continuously measures environmental parameters and delivers air quality index (AQI) values on a 0–100 scale, enabling mobile, citizen-level air quality monitoring

Role of the tool within the GREEN Engine:

Atmotube PRO empowers citizen engagement and participatory monitoring within GREENGAGE by providing individual users with wearable real-time, location-based air quality sensors used for air quality data collection.

Tool interoperability with other GREENGAGE tools (indicative):

The sensor’s standardized AQI output and mobile data compatibility support integration with the GREEN Engine ’s centralized data systems for enhancing spatial coverage and public awareness.

Technology description

Table 3: Atmotube PRO technology description

Property	Value
GDPR compliancy	Compliant (handles personal and GPS data per GDPR terms)
Technology Readiness Level (TRL) of the tool	9 (product is fully developed, deployed, and commercially available)
Deployment strategy of the tool	Commercial deployment via mobile app, optional cloud API access (for research/data platforms)
Main license type of the tool	Proprietary (private license – not open-source)
Programmatic interfaces of the tool	Bluetooth (open GATT and advertising packet APIs), Cloud REST API (via Atmotube Cloud), MQTT via BLE <->Wi-Fi bridge
Data types and vocabularies	Sensor data (TVOC, PM1/2.5/10, Temperature/Humidity/Pressure), transmitted in JSON over MQTT/REST; uses standard SQL/MongoDB or cloud backend; supports Copernicus/Open Data integration (via custom pipelines)
User interfaces of the tool	Smartphone app (iOS/Android GUI), CSV export, web dashboard (graphical), CLI/SDK for advanced/custom integration
Supported platforms for the user interfaces	Native apps (iOS, Android), web dashboard, and support for integration with platforms like Grafana via MQTT/REST pipelines (community-supported)

4.1.3 Collaborative environment (DEUSTO)

The Collaborative Environment (CE) has evolved as a foundational tool within the GREEN Engine, building upon its origins in the INTERLINK project. It now serves as a comprehensive digital environment that not only facilitates co-production processes between Public Administrations, private stakeholders, and citizens, but also significantly enhances team communication, document collaboration, and stakeholder engagement. The CE is central to the formation and management of Citizen Observatories (COs), providing a seamless and efficient ecosystem for citizen-led initiatives and projects.

Major Developments and New Features

- **Integration with the GREEN Engine:** The CE is now a core component of the GREENGAGE toolbox, enabling integration with a wide range of external tools and assets, and supporting advanced process planning, resource management, and community engagement.
- **CO Enablers Catalogue:** The platform offers a catalogue of Citizen Observatory (CO) enablers (formerly INTERLINKERs), which can be browsed, searched, and instantiated to support specific tasks within a co-production process. This catalogue is publicly accessible at <https://demo.greengage-project.eu/catal>.

- **Process and Team Management:** Users can create organizations, form teams, and design co-production processes. Each process is structured into customizable phases, objectives, and tasks, guided by reference schemas that can be adapted to specific contexts.
- **Gamification and Incentivization:** A new gamification engine provides points and rewards to users based on their contributions, with leaderboards to foster engagement and loyalty.
- **Replication of Success Cases:** The CE now allows the cloning of successful co-production processes, promoting knowledge sharing and the replication of best practices across different contexts.
- **Resource and Task Tracking:** Tasks and resources are managed centrally, enabling transparent tracking of contributions and results throughout a campaign's lifecycle. Resources may include datasets, workflows, visualizations, training materials, or policy briefs
- **Enhanced Interoperability:** The CE supports shallow integration with external tools (e.g., Apache NiFi, Apache Superset, Loomio, WordPress, Discourse), allowing resources and results from these tools to be linked and tracked within the co-production process.

Selected features

Functional summary of the tool

The CE provides a digital workspace that facilitates the co-production of public services and citizen science campaigns. It enables the creation and management of organizations, teams, and processes, each organized into phases, objectives, and tasks. Users are guided through customizable process schemas, with tailored recommendations of knowledge and software enablers (CO Enablers). The platform also supports the assignment, claiming, and registry of enabler use. All resources generated during a process are centrally managed and shared, ensuring transparency, collaboration, and traceability.

Technical summary of the tool

The CE is a cloud-based application developed with FastAPI (Python). It supports the definition and management of co-production processes structured into phases, goals, and tasks, with the ability to instantiate and link resources from both internal and external tools (e.g., Google Drive, Loomio, Apache NiFi, Apache Superset). The system manages roles and permissions, tracks user contributions, and integrates with the built-in gamification engine for incentivization. Its web-based SPA interface is compatible with desktop and mobile browsers, offering an accessible and responsive user experience.

Figure 7: Example of instantiation of CO Enablers (Citizen Observatory's Thematic Co-Exploration specification template).

Role of the tool within the GREEN Engine

- **Management of Citizen Observatory Campaigns:** The CE governs the “Community and Co-production Process Management” area, supporting team assembly, campaign specification, progress tracking, and acknowledgment of contributions.
- **Resource and Task Management:** The platform enables the structured planning and monitoring of tasks and resources throughout the full lifecycle of a Citizen Observatory campaign. This includes phases such as data crowdsourcing, analysis, interpretation, and communication of results, ensuring continuity and traceability.
- **Community Engagement:** The CE fosters collaboration among diverse stakeholders—citizens, public administrations, NGOs, and private actors. It facilitates the creation of organizations and teams and promotes inclusive public participation in campaigns, strengthening the role of Citizen Observatories as open, participatory ecosystems.

Tool interoperability with other GREENGAGE tools (indicative)

The CE is designed for seamless interoperability. It can be hyperlinked from the GREENGAGE website and pilot site pages, and each Thematic Co-Exploration can be associated with dedicated topics in Discourse for community dialogue. The CE can instantiate generic resources (documents, questionnaires, decision spaces) and link to external resources (workflows, datasets, visualizations) produced by other GREENGAGE tools. Provenance and results tracking are managed within the CE, ensuring continuity and traceability throughout the co-production process.

Figure 8: View of Collaborative Environment depicting the reference co-creation process model for Thematic Co-Explorations.

User Experience and Publication

Participants can assign and claim tasks, contribute resources, and be rewarded for their efforts. New observers can join public processes, and completed Thematic Co-Explorations can be published as success stories, including all relevant metadata and links to external resources.

Technology description

Table 4: Collaborative Environment technology description

Property	Value
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GDPR compliancy	Compliant (handles user data under EU GDPR via secure access and roles)
Technology Readiness Level (TRL) of the tool	6 (prototype validated in relevant environments)
Deployment strategy of the tool	Cloud-based SaaS (hosted service for collaborative co-production)
Main license type of the tool	Open Source (code available under an open-source license)
Programmatic interfaces of the tool	RESTful Webservice, Python and JavaScript native libraries (for integration and scripting)
Data types and vocabularies	SQL-backed relational data, Public administration/open data datasets
User interfaces of the tool	SPA GUI (web-based graphical interface)
Supported platforms for the user interfaces	Web browser required (desktop and mobile-compatible)

4.1.4 UrbanTEP / VISAT (GISAT)

UrbanTEP/VISAT is a web-based application designed to facilitate the visualization and analysis of Earth Observation data, statistical information, alongside co-collected datasets, with a particular emphasis on urban environments. The application offers users access to an extensive range of geospatial data, supporting diverse urban research and monitoring activities represented by up-to-date pilots' use cases wrapped into interactive user stories, as well as through a Data Explorer. Its intuitive interface enables users to explore data interactively, perform advanced analytics, and process and visualize information in multiple formats (user stories and via the Data Explorer). UrbanTEP/VISAT fosters collaboration among researchers, urban planners, and policy makers by streamlining the sharing of results and workflows. Additionally, it aims to engage visitors, encouraging them to explore the GREENGAGE project in greater depth and to participate in existing Citizen Observatories or establish their own. As a core component of a robust infrastructure, UrbanTEP/VISAT plays a central role in the dissemination strategy, interlinking GREEN Engine tools and serving as a functional reference for GREENGAGE as an EU-funded project supporting innovative, sustainable urban development powered by project methodologies.

Since the beginning of the GREENGAGE project, GISAT has made significant progress in continuously developing and enhancing VISAT (Visual and Analytical Toolboxes), a key component of the web-based applications. Throughout this process, the core open-source framework underlying VISAT has undergone major updates to address modern challenges in spatial data visualization, analysis, and interpretation. This included a fundamental replacement of libraries that the framework previously depended on, resolving issues related to third-party maintenance inactivity. Additionally, new features have been introduced to extend functionality and improve performance, enabling faster and more efficient data operations.

Figure 9: Examples of GISAT's web-based applications built on top of older VISAT versions

Within GREENGAGE, GISAT's UrbanTEP / VISAT currently functions as a comprehensive system environment composed of several integrated sub-components:

- A web application developed using VISAT, featuring two primary modules:
 - User Story Component: A curated collection of user stories that address pilot use cases and demonstrate real-world applications.
 - Explorer: An interactive data explorer designed for visualizing geospatial datasets and combining multiple data sources.
- The VISAT Visualization and Analytics Toolbox, providing advanced tools for data analysis and visualization.
- A back-end service responsible for integrating with various data services and managing data flow between components.
- A metadata service that efficiently handles large datasets, including caching and pre-processing, to optimize data visualization and user experience.

Figure 10: UrbanTEP/VISAT architecture

Major Developments and New Features:

The latest version of VISAT, now integrated as a core component of the GREENGAGE web application (UrbanTEP / VISAT), introduces several significant new features. One of the most notable advancements is the implementation of server-side rendering, which enables much faster data loading and improved user experience. This enhancement has been made possible by migrating to the Next.js framework, transforming the application from a purely front-end solution into a hybrid architecture that incorporates a lightweight backend within its core.

Additionally, the metadata structure has been thoroughly enhanced and updated, allowing for the support of a broader range of data types and improving the system's flexibility in handling diverse geospatial datasets. These improvements not only boost performance and scalability but also lay the groundwork for more advanced analytics and visualization capabilities. As a result, users benefit from quicker access to data, richer metadata, and a more robust and future-proof platform for urban Earth observation and analysis.

Since the second iteration of this deliverable, the role of UrbanTEP / VISAT has evolved further. As one of the two central web applications for delivering insights to users (the other being Apache Superset, which is used for Observatory internal analysis work), it now also serves an important dissemination function, acting as an extension of the main project website, displaying publishable maps derived from the Observatories' analyses to tell its story to a broader audience. By adopting the project's branding and visual identity, UrbanTEP / VISAT not only integrates key GREEN Engine tools—such as Apache Superset for visualizations, the GREENGAGE app's data, and Apache Druid for data storage—but also provides clear explanations about the project's objectives, available tools, and best practices. The platform guides users on how to utilize these resources and replicate successful approaches to achieve sustainable development goals, whether by joining an existing Citizen Observatory or creating a new one. Additionally, UrbanTEP / VISAT offers direct links to other project tools and the main website, encouraging users to further explore, engage, and participate in the GREENGAGE initiative.

Figure 11: Example of proposed web-application's intro page

Selected features

Functional summary of the tool:

The tool offers support for analysis of complex data in an easy-to-use web environment. It utilizes modern information technology to bridge the gap between the available mass data collections, data streams and Earth Observation (EO) - based data on the one hand and the demand of science, planning, and policy for up-to-date information on the status, properties, and dynamics of the urban system on the other hand.

Technical summary of the tool:

Key components of a web-based application are based on: (i) Backend services - set of microservices, written in TypeScript (JavaScript) for the NodeJS environment and dockerized for easier maintenance and better scalability. At the same time, storage technologies are used according to the nature of the data + own spatial data in PostgreSQL / PostGIS. Complex metadata structures and dynamic database schemas are handled using MongoDB; (ii) Frontend components - a set of packages written in ReactJS and NextJS using Redux for state management, Nivo charts for graph visualization and deck.gl for map elements.

Role of the tool within the GREEN Engine:

Data curation and storage (efficiently managing large datasets by segmenting and caching data), Data analysis (processing and analysing the data to generate new insights and knowledge), Data exploitation (putting the outputs to use, whether internally or by trading them)

Tool interoperability with other GREENGAGE tools:

The tool is meant to support the integration of the acquired data, their visualization, exploration, analysis, and provision to Pilots. One of the core assets resulting from a Citizen Observatory campaign will be the set-up of thematic exploration workflows in VISAT. Such sophisticated data analysis pipelines can be cross-referenced from the Collaborative Environment where the goals of the campaign, the team associated, and intermediary results obtained through other tools can be indexed.

Technology description

Table 5: UrbanTEP/VISAT technology description

Property	Value
GDPR compliancy	Compliant
Technology Readiness Level (TRL) of the tool	8 (System complete and qualified)
Deployment strategy of the tool	Hybrid (SaaS + On-premises)
Main license type of the tool	Open Source, some elements under private license
Programmatic interfaces of the tool	(Webservice) REST, (Native library) JavaScript, (Native library) Python
Data types and vocabularies	(Database technology) SQL, (Database technology) NoSQL – Document oriented, (Open Data) Copernicus
User interfaces of the tool	(GUI) Graphical User Interface
Supported platforms for the user interfaces	Tool requires a web browser

4.1.5 MODE (AIT)

AIT’s MODE software technology uses smartphones to automatically track the distances travelled and transport modes used, thus enabling software developers, system integrators and transport operators to design innovative mobility services. MODE provides the missing link for the development of innovative mobility services: automatic, reliable recognition of the means of transport used, and travelled routes using smartphones. Figure 12 shows a detection example.

Major Developments and New Features:

- MODE is now integrated as part of the GREENGAGE app, where it is used transparently to record user trips (including transportation mode) for selected trips.
- Due to battery and privacy considerations, not every trip is tracked; users must actively start and end tracking for trips they wish to record.
- Interoperability is now provided via a dockerized REST service, which receives raw trip input from smartphone apps and outputs trips (including transportation mode) in (Geo)JSON format. These can be visualized in tools like Apache Superset, kepler.gl, UrbanTEP/VISAT or any GIS software.

- The tool itself does not have a graphical user interface, except for tracking buttons integrated into the GREENGAGE app, ensuring seamless user experience.

Figure 12: MODE detection example © AIT

Selected features

Functional summary of the tool:

The purpose of the MODE library is to provide the out-of-the-box solution for mobility surveys via smartphone app and web service. It yields high-precision, multimodal mobility data for traffic planning, mobility research, cities, and communities. The most important functionality it provides for the goals of GREENGAGE are the routes and used travel mode(s) of users. To do so, users must actively start and end trip tracking, increasing privacy and user control.

Figure 13: Overview of MODE SaaS (NB: Only the MODE library is provided for the GREENGAGE project). ©AIT

Technical summary of the tool:

MODE is a trip recording and mode detection framework. It consists of two main software components: a data recording module for iOS and Android apps and a backend data analysis module. Figure 13 shows a high-level overview and demonstrates how to embed the MODE components into a system (AIT components are highlighted in blue, other components must be provided by a partner). Client-side tracking and data recording functionality can be added to an existing App by including the libMODE library. Once the library is configured and activated (libMODE API), it tracks user activity and records relevant movement data. The library transmits completed trips to a backend server using REST calls (REST API). On the server side, the transmitted trip data can be processed using the AIT JMDCA library. The JMDCA library is written in Java and provides core data structures, processing routines and analysis algorithms which allow application programmers to easily analyse trips and perform mode detection on the recorded data (JMDCA API). To deliver high-quality results, the JMDCA mode detection algorithm requires access to a third-party public transit routing engine (such as HERE or Google routing).

Role of the tool within the GREEN Engine :

- Data capture (recording and capturing data)
- Data analysis (processing and analysing the data to generate new insights and knowledge).

Tool interoperability with other GREENGAGE tools (indicative):

- Interoperability is primarily with the GREENGAGE app, but any tool can access the MODE service if needed.
- Data sharing and integration are enabled via the dockerized REST service, with output suitable for visualization in Apache Superset, kepler.gl, UrbanTEP/VISAT, and similar tools.
- User experience is seamless, with tracking buttons integrated into the GREENGAGE app.

Technology description

Table 6: MODE technology description

Property	Value
GDPR compliancy	Compliant. End-user must opt-in to have the location being tracked. The developer who stores the resulting routes must provide a possibility to have the data being deleted on request
Technology Readiness Level (TRL) of the tool	6 (Technology demonstrated in relevant environment)
Deployment strategy of the tool	Deployment strategy of the tool is currently evaluated by the developers of the backend which uses libMODE. Theoretically, it can be used anywhere where a Java library can be used. It is also available as a dockerized REST service.
Main license type of the tool	Library is closed source. Example how to use the library (REST endpoint) is provided open source.
Programmatic interfaces of the tool	(Webservice) REST, a simple example server of the REST endpoint is provided for the integrator.
Data types and vocabularies	Not applicable
User interfaces of the tool	No user interface, MODE is only a library
Supported platforms for the user interfaces	No user interface

4.1.6 Data Quality Dashboard (VRVis)

VRVis is Austria's leading research centre in the field of visual computing. As a COMET Competence Center, it pursues the goal of building a bridge between research and practice with partners from science, business, and industry. As experts in the fields of Visual Computing as well as Virtual and Augmented Reality, the VRVis aims at presenting data, connections, and questions in the best possible

visual and interactive form. VRVis turns data into information and images: This ranges from digital twins and computer vision to data science and virtual reality – to name just a few examples.

VRVis's Visual Analytics group specializes in developing Visual Analytics (VA) and Data Quality Assessment (DQA) tools. These offer intelligent analytics dashboards for in-depth structural analysis and quality checks of time-series and categorical data.

In the scope of the GREENGAGE project, our task was to provide a tool that is meant to support the initial quality assessment of the acquired data. By inspecting the quality of the collected data and by solving all the detected problems, we can validate the correctness of the data and increase its trust levels for future use in evidence-based decision-making. Thus, we envision this tool to be a mandatory and essential entry point for any further investigations.

The DQA tool for the GREENGAGE project offers functionality relevant to the data types and sources involved in the project, such as time-series-based air quality, noise, or meteorological data. Time-series data, especially sensor data, is prone to quality problems at different stages and aspects of measurement gathering workflow. On the hardware level, these can be problems related to power supply, communication persistence, and sensing circuit flaws. Other issues might be related to data recording and storage, various software related issues (e.g. device's companion application), or sensing device faulty installation (thus making measurement skewed by external factors).

In the Figure 14, detected missing values are displayed in the whole data pool with exact positioning of concerned missing instances marked with blue bars, visual detection of threshold breaches marked with red points, heatmap of hourly/daily values, histogram of distribution of values.

Figure 14: Illustration of a Visual Analytics toolkit for data quality check using the air quality timeseries data

Functional summary of the tool:

DQA dashboard offers interactive visual analytics dashboards for an in-depth analysis and quality check of time-series data (Figure 15). For instance, we may inspect the completeness of time-series data (i.e., detection of missing values and missing periods), the validity and uniqueness of time-series data (i.e., detection of duplicate timestamps), accuracy of the data (e.g. values outside of measuring device range) or carry out an anomaly detection (i.e., detection of outliers or unusual sequences of identical values). Following the industry standard, it will also inform the user of overall assessed data quality scores.

Technical summary of the tool:

The DQA Dashboard is a client-side frontend web application built in the JavaScript environment and utilize among others - React library for the interactive user interface, Plotly library for visualization.

Role of the tool within the GREEN Engine:

Data analysis and validation (processing and analysing the data to assure quality and reliability).

Tool interoperability with other GREENGAGE tools:

The tool is meant to support the initial quality assessment of the acquired data. By inspecting the quality of the collected data and by detecting existing problems, it can validate the correctness of these data and increase the trust in these data for future use in decision-making. Thus, the tool is envisioned to be the entry point to any further investigation.

In future Observatories, the tool will be essential to assure the highest possible quality of data captured by citizens in the Citizen Observatory campaigns which may need to be correlated with authoritative data coming from other more reliable sources of data.

Technology description

Table 7: Data Quality Dashboard technology description

Property	Value
GDPR compliancy	Compliant
Technology Readiness Level (TRL) of the tool	8 (System complete and qualified)
Deployment strategy of the tool	On-Premise
Main license type of the tool	Open source
Programmatic interfaces of the tool	None (front-end only JavaScript/TypeScript application)
Data types and vocabularies	(Database technology) Apache Druid (SQL-compatible)
User interfaces of the tool	(GUI) Graphical User Interface
Supported platforms for the user interfaces	Tool requires a web browser

4.1.7 GREENGAGE app (Sushi Dev + Digitalsunray)

The key idea behind the GREENGAGE app is to provide a universal tool to help engage Citizen Observatories in the research of the project through completion of pilot-defined tasks in a comprehensible and gamified manner. The GREENGAGE app allows for a broader scope of research like visitor density, free-text surveys, route evaluation and overall, POI (Point of Interest) for, e.g., liveability reporting and validation. In addition, a comprehensive and highly customizable environment was created for defining and modelling tasks.

The GREENGAGE app addresses the specific needs of the pilot activities, considering insights from WP2. The resulting findings and refined requirements were incorporated into the development of the GREENGAGE app and its backend infrastructure. Focus was put on user friendliness—both for backend users and on the observatory side—to enable Observatories to be executed efficiently and, above all, iteratively via the app. In addition, deeper integration of AIT's MODE library as the leading GPS tracking and analysis tool was implemented as part of the project.

Following the feedback from version 1, more in-depth input was received, which shaped the development of version 2 of the GREENGAGE app. The focus was primarily on improving the user experience and expanding the functional scope, particularly on the backend side.

In response to the limitations identified in version 1, the administration interface underwent a complete refactoring to allow for faster and more efficient entry of information and tasks into the system.

The improvements aimed to increase automation and enable quicker responses to user input.

The following images show selected development screens from the adapted version of the GREENGAGE app.

Figure 15: GREENGAGE app development screens © Digitalsunray

Figure 16: User interface screens of the GREENGAGE app

Selected features

Functional summary of the tool:

Tailored to the generic requirements of the pilots, GREENGAGE app now has an expanded functional set. The new interface allows for evaluation of Points of Interest and City Sectors through:

- reporting features
- multiple- and single- choice questionnaires
- a rating system (indicative)

- free text surveys
- geo-tracking via the integration of the MODE library.

Users can add their presence spots, describe their means of accessing them through different transport types, evaluate the air quality/noise level/security level/etc. through the tasks defined by the pilots as relevant metrics. The trending and relevant topics can be filtered out as well as expanded. Information about the POI is summarized upon cumulation of feedback and calculation of Liveability Indexes out of combined metrics, e.g., in Superset.

Field tests with a diverse user base revealed significant potential for broad-reaching improvements in this area, prompting targeted refinements to enhance usability and clarity.

Who can use the tool

Citizens, stakeholders (via the Backend) with their mobile phones (iOS and Android).

Technical summary of the tool:

The GREENGAGE app consists of three user accessible sections:

- App (client)
- Backend (Microservice landscape) - <https://api-v2.greengage.dev/>
- Admin-Interface - <https://console-stage.greengage.dev>

The Client (App, Web-App) consumes and pushes data into the backend via a single point – the “Gateway” or “Router” which is an Apollo Server. This Apollo Server makes use of the Sub- and Supergraph Interface of GraphQL (more details:

<https://www.apollographql.com/docs/federation/v1/subgraphs/>), which is the best way to connect a widespread landscape of different application.

Figure 17: Example for a GraphQL Microservice Infrastructure © Digitalsunray

The illustration above demonstrates the used concept of the landscape. All data transfer takes place via the Router which is a hosted service. By using this concept of “Federation” the infrastructure can also make use of concepts like “Entities” (<https://www.apollographql.com/docs/federation/entities/>) which allow to link and point to different datasets and seamlessly connect those. Although the application might be a hosted service – via the federation concept the created data can be used within third party services.

GraphQL allows the user/pilots to access exactly what they need to know after the GREENGAGE app aggregates the data.

All those functions are accessible via an easy-to-use admin tool hosted at console-stage.greengage.dev and through the API (<https://api-v2.greengage.dev/>) which is the central point of entry. Additionally, the application uses fairu.app a Digital Asset Management (DAM) solution which allows to manage copyrights and licenses.

The next screenshots show the current GREENGAGE app's backend GUI: The Login screen (Figure 18), the Dashboard (Figure 19) and the Task management (Figure 20).

GREENGAGE ^{Beta}

E-Mail

Password

Remember me

Login

or

GREENGAGE Project Account

[Create free account](#) [Forgot your password?](#)

Figure 18: Login screen for the admin console with support of GREENGAGE Login system.

GREENGAGE ^{Beta} EN Help Sign out

Testing

Home

Collecting data

Tasks and missions

Point of interests

Surveys

Analyze

Spots and marker

Tracking and Analytics

Tenant settings

Users

Roles and permissions

Settings

MP Manuel Pirker-Ihl

Hello Manuel Pirker-Ihl!

Welcome to the GREENGAGE App Console

Open invites for you

Turano Valley Public Archaeology Campaign Accept Decline

GREENGAGE App-News

UX improvements for mission creation and more

Enhancements for GREENGAGE

First steps with the GREENGAGE App

The GREENGAGE App is a versatile tool that seamlessly integrates with your citizen observatory campaign. It enables you to uncover issues and assess needs by creating customized tasks and surveys—and can also be embedded into any other application. All you need to start is our app.

[Download iOS App](#) [Download Android App](#)

Figure 19: Dashboard for the GREENGAGE app Admin interface

Figure 20: Task management within the GREENGAGE Admin interface

From an architectural perspective, the technical barrier to adopting the platform by observatories has been significantly reduced by shifting from a self-hosted setup to a free Software-as-a-Service (SaaS) solution. This strategic decision enables observatories to get up and running within minutes instead of hours, streamlining the onboarding process considerably. By minimizing the complexity and time required for deployment, the platform is now much more accessible, which is expected to lead to a faster and more effective activation of individuals within the observatories.

Major features of the of the tool are:

- User management (GREENGAGE app users)
- Role management
- Automatic SSL-Management for the tools
- Image-Proxy via fairu.app
- Custom observatory management
- Task Management, Point of Interest Management, Spot-Management
- Mode-Data management
- Survey and Data-Management
- File Upload System
- Further Datasets.

What is an Image Proxy:

Early in the project the need for an optimized image delivery pipeline occurred. Hence, the previously integrated Image-Proxy had been replaced by fairu.app in the second phase. This integration allows to extract and load images in an optimized way which reduces the overhead in data transfer. Consequently, the native apps (iOS/Android) consumed less traffic and got faster.

Role of the tool within the GREEN Engine:

The role of the GREENGAGE app is important and highly integrated in various parts of the toolbox. The app and the admin interface are a very good starting point and the highly adaptive software enables to get fast and instant qualitative feedback from the participating audience of an observatory.

The backend provides data collection monitoring and visualization capabilities. It is an interactive tool for Citizen Observatory management and outcome communication between COs and Pilots/Observatory owners (tasks-data-feedback). The backend also allows for a fast mode-tracking information extraction (Figure 21).

Figure 21: UX for the MODE-Lib Tracking visualisation

Tool interoperability with other GREENGAGE tools:

The GREENGAGE app directly integrates AIT's MODE library. The MindEarth for GREENGAGE app has been integrated via a waterfall-hierarchy task distribution (deep linking) – initial Observatory tasks involving MindEarth missions' analysis will require the user to switch to the aforementioned tool to design and conduct the missions and the GREENGAGE app shows those missions in the map and Observers are sent to the external app via a deep link. Both tools are integrated into the GREENGAGE app platform as a GraphQL Subgraph, which allow users and pilots to connect in an easy way.

Tutorials for using GREENGAGE app can be found at <https://docs-stage.greengage.dev/>.

Technology description

Table 8: GREENGAGE app technology description

Property	Value
GDPR compliancy	Compliant. The data collected with the GREENGAGE app is stored in datacentres located in the European Union (Digital Ocean – Kubernetes Infrastructure)
Technology Readiness Level (TRL) of the tool	6 (Technology demonstrated in relevant environment)
Deployment strategy of the tool	Apple App Store, Google Play Store by Digitalsunray with Digitalsunray- or GREENGAGE accounts Infrastructure: Kubernetes Cluster hosted by Sushi Dev (on Digital Ocean)
Main license type of the tool	General usage of the GREENGAGE app is unrestricted and open for any user, also after the lifetime of the project. The codebase is a private resource of the developers (Digitalsunray/Sushi Dev) (closed source). The template for a RESTful to GraphQL Adapter is provided via MIT-licence in the main repository of the GREENGAGE Toolbox. The https://console-stage.greengage.dev/ is a free-tier SaaS-tool.

Programmatic interfaces of the tool	The GREENGAGE app uses a GraphQL Interface which accesses the data from a Kubernetes based microservice landscape. Via a management tool (on https://console-stage.greengage.dev) Observatory owners can access the tool and its datasets. Every Observatory owner has access to the above router which is maintained and hosted via the Kubernetes SaaS-tool. The API and underlying data architecture are tenant-based, ensuring strict separation of data between different Observatories. This multi-tenant approach guarantees that each Observatory's data remains fully isolated and secure, providing both privacy and scalability across multiple deployments.
Data types and vocabularies	JSON structure + highly typed Entities
User interfaces of the tool	GREENGAGE app (Android, iOS) console-stage.greengage.dev (Admin) api-v2.greengage.dev (Endpoint)
Supported platforms for the user interfaces	iOS and Android devices.

4.1.8 Text analysis – sentiment / summarisation (UWE)

While executing the GREENGAGE pilot Observatories, it became evident that textual analysis services were needed to effectively process data collected through surveys, interviews, and discussions. In response, UWE developed a prototype text analysis tool and applied it to pilot data.

Figure 22: Text Analysis service architecture

Sentiment analysis (UWE): Using Large Language Models (LLMs) - Flan-T5, sentiment analysis is performed on transcripts from videos, interviews, and written texts from citizens. Inputs are processed by the LLM to detect emotional tone and classified with a binary label (1 for positive sentiment and 0 for negative). This approach enables rapid assessment of overall emotional trends, helping to quickly understand the prevailing mood or attitude expressed across large volumes of collected data. The

models used are run locally to avoid sharing information with third party software. Initial evaluation is compared against ground truth and results are promising.

For sentiment classification, the Flan-T5 model was selected as the core technology. This model is openly available and can be accessed either by downloading it directly or through appropriate APIs such as Hugging Face's platform. This approach ensures that sensitive information remains private and is not shared with third parties, as the entire process can be conducted locally. The chosen Flan-T5 model variant is sufficiently lightweight to run on a standard laptop without requiring specialised hardware or cloud computing resources. This makes the solution accessible to users with typical consumer-grade equipment while maintaining reasonable processing speeds and memory requirements. The model operates using a zero-learning approach, meaning no additional training or fine-tuning is necessary, making this solution accessible to those with minimal coding skills.

The sentiment classification is performed using a structured prompt template: "Please perform Sentiment Classification task. Given the sentence, assign a sentiment label from *{labels}*. Return label only. Sentence: *{text}*". Users customize this by replacing two placeholders: *{labels}* with their desired categories (e.g., "positive, negative") and *{text}* with the input sentence to analyse. When processing text through this system, the model analyses the input sentence and returns an appropriate sentiment label based on the predefined categories provided in the prompt. The labels can be customized according to specific requirements, whether using simple positive/negative classifications or more nuanced categories including neutral sentiments or emotional granularities.

Summarization and thematic analysis (UWE): As part of the Bristol Pilot, a text summarization service leveraging LLaMA 3 was developed to summarize content from qualitative comments submitted by citizens through the EBLN25 platform. This tool is designed to help the Pilot owner and other stakeholders quickly grasp key themes from large volumes of textual survey data. To support experimentation and broader usability, a stream lit web application has been created, enabling users to upload their own datasets and explore summarization across various contextual settings. Initial evaluations by domain experts have shown that summarisation quality can vary depending on the context provided, an insight that is guiding further refinement. Building on this foundation, the work is now being extended to include thematic summarization, aiming to group and highlight recurring topics and concerns more effectively. This evolving capability holds strong potential for enhancing civic engagement analysis and decision-making.

4.1.9 Video analytics (UWE)

Dashcam-based Road Defects Detection (UWE): One of the Pilot use cases required processing dashcam data (Figure 23). In response to this need, the image analysis work has been successfully extended to dashcam footage, aiming to spot a wide range of roadway defects for the Turano Pilot, including potholes, surface cracks, faded road markings, and vandalised road signs. As part of the initial training phase, we deployed CVAT24 to label representative frames from the dashcam videos. Further, we integrated Segment Anything Model (SAM) model inside CVAT to speed up and accelerate the annotation process. An AI model has been developed, and an early prototype already demonstrates promising results, offering side-by-side visual analysis of identified defects. The final release aims to generate output structured in JSON files detailing all roadway defects and respective metadata, enabling research and development for downstream urban use cases. This is an exciting and evolving area of work, with ongoing interactions to increase accuracy, usability, and scalability.

The sentiment analysis, summarisation and dashcam analytics services were not part of the initial plan for GREENGAGE offerings. They were proposed in response to discussions and pilot requirements arising during the project. Therefore, these services are still in the early stages of active development. Appropriate training materials and manuals will be developed as the services are further developed and made available to pilots for use.

Figure 23: Original dashcam video (left), defect detections video (right).

4.2 Pilot specific tools used in GREENGAGE project

The Pilot cities within the GREENGAGE project exhibit a diverse range of characteristics, including varying levels of technical expertise and experience. This diversity necessitates a tailored approach to the selection and implementation of technological tools. While some pilots may not possess an extensive technical background, others, such as Bristol, bring significant experience in deploying their own technologies or leveraging stakeholder-provided solutions to address specific segments of the technological pipeline, effectively meeting their unique requirements, which, in the best case, should be capable of being integrated into the GREEN Engine, to enhance the Observatories' understanding of their area under investigation.

This heterogeneity in technical proficiency among the Pilot cities underscored the importance of adaptability and flexibility in the toolset employed. The GREENGAGE project recognized and accommodated these differing needs, ensuring that the technological infrastructure is designed to be accessible and beneficial for all Pilots, regardless of their initial technical capacity. This inclusive approach not only maximizes the project's reach and impact but also fosters an environment of collaborative learning and knowledge sharing among the diverse stakeholders involved. By accommodating the varying technical backgrounds and capabilities of the Pilot cities, GREENGAGE aimed to facilitate the seamless integration and utilization of the chosen tools, ultimately contributing to the success of the project's overarching objectives.

4.2.1 Verplaatsingsdata app used by North Brabant

In GREENGAGE's North Brabant pilot, mobility pattern data played a pivotal role in promoting sustainable transportation data, as it allows for the identification of key cycling flows or corridors. The Verplaatsingsdata app is part of a larger Provincial project in North Brabant and is therefore already well-known amongst users and comes with already existing cycling flow data. While envisioned as a more suitable and accessible tool for the North Brabant pilot in pursuing practical, healthy, and eco-conscious modes of travel, its availability and regional exclusivity limited the uptake during the lifetime of the project.

The Verplaatsingsdata app (Figure 24) – using the Sesamo app tool skeleton with a Mobidot Tracking tool - tracks the travel patterns of users through their smart phone and determines which section of their trip is performed and with which modality. The app runs continuously in the background of phone without requiring activation. Apart from GPS tracking, some situational dimensions are also gathered. When tracking a representative sample of the analysed area over a longer period, an origin-destination matrix per modality can be generated.

Figure 24: Verplaatsingsdata app (Mobidot) interface.

Functional summary of the tool:

Respondents can download the app, which is designed and optimised for travel data, tracking both the route legs and mode of transport. The app automatically starts measuring with minimal load for the respondent – turning the app on is not a requirement as it works in the background. The mode is shared with the respondent and likely travel objectives are suggested. Respondents can review their trips, remove or validate the suggestions, and get an overview of their trips. The data of trips and the modalities per leg of the trip is uploaded to a server, to be processed in data analysis programmes.

Role of the tool within the GREEN Engine:

- Data Gathering: The GPS tracking function ensures modality, trip, and origin-destination data is gathered through the province.
- Data Curation: Users can verify suggested trip objectives or adjust them.

The Verplaatsingsdata app was supposed to be used in the North Brabant pilot due to its embedded user base, as well as broader use in Provincial projects, ensuring recognition and improving uptake. However, the accessibility of the tool was low due to delayed delivery, as well as a steep entry curve due to an invite-based login requirement. The data gathering – both GPS points and modality – functionality was instead fulfilled by the GREENGAGE app. An added benefit of this shift was the easier addition of surveys during the act of data gathering, instead of being sent after the activity only. The GREENGAGE app therewith also provided the required data curation possibility, by allowing for qualitative information next to geopositioned data. The delayed and limited availability of the Verplaatsingsdata app outweighed the local familiarity with the tool. The accessibility and adaptability of the GREENGAGE app provided an alternative.

Next to the accessibility, the focus of the North Brabant pilot shifted from logging trips to assessing bike path maintenance. As the Verplaatsingsdata app only gathered GPS displacement data and trip functions, the app was less suited for the new data focus of the pilot. Hence, the wait and planned use for the pilot were abandoned in favour of the GREENGAGE app.

Tool interoperability with other GREENGAGE tools (indicative):

- The gathered mobility data was envisioned as the start of the data pipeline. This technology enables policy makers to enlist citizens in gathering mobility data – specifically, routing and origin-destination data. The curation, analysis, and visualisation come later. Therefore, the gathered data could be linked to the VRVis data quality platform, and the data might be visualised in the DigiTwin in the future (as no data was gathered using the app, this link was not explored).
- A deeper understanding of the travel patterns, modality use, and roads (not) taken, allows COs to study the movement pattern throughout a neighbourhood and determine the accessibility of different modalities. This includes the logging of the effect of road closures as well as the intensity of the traffic during specific months within an area. This line of inquiry was not pursued in the North Brabant pilot and this requirement could be fulfilled by the GREENGAGE app instead.

- The app can also send out a selective survey to some of its users to enhance the gathered data with some qualitative data. This capacity was still available, but a broader accessibility of surveys was provided through the GREENGAGE app.

Technology description

Table 9: Verplaatsingsdata app technology description

Property	Value
GDPR compliancy	Compliant
Technology Readiness Level (TRL) of the tool	8 (System complete and qualified)
Deployment strategy of the tool	Software
Main license type of the tool	Account based access, closed source
Programmatic interfaces of the tool	(GUI) Graphical User Interface
Data types and vocabularies	Not relevant
User interfaces of the tool	Mobile app
Supported platforms for the user interfaces	Android, iOS

4.2.2 Urban Belonging app used by Copenhagen

The Urban Belonging (UB) project is an innovative initiative focused on studying place attachments using a comprehensive digital, visual, and participatory methodology. At its core lies the photovoice UB App, a powerful tool that encourages participants to document their urban experiences through digital photographs, annotations, and reactions to others' images. This application is part of a larger toolkit designed to gather, process, and visualize this data effectively. The UB App represents a collaborative effort involving various stakeholders, including researchers, planners from Gehl Architects, and members of six marginalized communities, as well as citizen engagement professionals. Their valuable inputs have played a crucial role in shaping the app's design specifications, ensuring that it facilitates inclusive data collection while addressing concerns related to privacy, as well as visual and spatial literacy.

The UB App is not only accessible on both Android and iPhone platforms but is also available in multiple languages including Danish, English, Dutch, and Italian. Its user-friendly interface empowers participants to capture urban experiences in a personal and situated manner. The metadata accompanying each photograph, including location and sentiment, provides a rich source for both qualitative and quantitative analyses. This granularity of data enables various types of demographic and post-demographic assessments, shedding light on commonalities in what people document and where they navigate within the city. Additionally, the app fosters a diverse empirical ground by inviting participants to react to one another's photos, revealing the diverse perspectives through which individuals perceive the urban environment.

The UB App has been successfully employed in the Urban Belonging project, which took place in Copenhagen in 2022. This project was a collaborative effort between researchers from different universities and professionals from Gehl Architects. The primary objective was to gain diverse insights into how the city functions as a space of belonging for marginalized communities. The project was characterized by two central tasks: the development of the UB App to capture feelings of urban attachment, and the creation of data representations to facilitate meaningful conversations among participants.

One of the distinctive features of the UB toolkit is its participatory design approach. The process of tool development was influenced by various actors, including researchers, urban professionals, and representatives from marginalized communities. Each group provided unique perspectives on how the app should be designed, ensuring that it caters to a wide range of user needs. The involvement of community organizations and project participants, representing minority groups in Copenhagen, was

particularly crucial. Their inputs helped address issues of accessibility, trust, and inclusivity, which are often overlooked in traditional urban engagement exercises.

The UB App has recently been tested within the GREENGAGE framework and is scheduled for use in a datathon in autumn of 2025. This event will serve as an opportunity to explore the app's capabilities in new urban contexts and assess its effectiveness in facilitating inclusive data collection, participatory mapping, and citizen engagement. The outcomes of the datathon will help refine the integration of the UB App into the broader GREENGAGE platform and inform future applications across different pilot areas.

4.2.3 DigiTwin (Argaleo)

DigiTwin, also known as the Argaleo Digital Twin City, is a cloud based digital twin/atlas made by Argaleo. Within GREENGAGE, this data repository and its visualising components are used by the Province of North Brabant and Breda University of Applied Science, a University of Applied Science with several academies in Breda, the Netherlands, specifically by the research department of the Academy of Built Environment and Logistics. Following is a discussion of the general and technical functioning of the DigiTwin, the uses within GREENGAGE, its positioning in the data pipeline, and its special role as a GREEN Engine tool.

Functionality:

DigiTwin uses a cloud platform which contains different data sets from various sources to visualize the static and dynamic/real-time data for cities, regions and the whole Netherlands. These datasets include different fields such as urban design, mobility, energy, and demography. Users, based on their needs, can request access to just a set or all of them and run multi-purpose analyses and 3D visualizations. DigiTwin is a modular web application which can be customized and developed based on the needs and objectives of different users. The main datasets of this application are reliable open-source datasets which are usually provided by governmental organizations such as Netherlands' Cadastre (Land Registry and Mapping Agency), CBS (Central Bureau of Statistics), the Ministry of Infrastructure and Water Management and municipalities. Users, based on their needs and objectives, could link their data sets into available and integrated data sets, to perform specific analysis and customize their visualization by adding different layers of information.

Users can perform geo-spatial analyses by combining datasets and visualize the results in 3D, 2D or even through tables and charts. Different kinds of datasets can be integrated into DigiTwin, such as Geopackage, Shapefile, CSV and GeoTIFF formats as well as WFS links.

In the GREENGAGE project, the GPS and questionnaires data, gathered by the Citizen Observatories in the North Brabant pilot, were translated into compatible input file formats and integrated into the DigiTwin datasets. By qualitatively co-analysing the quantitative and visualized data in the DigiTwin, this technology can help the North Brabant pilot pursue co-creation of sustainable developments in the region.

Technical structure:

DigiTwin uses Environment Server ("Omgevingsserver" in Dutch) which is a cloud platform developed by Geo ICT experts. The elements of Environment Server are shown in Figure 25. In this figure the Environment Server is the core which is fed by data sources and used for different applications.

Figure 25: Elements of Environment Server and its working mechanism (SPOTInfo, 2020a).

The short explanations of the process and main elements are as follows (SPOTInfo, 2020b).

Data sources:

Environment Server is based on the spatial open data sources that the Dutch government currently offers. In addition to the system of basic registers, Environment Server uses various data sources such as the National Register of Childcare; CBS demographic data; the Risk map including the flood models; the Register of National Monuments; Spatial (zoning) plans (IMRO); the Energy Labels of homes; the Antenna Register; the current Digital Elevation Model.

The datasets are anonymized before integration into the twin. DigiTwin is a license-based service, ensuring that only involved researchers or specialists will have access to the visualized datasets. Several datasets are open data or public information, whereas more privacy sensitive datasets are only integrated on request by the license holder. By accessing their own shell, the sensitive data is thereby protected.

Data management:

The DigiTwin imports the source data and enriches the data. The SPOTInfo solution periodically retrieves the current source data and then combines and further enriches that data. This 'data engine' is highly optimised for this data processing and is constantly being improved.

Data store:

The resulting Environment Server data platform contains a large collection of datasets that cannot be found (of this quality) anywhere else in the Netherlands (regarding their topicality, reliability and completeness). As more (government) data becomes available and other social themes become relevant, the Environment Server data platform reflects these developments.

Data Services:

The managed data services ensure access to the data platform. Robust open-source techniques are used to make the data available in common ways. The following outputs are available:

- Map images: as WMS (Web Map Service), WMTS (Web Map Tile Service), TMS (Tile Map Service), 3D vector tiles, 2D Open Layers.
- Datasets (tables with data): as WFS (Web Feature Service, OGC standard); via a REST API; and further (optional) in .OBJ format (for 3D objects), and in the future as CSV / Excel tables.
- OBJ export for e.g., 3D-printing and Virtual/Augmented Reality and gaming.

Applications:

Environment Server supports its own 3D viewer in the browser based on Open-Source Map box technology. The OGC data services can also be used in common GIS software. Libraries such as Open Layers, Leaflet and Map box GL can also consume the data.

Uses:

DigiTwin provides visual output of datasets but also contains some built-in analysis functions. These analyses centre on mobility metrics, such as accessibility isochrones of locations (bus stops, schools, etc.), the supporting network justifying these accessibility metrics (like an overview of the spread and functioning of the bicycle network), but also the mapping of origin-destination relations in relation to specific locations. Next to these quantitative mobility analyses, qualitative survey data, like neighbourhood inquiries, can be mapped as well. Most analyses work with record data, although some real time visualisations of traffic situations are also possible.

DigiTwin merges the gathered bike path maintenance data in the North Brabant pilot. Citizen Observers cycled over designated bike paths and scored the quality of the lighting, roadside maintenance, surface maintenance, and presence of obstacles. Additionally, a general verdict of the quality of bike experience was added. The selected bike paths have an institutional quality level (good, mediocre, bad). The institutional levels are added as colours over the specific cycling paths in the DigiTwin. In a different layer, the scores from subjective users are added per category. These two layers can now be compared, highlighting discrepancies in institutional maintenance assessment and those experienced by cyclists. The data-repository nature of the DigiTwin allows for further comparison with different datasets, such as geolocated bollards, cycling intensities, road width, and accident counts, amongst others. The addition of subjective data in the DigiTwin will then allow for a more detailed investigation into the causes of discrepancies in maintenance experiences; providing a richer dataset than just the institutional assessment.

Data Pipeline:

The DigiTwin itself is not capable of capturing data, nor does the platform itself curate data. On request, curated datasets can be integrated into the twin. The platform can analyse different datasets, with some functions focused on accessibility or range. However, most of the analyses stem from the visual combination of different data sets, which require interpretation. The main role of the DigiTwin then is in Data exploitation and co-creation. The curation process, as well as the visualized analyses facilitate real life conversation with involved stakeholders – like CO members. Going through the process of exploiting the data for useful insights sets up the possibility for co-creation. This requires taking citizens through the process of data curation, and analysis, to enrich the quantitative visualized results with qualitative additions.

As a conversation facilitator, the DigiTwin played a role in the later steps of the data processing pipeline. Therefore, GREENGAGE's specific data gathering technologies MODE and the GREENGAGE app's collected survey data were connected to the DigiTwin.

Relation to the GREEN Engine:

Within the GREENGAGE project, the DigiTwin was and is a repository for data gathered by Citizen Observatories. Data gathering technologies of the GREEN engine could be used to add co-created datasets to the platform. The DigiTwin itself functioned as conversation and analysis facilitator, highlighting relevant analyses or indicating missing information. Due to the focus on the Dutch context, the applicability of the DigiTwin in other GREENGAGE pilots was limited. While its web-based nature makes it accessible, the data focus on Dutch context and the closed nature of the platform did not provide a connection back to the GREEN Engine. Instead, as a digital twin or urban dashboard, the DigiTwin can serve an exemplary function on how digital twins can contribute to co-creation in smart governance.

The DigiTwin served a unique function within the North Brabant pilot focussing specifically on the Netherlands. It is a licensed cloud-based platform (TRL 9) that is already used by several governments and companies in the Netherlands. Because of this operational nature in the Netherlands, the platform poses a challenge for international use. The detailed focus, through available data, on the Netherlands makes it less applicable to pilots where there is no data basis existing. As such, the DigiTwin should be approached more as an exemplary case on how to use digital twins or atlases in smart governance.

Due to its role as local data visualizer and discussion facilitator in the Netherlands, the technical specifications of the DigiTwin for application in different scenarios or contexts is of less relevance. The

platform is static in that it always has the same analysis capabilities; only new datasets can be added for further visualization.

Selected features

Functional summary of the tool:

Users are presented with a virtual map of the Netherlands which they can navigate through, explore data and perform analyses. Data layers can be combined to show the interrelation between data sets. Different scenarios can be visualized and discussed in co-creation sessions.

Technical summary of the tool:

Argaleo's DigiTwin is a modular web application which can be customised and developed based on the needs and objectives of different users. The main datasets of this application are reliable open-data datasets which are usually provided by governmental organisations such as the Netherlands' Cadastre (Land Registry and Mapping Agency), CBS (Central Bureau of Statistics), the Ministry of Infrastructure and Water Management and municipalities. However, the users of this application are not only the governments, including municipalities and provincial organisations, but also research organisations, universities, companies and entrepreneurs.

Role of the tool within the GREEN :

Data analysis (processing and analysing the data to generate new insights and knowledge), Data exploitation (putting the outputs to use, whether internally or by trading them), Collaborative / co-creation support, Crowdsourcing.

Tool interoperability with other GREENGAGE tools:

The Digital Twin functioned on its own in the North Brabant pilot, since the Digital Twin is an online application uniquely made for the Netherlands. Therefore, this tool was not made available to other pilots. However, data gathered by other GREEN Engine tools, such as the GREENGAGE app could be integrated and visualised in the DigiTwin.

Management of the Citizen Observatory processes executed thanks to Digital Twin could also be supported by the Collaborative Environment of GREEN Engine.

Technology description

Table 10: DigiTwin technology description

Property	Value
GDPR compliancy	Compliant
Technology Readiness Level (TRL) of the tool	9 (Actual system proven in operational environment)
Deployment strategy of the tool	Cloud (SaaS)
Main license type of the tool	Private license (closed source). Argaleo is subcontracted by BUAS and they are responsible for the service. As this private technology is not available in the GREEN engine, not all the specifications are made public.
Programmatic interfaces of the tool	Confidential
Data types and vocabularies	(Database technology) SQL, (Open Data) Public admin datasets
User interfaces of the tool	(GUI) Graphical User Interface
Supported platforms for the user interfaces	Tool requires a web browser

4.3 Open-source tools adopted by GREENGAGE

Since the second iteration, the list of open-source tools has evolved to better support the project's growing technical and organizational needs. Several new tools were adopted to extend existing capabilities and fill specific gaps in the workflow.

For instance, **Kepler.gl** was introduced as an open-source visualization tool during the Turano Valley datathon to display mobility and air quality data. It addressed limitations in tools like **Apache Superset**, which offers only basic support for geospatial vector data. Kepler.gl enhanced the ability to deliver visual insights to citizens at a time when **UrbanTEP/VISAT** was still under development and dependent on finalized narratives and input data that were not yet available.

Open-source tools play a critical role in extending and supporting the **GREEN Engine** workflow by enabling flexible, transparent, and collaborative solutions throughout the project lifecycle. As the project evolved, so did the need for specialized tools that could complement core components and adapt to ongoing technical and user-oriented requirements.

4.3.1 Apache NiFi

Apache NiFi is an open-source data integration tool designed to automate the flow of data between systems in a secure, controlled, and extensible manner. It serves as a powerful platform for orchestrating data movement and supporting a wide range of data integration scenarios. NiFi operates through a web-based user interface that allows users to design and manage data flows through a visual representation of the process. NiFi excels in ingesting, transforming and transferring data across various sources and destinations. Regarding to the data ingestion, NiFi facilitates the ingestion of data from different sources, such as databases, IoT devices, log files, and more. It supports a variety of protocols, including HTTP, MQTT, and JDBC, enabling seamless connectivity with diverse systems. The main component of NiFi is the processor. Processors allow users to enrich, filter, and manipulate data on the fly. Among the available processors, those for data acquisition (e.g., ConsumeElasticSearch, QueryDatabaseTable, ConsumeKafka, GetHDFS, GetMongo, FetchFile, FetchS3Object, GetHTTP), for data transformation (e.g., ConvertRecord, ExtractText, ReplaceText, FlattenJson, SplitJson, JoltTransformRecord, MergeContent, ExecuteScript) and for data storage (PutDatabaseRecord, PublishKafka, PublishMQTT, PutEmail, PutFile, PutMongo) can be found. In case a custom processor is needed, NiFi provides the capabilities for its development.

Figure 26: Apache NiFi interface demonstration screenshot

Figure 27: Example of a NiFi dataflow

Role within the Citizen Observatory

Apache NiFi can play an important role within the Citizen Observatory, contributing significantly to the “Analysis and Visualisation for Insights Generation” area of concern. Thanks to its wide variety of processors for ingesting data, NiFi facilitates the seamless integration of data from diverse community sources into the observation process. It ensures that data generated through community engagement activities, such as app generated by mobile apps, surveys or collaborative platforms, is efficiently ingested and prepared for further processing. NiFi acts as a central hub for collecting, filtering, and curating data contributed by citizens. In addition to its ability to ingest data from various source, it can apply transformations, and route information based on predefined conditions, ensuring that crowdsourced data is curated in real-time. NiFi can become a fundamental tool for maintaining data quality, relevance, and consistency. In a nutshell, NiFi serves for data movement and transformation, enabling the efficient transfer of curated data to tools focused on analysis and visualization. By automating the flow of data between different analytics and visualization platforms, NiFi ensures that insights derived from one tool can be seamlessly integrated into the analytical workflows of subsequent areas. This contributes to a cohesive and integrated approach to deriving meaningful insights from the observed data. On the other hand, NiFi provides a user-friendly web-based interface that empowers users to design, monitor, and manage data flows visually. Users can interact with the tool to create, modify, and optimize data pipelines without the need for extensive coding or scripting. This visual representation enhances the accessibility of the tool across diverse team members, including those with varying technical expertise.

Interoperability with other tools

Apache NiFi excels in interoperability, seamlessly integrating with other tools within the Citizen Observatory to facilitate cohesive data sharing and processing. As mentioned before, NiFi enables the ingestion of data from various sources and can seamlessly share this data with other tools in the project. For example, data collected from sensors, mobile apps or community platforms can be efficiently ingested by NiFi and shared with analytical tools for further processing. NiFi supports a wide array of

integration protocols, including REST, HTTP, MQTT, and more. This flexibility ensures compatibility with diverse tools and systems within the project. NiFi's data transformation capabilities are crucial for ensuring that data is in a compatible format for downstream tools. Whether it is preparing data for visualisation or analysis, NiFi can apply transformations to align the data with the requirements of specific tools, promoting seamless integration. Regarding the user experience continuity, NiFi provides a visual interface for designing data flows, enhancing the user experience. The visual representation of data pipelines remains familiar, regardless of whether the user is working on data ingestion, transformation, or routing. This ensures that users can easily navigate and manage data flows throughout the project. The provenance tracking aligns with the project's need for transparency and traceability. The metadata associated with each data flow, including its origin, transformations applied, and destination, contributes to a comprehensive understanding of the data's journey. This integrated approach supports a seamless user experience by providing context and insight into the data's history.

4.3.2 Apache Superset

Apache Superset (or Superset) is an open-source data visualization and data exploration platform designed for modern data teams. It empowers users to create and share interactive dashboards and engaging visualizations, offering a rich set of features to explore and understand large and complex datasets. Developed under the auspices of the Apache Software Foundation, Superset integrates effortlessly with most SQL-speaking databases, making it an incredibly versatile tool in the world of big data analytics. Superset is particularly well-suited for creating charts, dashboards, and conducting SQL queries to datasets. Its user-friendly interface enables even those without extensive coding experience to build informative visualisations (Figure 28). This accessibility is combined with powerful analytical capabilities, allowing users to create custom visualisations, apply filters, and drill down into specific data points. The tool supports a wide range of chart types, from basic line and bar charts to more complex types like geospatial charts, making it a flexible choice for various data visualisation needs.

Figure 28: Example of Apache Superset Dashboard

One of the primary features of Apache Superset is its intuitive and responsive dashboard creation interface. Users can drag and drop components to build dashboards that present real-time data insights. Additionally, Superset provides robust SQL IDE support, enabling data professionals to write, run, and visualise the results of SQL queries directly within the platform, as shown in Figure 28. This feature is particularly useful for conducting deep data analysis and troubleshooting.

Unique to Apache Superset is its extensibility and customization. It offers a wide array of customization options, from changing themes to adding custom visualization plugins, and allowing teams to tailor the tool to their specific needs. On the technical side, Superset is built to handle large datasets efficiently. It leverages caching mechanisms to speed up query performance and can integrate with most SQL database backends, including popular choices like PostgreSQL, MySQL, and SQLite, as well as more specialized data stores like Apache Druid and Google BigQuery.

Role within the Citizen Observatory in the GREENGAGE project

Apache Superset's role is pivotal in the 'Analysis and Visualization for Insights Generation' area of concern, since it serves as a data visualisation interface for the data collected by the GREENGAGE app and auxiliary datasets, which can be uploaded to the platform to enhance the understanding of an Observatory's challenge. Superset facilitates sophisticated data analysis and the creation of dynamic, interactive visualizations for the GREENGAGE Observatories. Through its user-friendly dashboards and exploration tools, Superset transforms intricate datasets into clear, actionable insights, essential for informed decision-making in environmental monitoring. Its capacity to generate detailed reports and tailor data presentations makes it an asset for community engagement, underpinning the project's goal of effective environmental management and policy development. Within the GREENGAGE project, Apache Superset demonstrated remarkable capabilities in dashboard creation, combining charts from varied data sources and incorporating user-conducted analyses. Its interactive controls allow stakeholders to present insights derived from heterogeneous data effectively. The dashboards are not just visually engaging but also highly informative, facilitating a deeper understanding of environmental trends and patterns among diverse project participants and Citizen Observers. To streamline this process and to enhance the user experience, the connection of Superset with various data sources was managed by GREENGAGE's Pilot Support Teams (PSTs). This approach alleviated the complexity for pilots and the Citizen Observers, ensuring that they could focus on data analysis and interpretation without being burdened by the intricacies of data integration. This thoughtful arrangement allowed stakeholders to engage with the data more efficiently and effectively, enhancing the overall impact of their contributions to the GREENGAGE project.

Interoperability with other tools

Apache Superset's interoperability within the GREENGAGE Citizen Observatory was critical as Superset also had to ingest data from other tools available in the GREEN Engine. Apache Superset is capable of ingesting datasets from over 40 different datasources, including the most common relational databases as well as some specialised ones.

4.3.3 Apache Druid

Apache Druid⁴ is an open-source data store designed for high-performance real-time analytics. It excels in ingesting and querying large volumes of data with low latency, making it ideal for interactive applications. Druid is commonly used for business intelligence, operational analytics, and handling timeseries data. Its architecture allows for scalable, fast, and efficient data handling and is particularly effective in environments where real-time insights and quick query responses are crucial. Druid is well-suited for use cases that require rapid aggregation and flexible data exploration across large, dynamic datasets. The following Figure 29 Figure 36 shows the data source view in which users can check the columns and datatypes a data source hold.

⁴ <https://druid.apache.org/> Tested, 14.08.2025

Time	Site_ID	NOx	NO2	NO	PM10	O3	Temperature	ObjectID	ObjectID2	NPM10	VPM10
1993-01-04T00:00:00.000Z	188	27	27	0	31	48	empty	empty	815,518	empty	empty
1993-01-04T01:00:00.000Z	188	38	36	1	30	42	empty	empty	1,438,309	empty	empty
1993-01-04T02:00:00.000Z	188	32	31	1	20	44	empty	empty	1,159,358	empty	empty
1993-01-04T03:00:00.000Z	188	32	31	1	31	42	empty	empty	1,188,550	empty	empty
1993-01-04T04:00:00.000Z	188	17	17	0	26	48	empty	empty	1,188,548	empty	empty
1993-01-04T05:00:00.000Z	188	27	25	1	29	42	empty	empty	826,086	empty	empty
1993-01-04T06:00:00.000Z	188	36	31	4	33	32	empty	empty	815,514	empty	empty
1993-01-04T07:00:00.000Z	188	124	63	40	31	14	empty	empty	86,779	empty	empty
1993-01-04T08:00:00.000Z	188	325	73	165	39	10	empty	empty	439,636	empty	empty
1993-01-04T09:00:00.000Z	188	686	111	376	79	12	empty	empty	1,188,546	empty	empty
1993-01-04T10:00:00.000Z	188	947	164	513	111	14	empty	empty	815,510	empty	empty
1993-01-04T11:00:00.000Z	188	659	149	334	88	12	empty	empty	1,188,544	empty	empty
1993-01-04T12:00:00.000Z	188	229	82	96	52	18	empty	empty	815,506	empty	empty
1993-01-04T13:00:00.000Z	188	227	76	99	30	22	empty	empty	86,778	empty	empty
1993-01-04T14:00:00.000Z	188	222	65	103	35	18	empty	empty	439,635	empty	empty

Figure 29: Apache Druid interface.

Apache Druid offers a broad set of features that fulfil several requirements of the GREENGAGE project regarding data management:

- Real-Time Data Ingestion and Querying:** Druid's prowess in handling large volumes of data in real-time is a vital asset for the GREENGAGE project. In an era where immediate insights from environmental data are critical, Druid's ability to ingest and query data in real-time ensures that stakeholders can access up-to-the-minute information. This feature enables timely responses to changing environmental conditions, which is essential for informed decision-making.
- Scalability:** In the long term, the GREENGAGE project will generate and processes vast amounts of data, and Druid's scalable architecture is well-suited to meet these demands. As the project evolves and data volumes grow, Druid can seamlessly expand its capacity to ensure consistent performance. This scalability is crucial for accommodating the evolving data needs of the project and preventing bottlenecks in data processing.
- Time-Series Data Analysis:** Environmental monitoring inherently involves tracking and understanding trends over time. Druid's strength in time-series data analysis aligns perfectly with the project's objectives. It empowers users to delve deep into historical data, identify patterns, and gain insights into how environmental factors evolve over various timeframes. This capability is essential for making data-driven decisions and understanding the long-term impacts of environmental changes.
- Flexible Data Aggregation:** The GREENGAGE project often requires rapid data aggregation for quick analysis and reporting. Druid's ability to perform rapid data aggregation supports this need. Whether summarising data from various sources or generating real-time aggregations, Druid offers the flexibility required to extract meaningful insights efficiently. This feature streamlines the data analysis process, allowing stakeholders to focus on interpreting the results and deriving actionable insights.
- Interactive Dashboards:** Visualizing complex environmental data in an accessible format is crucial for effective communication and decision-making. It empowers users to create dynamic and interactive visualisations that facilitate data exploration. Although this is not Druid's primary role in the project, it enables users to do a quick analysis or preview whether data has loaded correctly as the following Figure 30 shows.

Figure 30: Apache Druid analytics view.

Role within the Citizen Observatory

Within the GREENGAGE project, Apache Druid assumes a pivotal role in the 'Analysis and Visualization for Insights Generation' area of concern, whose capabilities are instrumental in harnessing the full potential of the project's large-scale datasets. Druid's primary contribution revolves around its prowess in efficiently managing extensive volumes of data and facilitating rapid data access, which are indispensable requirements for this critical area. Apache Druid empowers users to interact with the tool, offering a comprehensive set of data processing capabilities that streamline the analysis of time-series data—an essential component for gaining insights into evolving environmental trends. Its ability to handle time-series data efficiently allows stakeholders to track and understand changes over various temporal scales, from short-term fluctuations to long-term patterns. This capacity for in-depth time-series analysis is invaluable for the GREENGAGE project, where the ability to decipher environmental trends is central to achieving its objectives.

Interoperability with other tools

Apache Druid seamlessly integrates with other tools within the GREENGAGE Citizen Observatory to facilitate data sharing and integration. For instance, data collected from sensor tools like IoT of-the-shelf sensors, MODE library⁵, MindEarth for GREENGAGE or the GREENGAGE app have been efficiently imported into Druid for efficient storage. Data can flow smoothly from data collection tools to Druid, ensuring that insights from various sources can be easily combined and explored. The only requirement is that the data hosted in Druid must be in a columnar format or should be transformable to it. Apache Druid contributes significantly to a seamless user experience across different areas of concern of the GREENGAGE project. Insights gathered from initial data collection tools, such as sensor data and mobility patterns from MODE, can be further stored and visualized within Druid. However, given its role as the primary data repository, maintaining the integrity and accuracy of the tool is of utmost importance. To minimise the risk of errors and data discrepancies, access to Druid shall be limited to individuals who possess the requisite skills and knowledge in data processing and management. This selective approach ensures that the data hosted within Druid remains reliable and consistent throughout Citizen Observatories lifecycle, aligning with GREENGAGE's commitment to high data quality standards.

4.3.4 Kepler.gl

Kepler.gl emerges as a powerful open-source tool perfectly suited for visualizing spatial data, making it a very good asset within the GREENGAGE project's technological ecosystem. Tailored for geospatial analysis, Kepler.gl facilitates the intuitive exploration and interpretation of location-based data, aligning seamlessly with the project's emphasis on spatial insights (Figure 30).

⁵ as part of the GREENGAGE App

Figure 31: Kepler.gl visualization used by GISAT at the datathon to present air quality in Lazio region.

Figure 32: Kepler.gl visualization used by MindEarth to present mobility dynamics in Lazio region.

Within the GREENGAGE framework, Kepler.gl could support visualising various forms of spatial data. Its versatility in managing geographic information, combined with its user-friendly interface, enables stakeholders to derive actionable insights from the collected data. By utilising Kepler.gl, the project

gained a dynamic tool for creating interactive, multi-layered maps that effectively communicate complex spatial relationships.

It is worth noting that one of the GREEN Engine tools, specifically UrbanTEP / VISAT, boasts a front-end framework constructed around the DeckGL framework. DeckGL serves as the foundation for rendering large-scale data visualisations, particularly within geospatial contexts. The interplay between DeckGL and Kepler.gl presents a noteworthy opportunity for seamless integration and enhanced visualization capabilities. By leveraging both tools in tandem, GREENGAGE stands to unlock powerful capabilities for visualizing and analysing spatial data with precision and clarity.

This strategic integration of VISAT built on and Kepler.gl's module (DeckGL) offers a unique opportunity to not only enhance the GREENGAGE project's spatial data visualisation capabilities but also to provide stakeholders with an intuitive and dynamic toolset for exploring and understanding complex geographic relationships. This interrelation strengthens GREEN Engine's capacity to extract valuable insights from spatial data, furthering its mission to drive evidence-based policy-making and sustainable urban solutions.

Role within the Citizen Observatory

Kepler.gl has played a key role in supporting pilot datathons and co-creation activities by enabling rapid, on-the-fly visualization of geospatial data without the need for complex pre-development. For example, in the Turano Valley, Kepler.gl was used to visualize Copernicus datasets—such as Air Quality and Land Cover data—and present them directly to citizens. Its primary strength lies in its user-friendly interface, allowing users of the GREEN Engine (during the project's lifetime, e.g., MindEarth and GISAT, in the future any citizens and municipalities using the GREEN Engine) to quickly visualize and interpret spatial data, making it an ideal tool for dynamic, participatory events and immediate data exploration.

Interoperability with other tools

Kepler.gl is an open-source tool, publicly deployed and accessible via the kepler.gl website, allowing any user to upload and visualise their geospatial datasets. While Kepler.gl does not offer direct technical interoperability or integration APIs, it is built on the DeckGL library—the same visualisation engine used by UrbanTEP/VISAT. This shared foundation enables a consistent visualisation experience across GREENGAGE tools, with Kepler.gl serving as a quick, standalone solution and UrbanTEP/VISAT providing more advanced, integrated visualisations supported by user stories and interactive exploration features.

4.3.5 DataHub

DataHub, in the context of the GREENGAGE project, is an advanced data management platform that plays a crucial role in integrating and organising diverse data streams. Its primary function is to aggregate data from various sources, providing a unified, accessible environment for data analysis. DataHub excels in metadata management, a critical feature that adds context and understanding to the data, crucial for informed decision-making. The platform also offers powerful data discovery and exploration tools housed within a user-friendly interface, making it accessible to users of varying technical expertise. DataHub is technically scalable, ensuring consistent performance as data volumes grow and adhering to strict data security and compliance standards. In GREENGAGE, DataHub's ability to provide a centralised data repository is vital for supporting advanced data analysis and enhancing the decision-making process in environmental monitoring and policy development.

Throughout various stages of data-centric projects, numerous challenges and queries arise. DataHub is designed to seamlessly guide participants through every phase of these projects, from the initial planning and data sourcing to the application of advanced data analytics and insights extraction. It offers comprehensive guidance for data management and utilisation and practical advice, templates, and tools tailored to enhance collaborative efforts.

Figure 33: Explore view of DataHub.

Role within the Citizen Observatory

DataHub plays a multifaceted role in the GREENGAGE project, acting as a central data aggregation, management, and analysis hub. Its functions include aggregating diverse data sources for accessibility, managing metadata to add context to raw data, and facilitating data discovery with a user-friendly interface. The scalability and robust security of DataHub's architecture ensure reliable performance and data integrity, which are crucial for handling growing environmental data volumes.

- **Aggregation and Accessibility:** At its core, DataHub is tasked with the job of aggregating data from over 50 sources, thus offering a unified and accessible environment for data analysis. This functionality provides an advantage as it allows datasets from disparate sources to be aggregated in one place, allowing stakeholders to identify them quickly and easily.
- **Metadata Management:** The brilliance of DataHub lies in its metadata management capabilities. By adding context and understanding to raw data, it elevates the information from mere numbers to actionable insights. This aspect is invaluable, especially when making informed decisions that could have far-reaching environmental implications. Furthermore, Datahub allows versioning of the assets and metadata, which is crucial for reproducing the proposed workflows.
- **Data Discovery and User Accessibility:** The platform is not just about handling data; it is about making data comprehensible and usable. With its powerful data discovery tools and user-friendly interface, DataHub caters to users with varied technical expertise, democratising data analysis.
- **Scalability and Security:** DataHub's scalable architecture ensures consistent performance despite increasing data volumes and adheres to the strictest data security and compliance standards. This scalability is crucial as environmental data continually evolves and expands.

In the GREENGAGE initiative, DataHub serves as the central data catalogue within the GREEN Engine, enabling teams to discover, understand, and govern data assets. In this setup, Apache Druid operates as the metric store, housing detailed time-series and aggregated data, while Apache Superset functions as the primary visualisation layer, creating dashboards and charts from Druid's datasets. DataHub ingests metadata from both systems—approximately 80% from Superset and 20% from Druid—cataloguing datasets, dashboards, and charts. This workflow allows DataHub to unify these assets into a searchable catalogue, though current metadata (ownership, tags, glossary terms) is still being enriched to fully support governance. Together, these tools streamline data exploration: Druid supplies analytics-ready data, Superset visualises it, and DataHub catalogues and enhances discoverability, ensuring teams can reliably find, interpret, and govern their data resources. However, although its primary role is played in the third area of concern, DataHub is present from creating the communities to explaining the data.

At the outset, in the Community and Co-production Process Management area of concern, DataHub is an instrumental that provides data overview being connected with Apache Druid for further data

operations. It aids in setting clear objectives for each campaign, identifying necessary datasets, and addressing potential data gaps. Additionally, it facilitates the selection of suitable tools and personnel, ensuring that the data collection process is both practical and efficient. As campaigns move into the Data collection area of concern, DataHub's strengths become even more apparent. It supports the development of sophisticated data workflows by aiding in tool selection and providing a centralized way of displaying them. Users can visualise how the data is ingested and stored as different versions of one dataset. Finally, the Analysis and Visualisation for Insights Generation area of concern is where DataHub contributes the most with its functionalities. It acts as a showcase of available data with enriched metadata and documentation for each asset. It also provides a centralised location to host charts and dashboards that may be used to present and extract data insights. Overall, DataHub democratizes data access, ensuring that all users have easy access to the information they need. Furthermore, this straightforward information access will allow users to inspire in previous campaigns and develop new ones. This will contribute to the sustainability of the project and the creation of a community of practice.

Interoperability with other tools

Regarding integration and interoperability with other tools proposed in the GREENGAGE project, DataHub enables seamless data sharing and integration. For instance, it can directly import data from IoT portable sensors, from the open data catalogues available in the cities where the Pilots are being conducted or from the databases of MindEarth for GREENGAGE and GREENGAGE app applications. This contributes to a holistic view of the Pilot and provides a centralised location for analysing the available information. Furthermore, DataHub maintains user experience continuity across project areas. Data from tools employed in the second area of concern can be integrated into DataHub, allowing for deeper insights, correlation and even the creation of charts and dashboards to present it. This seamless integration and continuity ensure that insights from one area are effectively utilised in subsequent ones, reinforcing the project's cohesive and comprehensive Citizen Observatory Community Journey. In summary, DataHub transcends its role as a mere data management tool. Enriching the GREENGAGE project with its functionalities, it functions as a pivotal hub for data discovery, management, and user empowerment. Its integration across the diverse areas of concern of the Citizen Observatory Community Journey positions DataHub as the central repository, facilitating data localisation and enhancing the accessibility and utility of data for all stakeholders involved.

4.3.6 KeyCloak

Keycloak has been adopted as the identity and access management (IAM) system in GREENGAGE to offer a unified and secure way for users to authenticate across all digital services in the project. Rather than relying on separate login systems for each tool, Keycloak enables a smooth and consistent sign-in experience, making it easier for users to navigate the GREENGAGE ecosystem while keeping security and access control tightly managed.

Socio-demographic data

Keycloak also has been extended to support the storage of users' socio-demographic data by incorporating custom user attributes into its identity management framework. This modification allows the platform to capture and persist information such as age range, gender, education level, and occupation directly within each user's profile, using <https://me.greengage-project.eu> as the frontend. These enhancements enable seamless integration with external applications requiring demographic segmentation or personalised user experiences, while maintaining compliance with privacy and security standards.

Please, select your pilot site or indicate your location, e.g. name of your place or ZIP code

Other

Other

Bilbao

Gender

Male

What is your level of education?

Master's degree

What is your level of knowledge in the usage of digital tools?

Advanced level (I make purchases electronically, I use spreadsheets, ...)

Could you indicate your work status?

Employed (private sector)

Please, select the type of organization you represent

Citizen

Do you consider yourself to belong to a minority or socially disadvantaged group based around, for example, ethnicity, gender, economic or social background, or other?

No

What is your age?

25-34 years – Early adulthood

I consent to taking part in the GREENGAGE research project based on the [consent form conditions](#)

Details **Attributes** Credentials Role Mappings Groups

Consents Sessions Identity Provider Links

Key	Value	Actions
userAttribute_ageRange	25-34	Delete
userAttribute_consent	2025-06-24T07:54:34.286Z	Delete
userAttribute_digitalToolsAcquaintance	Advanced level (I make pur	Delete
userAttribute_disadvantagedGroup	No	Delete
userAttribute_educationLevel	Master's degree	Delete
userAttribute_gender	Male	Delete
userAttribute_organizationType	Citizen	Delete
userAttribute_parentEmail	[REDACTED]	Delete
userAttribute_parentName	[REDACTED]	Delete
userAttribute_parentalConsent	-	Delete
userAttribute_schoolName	[REDACTED]	Delete
userAttribute_thematicRole	Core team member- organi	Delete
userAttribute_workStatus	Employed (private sector)	Delete
userAttribute_workStatus_other	false	Delete
userAttribute_zipCode	Bilbao	Delete
userAttribute_zipCode_other	Bilbao	Delete

Figure 34: Frontend view of the socio-demographic form (left image) and Keycloak's administrator view of socio-demographic data (right image)

Role within the Citizen Observatory

In the context of GREENGAGE's Citizen Observatories, Keycloak plays a central role in managing who gets access to what, based on their role and the project area they're involved in. By supporting widely used standards like OpenID Connect and OAuth 2.0.

Keycloak provides:

- Dynamic role assignment, enabling differentiated access for citizens, moderators, administrators, and developers within each observatory (e.g., to set-up access rights to Apache Superset for the Observers).
- User group management linked to specific Pilots or campaigns, allowing tailored access to missions, resources, and co-production processes.
- Auditability and traceability, logging all authenticated interactions to comply with the project's ethical and data protection frameworks.

Integration and Interoperability with Other Tools

Keycloak is fully integrated into the GREEN Engine infrastructure, acting as the unique identity provider for the following systems:

- **Collaborative Environment (CE):** User identities and team contributions are linked to JWT tokens issued by Keycloak, enabling verified and trackable attribution of tasks and resources.
- **Discourse:** Operates with Keycloak-based SSO through OpenID Connect, automatically synchronising user profiles and roles for community discussion and collaboration.
- **WordPress:** Utilises compatible SSO plugins, ensuring users authenticated via the portal can navigate CE, Discourse, and other services without additional login steps.
- **GREENGAGE app and MindEarth for GREENAGE app:** Backend services consume Keycloak issued tokens to authorise actions such as mission participation, data submission, and tracking.

- **Apache Superset:** Access is controlled via group and role-based permissions defined in Keycloak, ensuring users only access relevant datasets and dashboards.

Additionally, Keycloak is ready to support external login options, like university accounts or even social logins (e.g., Google, Apple), if these methods comply with GREENGAGE's privacy policies.

Ethical and Security Considerations

From the start, Keycloak was configured to comply fully with GDPR and the GREENGAGE Data Management Plan. Only minimal data (like email, user ID, and display name) is stored and always encrypted. On the security side, Keycloak allows administrators to define policies for token expiration, enable optional two-factor authentication, and control who has access to what through clear and strict permissions. Each service checks the token independently, ensuring tight control over access and reinforcing the principle of least privilege.

4.3.7 Zenodo

Zenodo has been adopted in the GREENGAGE project as the primary open-access repository for hosting and disseminating datasets generated through the Thematic Co-Explorations carried out within the Citizen Observatories. By leveraging Zenodo's trusted infrastructure, supported by CERN and OpenAIRE, GREENGAGE ensures that its scientific outputs are publicly available, citable, and aligned with FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) data principles. The GREENGAGE Zenodo community is available here: <https://zenodo.org/communities/greengage>.

Role within the Citizen Observatory

Within the context of GREENGAGE's Citizen Observatories, Zenodo plays a central role in the transparent publication and long-term preservation of data products resulting from citizen engagement, environmental sensing, and collaborative analysis. The dedicated GREENGAGE Zenodo Community serves as a centralized hub where datasets from different Pilots and thematic explorations in GREENGAGE can be accessed by researchers, policymakers, and the wider public.

Zenodo supports:

- **Dataset publication** with clear metadata and licensing, making it easier for others to discover, reuse, and cite the work.
- **Thematic organization**, grouping datasets by campaign, Pilot, or domain (e.g., air quality, biodiversity, noise pollution) for coherent access.
- **Version control and DOI assignment**, ensuring that each dataset is permanently identifiable and traceable to its source and version.
- Integration and Interoperability with Other Tools

Zenodo is integrated as part of the GREENGAGE data pipeline by manually importing data resulting from the GREEN Engine and visualization dashboards. Data generated via apps, sensor platforms, or collaborative missions can be cleaned, curated, and then published, by importing it manually as done in the project although it is also programmatically through its [API](#), to the Zenodo community. The metadata schema used in Zenodo aligns with the internal data cataloguing standards, ensuring consistency between what is stored locally and what is shared publicly.

So far, the GREENGAGE Zenodo community hosts a small but rich collection of datasets and publications. The most comprehensive dataset comes from a Thematic Co-Exploration conducted at the University of Deusto's Bilbao campus, including anonymized participant demographics, survey responses for four campus locations, geolocated photos, air quality measurements from Atmotube Pro sensors, and pre/post impact assessment questionnaires—all structured in open formats. The GREENGAGE Zenodo community features also all research papers and public deliverables that are published through GREENGAGE project. The published resources collectively illustrate GREENGAGE's commitment to open data and participatory research practices. Additional datasets and publications will continue to be published as observatory campaigns progress, reinforcing GREENGAGE's commitment to open science and transparent data sharing.

Table 11: GREENGAGE components summary

Area of Concern	Component	Description
Community and Co-Production Process Management	Collaborative Environment	Platform for planning, managing, and tracking co-production processes in Citizen Observatories
	Discourse	Discussion forum for collaborative communication Q&A, and community interaction
	Wordpress	CMS providing informational landing pages and integration points for GREENGAGE tools
Data Crowdsourcing and Curation	MindEarth for GREENGAGE app	Tool for crowdsourcing geospatial image collection and mission-based mapping
	GREENGAGE app	Citizen engagement app for mission-based data collection and interaction with policy makers
	MODE	Smartphone-based tracking of mobility patterns for transport-related research
	IoT Sensors	Low-cost sensors (e.g Atmotube PRO) for collecting air quality and noise data
Analysis and Visualization for Insights Generation	UrbanTEP/VISAT	Geospatial storytelling platform for sharing user stories and analysis
	DataHub	Metadata-rich repository and data management platform for GREENGAGE assets
	DigiTwin	3D visualization tool for urban planning insights and stakeholder dialogue
	Multi-modal data processing tool	AI tools for road defect detection, sentiment analysis, and thematic text summarization
Horizontal Services	Keycloak	Unified identity and access management system for all GREENGAGE tools
	Zenodo	Open-source repository for publishing datasets and documentation from thematic explorations

4.3.8 Wordpress⁶

WordPress is a versatile Content Management System (CMS). It initially gained popularity for blog creation but has since evolved into a key tool for developing a wide range of websites, including commercial ones. Its flexibility and user-friendly interface make it a go-to solution for website creation. Its primary objective is to simplify the process of website creation and management. Its user-friendly design, combined with powerful features, makes it an ideal choice for users ranging from novices to seasoned web developers. WordPress aims to enhance website functionality, improve user experience, and provide robust website management tools. Its main features include:

- Easy Installation, Update, and Customisation: Streamlines the setup and maintenance process.
- Automatic System Updates: Ensures the CMS stays current and secure.
- Multiple Authors and User Roles: Allows for collaborative work with various permission levels
- Support for Multiple Blogs: Facilitates the management of several blogs within a single site.
- Static Page Creation Capability: Enhances the flexibility of content management.

⁶ NB: Wordpress is not part of the GREEN Engine, since it needs a maintainer. It is described here for reference should future Observatories want to create a Wordpress site of their own.

- **Additional Features:** Includes categorization of articles and pages, password protection, WYSIWYG editor, email publishing, import options from various platforms, auto-save drafts, comment and communication tools, permalink support, content and comment distribution via RSS and Atom, link management, multimedia file management, plugin and widget support, integrated search functionality, and theme creation system.

Role within the GREENGAGE project

Within the GREENGAGE project, WordPress serves as the platform for the development and management of the GREENGAGE website (www.greengage-project.eu). Its versatility and extensibility via plugins, makes it the ideal choice to meet the project's objectives of accessibility, user engagement, and content dissemination.

The website is formed by the following main sections:

- **Become a GREENGAGE Observer:** In this section, visitors are invited to actively participate in the project by joining one of the GREENGAGE Observatories. It explains how citizens, local authorities, and organisations can contribute to data collection and environmental monitoring in their communities. The section encourages collaborative engagement and outlines the benefits of becoming an observer, such as contributing to local policymaking and accessing tools for environmental action.
- **GREENGAGE Academy:** This is the project's educational and training hub. It provides open access learning materials, toolkits, guidelines, and resources to support citizens, practitioners, and policymakers involved in the observatories. The Academy fosters capacity-building by promoting environmental literacy, digital skills, and participatory governance methods.
- **GREEN Engine Platform:** This section introduces the digital backbone of the GREENGAGE project— a comprehensive ecosystem that enables and supports the thematic co-production processes within the GREENGAGE Observatories. The GREEN Engine provides an integrated suite of digital tools, online services, and portable devices designed to empower citizen-led environmental exploration and action. It guides participants through the entire data lifecycle: from data collection and validation using mobile apps and IoT sensors, to analysis and visualisation through advanced platforms, ensuring that local knowledge can be transformed into actionable environmental insights. The platform's digital ecosystem is organised into three interconnected domains:
 - **Community and Co-production Process Management:** This includes tools like the Collaborative Environment (CE) for planning and managing Citizen Science campaigns, Discourse for forum-based community dialogue, and WordPress pages dedicated to each pilot site for public engagement and outreach.
 - **Data Crowdsourcing and Curation:** Tools such as the MindEarth for GREENGAGE app, GREENGAGE app, MODE mobility data tool, and IoT hyperlocal sensors (e.g. Atmotube PRO) enable real-time data collection on environmental conditions, urban mobility, and air quality—all driven by citizen participation.
 - **Analysis and Visualization for Insights Generation:** The GREEN Engine uses a robust data infrastructure including Apache NiFi for data integration, Apache Druid for storage, and Apache Superset for interactive dashboards. VISAT/UrbanTEP, the Data Quality Dashboard, and the DataHub16 further enhance the project's ability to explore, analyze, and share complex environmental data.
- **GREENGAGE Observatories:** Here, users can explore the GREENGAGE Observatories within the five GREENGAGE Pilots (Bristol, Copenhagen, Gerace, Turano Valley, and North Brabant). Observatory pages provide local context, objectives, activities, and ways in which citizens and stakeholders work together to address urban environmental challenges. Knowledge Base: A collection of deliverables, datasets and publications generated during the project, made available in time of their creation.
- **Events:** This section provides information about upcoming and past events related to the GREENGAGE project. It includes workshops, conferences, field activities, and meetings, showcasing how the project fosters collaboration and knowledge exchange among partners, communities, and experts.

- **Blog:** The blog shares news, stories, and updates from the GREENGAGE project. It includes highlights from meetings, citizen initiatives, technical updates, and success stories from the observatories. This section helps keep the public and stakeholders informed and engaged throughout the project's lifecycle.
- **'What is GREENGAGE?':** Here is a comprehensive overview of the GREENGAGE project, including its goals, methodology, timeline, and the consortium of partners behind it. It also includes acknowledgments of funding sources, contact information, and links to legal documents such as privacy and cookie policies.

Interoperability with other tools

The GREENGAGE project website benefits from a diverse suite of WordPress plugins that enhance its functionality, performance, interactivity, and compliance. These integrations support the user experience, data handling, communication, and legal adherence essential for a large-scale EU-funded initiative. Below is an overview of how the installed plugins contributing to the overall integration and capabilities of the site:

- **The Events Calendar and Events Shortcodes for The Events Calendar** allow the publication and display of upcoming events in flexible layouts, supporting visibility for workshops, campaigns, and co-production sessions.
- **Filter Everything PRO and Filter for Divi improve** content navigation by allowing visitors to filter posts, datasets, or observatory pages by specific criteria, supporting better user orientation and content discovery.
- **MapGeo** – Interactive Geo Maps facilitates the integration of interactive geographical maps to showcase project locations, observatories, and campaign coverage areas, making spatial data more accessible and visually engaging.
- **Complianz | GDPR/CCPA Cookie Consent** ensures that the website complies with European and international data protection laws by managing cookie consent banners, cookie policy generation, and conditional script loading based on user consent.
- OMGF self-hosts Google Fonts to improve GDPR/DSGVO compliance by reducing external data requests and increasing privacy.
- **Connect Matomo** integrates the privacy-friendly Matomo analytics platform directly into the WordPress dashboard, allowing the team to monitor visitor behavior without compromising data protection principles.
- **W3 Total Cache** significantly enhances site speed and performance through caching mechanisms, content delivery network (CDN) integration, and minification of assets, all of which contribute to a smoother user experience.
- **UpdraftPlus** provides automated and secure backup solutions, safeguarding the website's data and configurations against unexpected failures or cyber threats.
- **Query Monitor** offers developer-level diagnostics and debugging tools, helping the web team to monitor performance, identify bottlenecks, and optimise plugin interactions.

These plugins collectively ensure that the GREENGAGE website not only serves as a functional and informative platform but also acts as an interactive, legally compliant, and high-performance digital hub for Citizen Science collaboration across Europe. In addition, GREENGAGE website and Mailchimp have been integrated to allow visitors to easily subscribe to the GREENGAGE newsletter. As shown in Figure 10, a pop-up form is shown to all new visitors.

GREENGAGE

Sign Up For Our Periodical Newsletter!

First name

Last name

Your email address

I agree [GREENGAGE TOS](#) and [Privacy Policy.](#)

Continue

Figure 35: Mailchimp newsletter subscribing form

4.3.9 Discourse

Discourse is an open-source discussion platform tailored for building a community forum, ideal for projects like Citizen Observatories. Its comprehensive feature set focuses on enhancing user engagement and streamlining conversations. The platform is designed to transform the way forum discussions are conducted. Discourse offers a continuous, just-in-time loading conversation stream, ensuring the dialogue flows smoothly without any interruptions. This dynamic approach to conversations makes it easier for users to follow and participate in discussions. Additionally, Discourse integrates realtime chat channels, fostering informal, immediate interactions within the community. These chat messages can seamlessly transition into more structured forum topics, maintaining both continuity and discoverability of discussions.

Discourse stands out through its integration of Artificial Intelligence, which significantly improves community interaction and moderation. This makes the platform not only more user-friendly but also more efficient in managing community dynamics. Among its unique features, Discourse offers extensive personalisation options. Users can adjust their experience through a custom sidebar and user preferences, while admins can set defaults and site settings for a configurable community environment. The platform also maintains a simple, linear conversation flow, with contextual expansion in posts and quotes to reveal full conversations without disrupting the user's navigation. Moreover, sharing links on Discourse is interactive and informative, as pasted links automatically expand to show additional content and context from various popular websites.

From a technical standpoint, Discourse boasts several impressive specifications. It supports Single SignOn (SSO) integration with Keycloak using OpenID Connect, ensuring user convenience and security. Additionally, the platform includes community moderation tools for managing spam and resolving conflicts, fostering a healthy forum environment. It also features built-in protections like Akismet spam filtering and new user restrictions to block spam effectively. Email integration allows members to stay connected by receiving notifications and replying directly via email, ensuring they remain engaged even when offline. The extensive plugin ecosystem and comprehensive API provide additional functionalities and customisability. As a 100% open-source platform, Discourse encourages community-driven development and inspires confidence. Lastly, its one-click upgrade feature simplifies maintenance, making updates hassle-free.

Role within the Citizen Observatory

Within the framework of a Citizen Observatory, Discourse can serve as a very valuable engagement and communication platform. The platform can foster an environment where community members can actively participate in sharing observations, discussing findings, and collaborating on Citizen Science projects. It can also serve as “safe space” for communication amongst the Observers. This environment is conducive to an exchange of ideas and experiences, enhancing the collective understanding and coproduction processes essential in Citizen Science initiatives.

The utility of Discourse extends to various facets of community and co-production process management. It stands as a hub for generating discussions, enabling participants to debate ideas, share experiences,

and engage in collaborative efforts. In the realm of data crowdsourcing and curation, Discourse provides a venue where users cannot only share the information on the data they have collected but also discuss their implications, contributing to a collective effort of refining and curating this information. This is also a shared functionality with the Collaborative Environment. Furthermore, while Discourse may not be primarily a data analysis tool, it can play a significant role in facilitating discussions around data interpretation and visualisation. Insights gleaned from these discussions can then be visualised or analysed further using other tools. Beyond its data-centric capabilities, the platform is particularly adept at fostering community engagement, facilitating Q&A sessions, and encouraging collaborative problem-solving, all of which are vital for the successful operation of a Citizen Observatory.

To improve the usability of the Discourse platform and strengthen participant engagement within the Citizen Observatories, several targeted plugins have been deployed, during the second iteration of the solution. These tools have been selected and configured to address specific functional needs and to support more effective interaction among users within the GREENGAGE project framework.

The **Automation plugin** permits administrators to execute scripted actions based on defined triggers. In conjunction with the **Custom Wizard plugin**, it has been used to create a landing wizard (see Figure 36) that guides new users through a process of initial customisation. This includes the identification of the Citizen Observatory with which the user is associated and the username they want to display at Discourse.

Figure 36: Landing wizard for new users.

The **Category Experts plugin** fosters a community-based endorsement system, wherein users can recognise each other as experts within thematic categories. This functionality supports the visibility and authority of knowledgeable participants within the Citizen Observatories, thereby promoting peer-to-peer learning and recognition.

To encourage active participation, the **Gamification plugin** enables the configuration of community contests that reward user engagement. Administrators can design scoring systems and display leaderboards to highlight individual contributions and foster a sense of progression and achievement.

The **Solved plugin** introduces a mechanism for designating accepted answers within discussion threads in specified categories. This feature enhances the clarity and navigability of the discourse by making validated solutions more accessible to other users.

The **Translator plugin**, integrated using the open-source tool LibreTranslate, facilitates multilingual interaction on the platform (see **Error! Reference source not found.** Figure 37) Figure 38). By enabling users to translate posts directly within Discourse, this tool supports communication among participants from different linguistic backgrounds, ensuring that language differences do not constitute a barrier to collaboration or information exchange within the GREENGAGE consortium.

How to Participate

- Join discussions in the relevant subcategories based on your interests.
- Share your thoughts, experiences, and ideas from the pilot event.
- Stay connected with other participants, experts, and local stakeholders.
- Contribute to shaping future initiatives based on the pilot's findings.

Get Started

👉 **Introduce yourself** in the comments below! Tell us which group you were part of and what excites you most about the GREENGAGE project.

👉 **Visit the subcategories** Attractiveness & Livability group and Mobility group to dive into focused discussions.

Let's keep the momentum going and work together toward a greener, smarter Turano Valley! 🌱

Figure 37: Discourse topic in which the automatic translation button can be seen

The screenshot shows a Discourse forum post. At the top, there is a user profile picture and the title "Get Started". The main text of the post is in English, matching the content in Figure 37. Below the main text, there is a section titled "Chi siamo Turano Valley Pilot (Marzo-2025) categoria" with a sub-header "Tradotto dalla lingua en da LibreTranslate". The main text of this section is in Italian. To the right of the post, there are engagement metrics: "20 mar", "1 / 7", "20 mar", and "13g". There are also icons for reply and notification.

Figure 38: Result of the automatic translation of a Discourse topic

Interoperability with other tools

Discourse's advanced interoperability features, particularly its robust API, facilitate seamless data sharing and integration with various tools. The API enables Discourse to effectively receive and incorporate data from diverse sources such as WordPress posts and various data analysis platforms, allowing this information to be displayed and discussed within forum threads. This integration capability is detailed in the Discourse API Documentation. Additionally, the platform supports embedding and linking functionalities, which allows users to effortlessly embed or link visualisations and data from other platforms directly into their posts. This level of integration ensures that Discourse acts not just as a standalone forum but as a comprehensive hub for data interaction and collaborative discussion.

The seamless transition between phases in a project is a key aspect of the user experience in Discourse. Insights and discussions on the platform can significantly inform and shape activities in other stages of the project. For instance, a lively discussion about a specific data trend on Discourse can lead to a more focused approach in data collection or analysis in subsequent areas. Moreover, the platform facilitates cross-tool engagement. Users can reference discussions, polls, or insights gathered on Discourse in other tools, ensuring a consistent and uninterrupted thread of engagement and knowledge sharing throughout the entire lifecycle of the project. This feature of Discourse greatly enhances the coherence

and continuity of the user experience, making it an asset in any collaborative endeavour. Notice that Discourse and Collaborative Environment share some features for sharing contents and fostering dialogue. They should be understood as complementary and could be used simultaneously or independently in different Thematic Co-explorations. Whilst Discourse is designed to foster community engagement and dialogue, the focus on the Collaborative Environment is more on the management and governance of co-production processes. Whilst Discourse is more accessible and could be adopted by every observer in a Thematic Co-exploration, the Collaborative Environment is a more complex and sophisticated tool, which is more targeted to more active well-trained volunteers, which are responsible for completing the different stages of a Thematic Co-exploration.

AWAITING VALIDATION BY THE EUROPEAN COMMISSION

5 Technical Manuals of GREENGAGE tools

The manuals provided here aim to offer comprehensive technical documentation on how to effectively utilize the suite of GREENGAGE tools. These resources are tailored to guide users in understanding the interplay between GREENGAGE-specific tools, pilot-specific tools, and the open-source tools adopted by GREENGAGE. By harmonizing these tools, pilot cities and future Citizen Observatories can make significant strides toward achieving their specific objectives.

The manuals provided here are the final version of the comprehensive documentation on how to use the GREEN Engine.

Objective of the Manuals

The manuals serve as essential guides for project stakeholders to seamlessly use, integrate and leverage a diverse set of tools within the GREENGAGE ecosystem. They provide clear instructions, best practices, and practical insights on how to harness the combined power of these tools to address the unique challenges and goals of each pilot city and assistance on smooth establishment of CO campaigns (Figure 39).

Figure 39: Data workflow diagram

Key Focus Areas

Integration and Workflow: Aim is to help understand how to harmonize the GREENGAGE-specific tools with pilot-specific and open-source tools to create cohesive workflows. This section emphasizes the interoperability and synergies between the different tools.

Figure 40: GREEN Engine workflow final evolution phase within the project progress (for an in-depth data flow chart please see D1.12, Figure 5)

Data Flows and Transformation: Learn how to efficiently manage data flows, from ingestion to transformation and export. Manuals cover step-by-step processes involved in utilizing the tools for effective data processing.

Security and Compliance: Guidelines for ensuring data security, privacy, and compliance with relevant regulations. Understand the measures required to protect sensitive information.

Optimization and Best Practices: Discover strategies for optimizing tool usage and adopting best practices to achieve maximum efficiency and effectiveness in addressing pilot city objectives.

Troubleshooting and Support: Access resources for identifying and resolving common issues that may arise during tool integration and utilization. Learn how to effectively seek support when needed.

Figure 41: Citizen Observatory Loop in GREENGAGE

Collaborative Approach

The manuals promote a collaborative approach by providing insights into how GREENGAGE tools can complement each other, ensuring a holistic solution for pilot cities. By following the guidance provided, cities can harness the full potential of the toolset to drive positive change in urban mobility and sustainability.

Empowering Pilot Cities

The manuals are designed to empower Citizen Observatories with the knowledge and skills needed to utilize the GREENGAGE toolset effectively. They enable cities and citizens to take ownership of their mobility and sustainability initiatives and leverage the combined strength of tailored tools for their specific contexts.

5.1 GREENGAGE tools

5.1.1 MindEarth for GREENGAGE app (MindEarth)

Name	MindEarth for GREENGAGE app Data access system: DataView
URL	https://play.google.com/store/apps/details?id=ch.mindearth.mindviewgreengage&hl=de_AT (Google Play Store)
Description / abstract	MindEarth for GREENGAGE app, enables users to capture and upload geo-tagged street-level imagery using their smartphones or compatible devices. Users are incentivized based on the complexity and duration of tasks, such as following predefined routes, capturing specific objects, or standing at designated locations. These tasks can be commissioned by third parties for research, urban planning, or commercial purposes. The app facilitates data collection in populated areas, gathering images that may include personal information. However, to adhere to GDPR regulations, collected images undergo anonymization, including face and license plate blurring. The captured data is subsequently used for extracting various analytics, including built environment assessment, foot traffic analysis, public space usage evaluation, and

	more, providing valuable insights for urban and spatial planning, disaster risk management, and territorial management.
Snapshots	
Authorship	MindEarth
Audience	<p>Check Audience field in https://eu-citizen.science/resources</p> <p>MindEarth for GREENGAGE: Researchers & Academics, Community Members & Citizens</p> <p>DataView: Researchers & Academics.</p>
Date creation	March 2022
Date modified	Last update: August 2025.
Latest updates	<p>MindEarth for GREENGAGE app:</p> <p>Integration with GREENGAGE app for displaying missions;</p> <p>Improved images upload system;</p> <p>DataView:</p> <p>added integration for bulk mission upload.</p>
Keywords	Mobile mapping, crowd mapping, data generation, Artificial Intelligence
Category	Dataset, Image, Service, Still Image.
License	<p>The MindEarth for GREENGAGE app and the DataView platform are commercial products with closed source implementation. Images collected and anonymized are not shared with partners nor to third parties.</p> <p>No restriction on reuse of aggregated and processed KPI and metrics made available through the designated GREEN ENGINE platform (applicable licence: CC BY-SA 4.0).</p>
Publisher	N/A
Date published	N/A
Theme	Research design and methods, Empowerment, Evaluation of citizen science.

Languages	English.
DOI	N/A
Nature	MindEarth for GREENGAGE: Internal Software DataView: Internal Software
Problem profile	<p>MindEarth for GREENGAGE contributes to solving a citizen science problem related to geospatial data collection and mapping. It enables individuals to actively participate in the process of creating and improving maps by capturing and sharing geotagged images. These images can be of streets, landscapes, landmarks, or any other geographical features.</p> <p>This approach addresses the challenge of maintaining up-to-date and comprehensive maps, which can be a resource-intensive task for official mapping agencies. By harnessing the collective efforts of the community, the app helps fill in the gaps in mapping data, particularly in less documented or rapidly changing areas. This is especially valuable for regions where official mapping sources may be limited or outdated.</p> <p>Furthermore, this type of citizen science initiative promotes local knowledge and engagement. People who are familiar with their surroundings can provide context and details that might be missed by automated mapping processes or remote mapping efforts. As a result, the app not only enhances the accuracy and completeness of maps but also empowers individuals to actively contribute to their communities' spatial knowledge and infrastructure.</p>
Usage Examples	<p>MindEarth for GREENGAGE can come handy in all those situations where a real-time, on-demand photographic survey of the urban space is required. The system manages all the implementation details from the submission of the Area of Interest (AOI) to be surveyed to the output of the aggregated data in static files (csv or geo-referenced files) or interactive REST APIs.</p> <p>One example is the possibility to get insights on the pedestrian presence in a specific urban area. Citizen Observers might be interested in assessing foot traffic patterns in a busy city centre to optimize urban planning and enhance public space utilization.</p> <p>The implementation would start by defining the boundaries of the AOI to be surveyed, the constraints of the time of the day and day of week during which data need to be collected and the number of passover to be realized (to provide consistency on the data collection process). These inputs shall be transmitted to MindEarth in the format of GIS files containing one geometry per mission (i.e., a path to be followed by the mappers) and the specific time-constraints.</p> <p>Then, MindEarth for GREENGAGE will take care of the user onboarding for mission execution, data collection and data upload. The output could then be retrieved using a Python client querying the APIS.</p> <p>To begin using the MindEarth for GREENGAGE app, follow these steps:</p> <p>Step 1: Download and install the app</p> <p>Visit the Google Play Store and search for "MindEarth for GREENGAGE". Follow on-screen instructions to install the app on your Android device.</p> <p>Step 2: User Registration</p> <p>Launch the app. Create a new account by providing the required details or log in with existing credentials.</p>

Complete the registration process.

Step 3: Browse Missions

Once registered, users can access available missions in their surroundings.

Missions can be explored through the list or map view to browse available missions.

Select a mission based on your location and preferences.

Step 4: Executing Missions to fulfil missions and contribute valuable data:

Mission Details

Review the details of the selected mission, including objectives and special requirements.

Follow Mission Directions

Follow the provided directions while executing the mission. This may include predefined routes, specific objects to capture, or designated locations to visit.

Capture and Upload Images

Use your smartphone's built-in camera to capture geo-tagged street-level imagery.

After completing the mission, review the captured images and upload them to the backend.

Step 5: Retrieving Mission's Data Outputs

After the data collection process, MindEarth handles the image processing by anonymizing the raw images and leveraging techniques for object detection (e.g., pedestrian volume, vehicles, landmarks, etc).

The output, which can be a JSON file, can then be retrieved using a Python client querying the API. Then, the user can visualize and analyse the data as needed.

	<pre> # Sample Python code to retrieve foot traffic data using API import requests # Set the API endpoint for foot traffic data api_endpoint = "https://mindearth-api.example.com/foot-traffic" # Define parameters, e.g., location, time frame params = { "location": "POLYGON(...)", "time_frame": "weekly", } # Make a GET request to retrieve foot traffic data response = requests.get(api_endpoint, params=params) # Process the response (e.g., visualize data or perform analytics) foot_traffic_data = response.json() </pre> <p>By following these steps, users can actively contribute to data collection efforts within the GREENGAGE project, ultimately supporting urban planning and policy-making initiatives.</p>
Documentation	<p>MindEarth for GREENGAGE</p> <p>The app will be freely available on the Google Play Store and to internal partners as a standalone APK file. On the first app boot, users are required to register a new account or to login with their existing credentials. Then, available missions in the users' surroundings can be queried via the list or map view and the app will guide the users with tutorials and introducing potential special requirements for each mission.</p> <p>The missions can be loaded to the platform by transmitting their shapes and time constraints in a GIS file + specification file. MindEarth will take care to upload the missions in the backend and make them available to users.</p> <p>DataView</p> <p>All the postprocessing of the missions' images is done in the background (MindEarth cloud backend) and it is transparent to the end-user. The aggregated data as well as a copy of the KPI and metrics are then transferred to UWE OneDrive and made available to all project partners in tabular format and to the general public through the GREEN ENGINE via web APIs exposing the database content with an agreed schema. No installation is required to use and browse the APIs as a public swagger for interactive development will be made available.</p>
Support	<p>All questions and requests should be forwarded to mindearth@mindearth.ai or mailto:mindearth@mindearth.ai</p>
Complementarity / Interoperability	<p>MindEarth for GREENGAGE seamlessly integrates into a Citizen Observatory's co-production process by enabling citizens to collect on-the-ground data. It serves as an input resource by allowing users to capture geo-tagged imagery and reports. This data can then be processed, analysed, and visualized, contributing valuable insights to inform decision-making. Complementary tools, such as mapping platforms, machine learning tools, and community engagement platforms, can enhance its functionality and further empower citizen participation in the GREENGAGE vision.</p>
Open Standards & Protocols	<p>The app follows standard protocols for ensuring basic interoperability and security. User registration is handled securely, and user data is protected through standard encryption methods.</p>
APIs & Interfaces	<p>DataView is still under development and no final link to the resources, nor a final outline of the data endpoints is available.</p>
Modularity & Extensibility	<p>The MindEarth app allows for extension of the app functionalities as it is based on a Flutter codebase with custom views and routers enabling the customization of each step from the mission reservation to picture upload. Specifically, each mission can be decorated with a custom procedure for the mapper to follow. For</p>

	<p>instance, the mapper can be instructed to turn on and pair a specific sensor with the mobile phone or to take pictures of particular scenes (like an illegal dump or empty store locations). This ensures a modular mission design to ensure users can extend or customise its functionality to meet specific requirements.</p> <p>On the same line, the list of indicators that can be extracted from the street-level imagery can be selected among the MindEarth models or new models provided by end-users can be inserted into the processing pipeline to extract novel indicators.</p> <p>Finally, DataView provides interactive APIs that allow external services to interact with MindEarth app-based data seamlessly. Users can integrate additional data sources or services along the the APIs' workflow, enhancing their capabilities. Besides, DataView offers flexible data export options, allowing users to extract collected data in various formats, including JSON, CSV, or custom formats. This flexibility supports the integration of the app with external data processing tools and systems.</p> <p>In summary, MindEarth for GREENGAGE's modular design and support for customization ensure users can easily extend its functionality. Whether by integrating new data sources, external services, or developing custom missions, the app remains adaptable to meet specific requirements within the GREENGAGE initiative, promoting innovation and collaboration.</p>
<p>Metadata & Data Discovery</p>	<p>Data discovery will be guaranteed by implementing a swagger interface and an openAPI JSON specification to the web API clearly explaining all the available endpoints.</p> <p>Moreover, the aggregated data exported to the GREENGAGE portal will be tagged and will come with a detailed description of their content.</p>
<p>Data Collection & Integration</p>	<p>MindEarth for GREENGAGE facilitates data collection from citizen observations and other sources through its user-friendly interface and structured data output.</p> <p><u>Data Collection from Citizen Observations:</u></p> <p>User-Friendly: The mobile app is designed to be user-friendly, allowing even users with little or no technical expertise to capture street-level imagery and report observations easily.</p> <p>Geo-Tagged Data: The app collects geo-tagged street-level imagery, which includes location metadata. Image postprocessing automatically report person observations, hazards, or specific objects at precise geographic coordinates.</p> <p>Flexible Survey Plan: The app accepts GIS information to define the surveys to be executed. These allows also for flexible time constraints to allow answering different urban management questions.</p> <p><u>Supported Data Formats:</u></p> <p>Image Formats: The app primarily captures and stores images in JPEG. These image formats are universally supported and can be easily integrated into various data processing pipelines.</p> <p>Metadata: Besides images, the app attaches metadata to each observation. This metadata typically includes timestamp, geolocation (latitude and longitude).</p> <p>Geographical Database: the PostgreSQL database collecting the data is linked to a rest API serving aggregated or raw views on the processed data in a standard JSON format.</p> <p><u>Data Integration and Harmonization:</u></p> <p>Structured Data Output: The app's data output is structured, making it compatible with various data analysis and visualization tools. For example, JSON or CSV formats can be generated to facilitate data integration.</p>

	<p>Unified Data Format: The app ensures that all data follows a unified format with consistent metadata. This harmonization simplifies the process of aggregating and processing data from multiple sources.</p> <p>API Access: The DataView API provides programmatic access to the collected data, allowing for seamless integration with other tools and platforms used within GREENGAGE.</p> <p>Data Enrichment: MindEarth for GREENGAGE's data output standard format is suitable for enrichment with additional data sources (for more comprehensive analyses).</p>
Visualization & Analysis	The APIs or the static file output can be integrated in interactive visualizations by binding the parameters of the visualization itself to the request parameters to the API or the query parameters of the static data frame.
Security & Privacy	The APIs will be protected by a user management system managed by a KeyCloak instance. All connections to the API and backend are encrypted using SSL certificates. All the data will be stored in the private section of an AWS VPC. All the platforms will be GDPR compliant as no image (neither anonymized) will ever be served to external partners and no sensitive information will be shared in the aggregated data.
Deployment model: Scalability & Performance	The database scalability is guaranteed by hosting it on EC2 instances that can be scaled up in terms of storage and computing capacity as the volume of data/requests increases.
Social rating	Not applicable

5.1.2 Atmotube PRO (Atmotube, supported by Libelium)

Name	Atmotube PRO
URL	https://atmotube.com/atmotube-pro
Description / abstract	<p>Atmotube PRO is a portable air quality sensor that allows to connect with a mobile phone through a dedicated app. How to connect and use the device and the app is shown in this video.</p> <p>A user manual is also available at the Atmotube web page.</p>
Snapshots	
Authorship	ATMOTUBE
Audience	General consumers, researchers, environmental agencies, educational institutions, EU-funded projects on citizen science and air quality monitoring, companies monitoring indoor/outdoor air.

Date creation	October 2019 (market release of Atmotube PRO).
Date modified	November 2024 – latest firmware and app update.
Latest updates	Improved Bluetooth connectivity, updated particulate matter detection algorithms, and compatibility with the latest iOS/Android versions.
Keywords	Air quality, Portable sensor, PM2.5, PM10, VOC, IoT, Citizen Science, Environmental monitoring.
Category	Hardware / IoT sensor / Environmental monitoring device.
License	Proprietary – commercial hardware and software license.
Publisher	(who)
Date published	2019 (initial market release)
Theme	Environmental monitoring, Citizen science, Personal exposure tracking, Public health, Climate and sustainability projects
Languages	English (App and documentation available in multiple languages)
DOI	Not applicable
Nature	Commercial hardware and software solution
Problem profile	Air pollution is a major global health challenge, affecting urban and indoor environments. Traditional air monitoring stations are expensive, fixed, and sparse. Atmotube PRO addresses the lack of affordable, portable, and real-time monitoring tools, enabling both individuals and institutions to track exposure and gather high-resolution environmental data.
Usage Examples	(The biggest section that includes actual manuals! for example: “How to ..” and manual describes the steps)
Documentation	Official user manual: https://atmotube.com/pages/user-manual
Support	a.pujante@libelium.com – Software developer team a.illueca@libelium.com – Software developer team General inquiries: support@atmotube.com Technical support: dev@atmotube.com
Complementarity / Interoperability	(What tools could complement your solution to make reality GREENGAGE vision)
Open Standards & Protocols	Supports Bluetooth Low Energy (BLE) communication for interoperability Data export available in CSV/JSON for integration with other systems Can be linked with open data platforms (e.g., via API)
APIs & Interfaces	Atmotube PRO connects to mobile devices via Bluetooth Low Energy (BLE). Data can be accessed through the Atmotube mobile app (iOS/Android), which provides real-time visualization and local storage. Users can export datasets in CSV/JSON formats. API Access: The Atmotube app allows data export and integration with third-party platforms. A developer API is available for advanced use cases (upon request from the manufacturer).

	<p>Supported protocols: BLE for device-to-app communication; CSV/JSON for interoperability with external data systems.</p> <p>Integration: Data can be uploaded to cloud services or imported into analysis environments such as Python, R, or GIS tools.</p>
Modularity & Extensibility	<p>The Atmotube PRO is a self-contained device but follows a modular integration approach:</p> <p>Data can be combined with other IoT sensors (e.g., weather stations, GPS trackers). Exports in standard formats allow extension through external visualization and analytics platforms. Also, the mobile app can integrate additional features (air quality alerts, historical data review). Researchers can develop custom plugins/scripts to harmonize Atmotube data with larger environmental monitoring frameworks (e.g., EU citizen science portals).</p>
Metadata & Data Discovery	<p>Each record includes time, location, and pollutant type, ensuring interoperability and facilitating discovery in citizen science repositories. Metadata allows filtering and retrieval of relevant observations for research and policy applications.</p>
Data Collection & Integration	<p>The device measures particulate matter, VOCs, temperature, humidity, and pressure. Data is collected continuously, stored in the app, and exported in standard formats, making it easy to integrate with heterogeneous datasets such as weather or satellite observations.</p>
Visualization & Analysis	<p>The app provides real-time visualization, historical graphs, and alerts for high pollution levels. Exported datasets can be analysed externally and mapped with GIS or any different dashboards, supporting both personal awareness and professional research.</p>
Security & Privacy	<p>Data transfer is secured through encrypted Bluetooth channels and HTTPS for cloud communication. The system complies with GDPR by leaving full control of geolocation and personal data to the user. No personal identifiers are stored by default.</p>
Deployment model: Scalability & Performance	<p>Atmotube PRO is deployed as portable hardware paired with a mobile app. It is scalable for distributed monitoring networks, has a battery life of 10+ hours, and runs on common smartphones (iOS 12+/Android 6.0+ with Bluetooth 4.0 or higher).</p>
Social rating	<p>The device has strong positive feedback from individual users, NGOs, and citizen science projects, being valued for its portability, ease of use, and contribution to democratizing access to air quality data.</p>

5.1.3 Collaborative environment (CE) (DEUSTO)

Name	Collaborative Environment
URL	https://demo.greengage-project.eu
Description / abstract	<p>Purpose</p> <p>The Collaborative Environment project has been developed with the main objective of serving as a solid foundation for Citizen Observatories. It uses prominent technologies in its frontend to ensure effective collaboration and an intuitive user interface. The modular structure of the project, based on functional React components, facilitates its expansion and maintenance, thus allowing continuous adaptability to meet the emerging needs of Citizen Observatories.</p> <p>Functionality</p> <p>The system offers outstanding functionalities that facilitate the creation of a platform that is accessible and usable by a wide range of users. Among these functionalities is a strong focus on internationalization, using "react-i18next" to offer advanced</p>

translation capabilities, including functionalities such as plurals, formatting, interpolation, among others. In addition, the project facilitates the addition of new elements and routes through well-documented examples, thus promoting agile and efficient development.

Contribution to Citizen Observatories

Collaborative Environment uses Redux for efficient global state management and React's Context API to facilitate passing data through the component tree, avoiding the need to manually pass props at each level. This approach ensures that the system can handle significant complexities, facilitating the development of robust and flexible Citizen Observatories. Inclusion and diversity are promoted through its focus on internationalization, ensuring that a wide range of users can access and use the platform effectively.

Snapshots

Authorship

University of Deusto

Audience

All audiences

Date creation

04/05/2022

Date modified

16/07/2025

Latest updates

Check changelogs in:
<https://github.com/Greengage-project/backend-auth>
<https://github.com/Greengage-project/frontend>
<https://github.com/Greengage-project/backend-coproduction>
<https://github.com/Greengage-project/interlinker-googledrive>
<https://github.com/Greengage-project/backend-catalogue>

Keywords	Collaboration, resources, share, link
Category	Software service
License	Apache 2.0
Publisher	University of Deusto
Date published	04/05/2022
Theme	Project Management Co-creation Engagement Project sustainability
Languages	English, Spanish, Italian and Latvian. TBA: Dutch & Danish
DOI	N/A
Nature	Internal software: tool to support co-production
Problem profile	The Collaborative Environment comprises the following problem profiles: Team communication for co-production Document collaboration Stakeholders' engagement Loyalty, incentives and rewards Citizen Observatory process planning
Usage Examples	<p>Initial configuration, prior to deployment (for Developers)</p> <p>It is necessary to download the code from the repository (https://github.com/GREENGAGE-project/interlink-project) and follow the instructions described in https://greengage-project.github.io/interlink-project/environments/overview.html#development-and-demo.</p> <p>Account creation and login</p> <p>There are 2 ways to login to GREENGAGE as an authorized user, one is by using your email and registering or by using your google account. To access it you must go to Access Collaborative Environment > Login and select if you want to create your account in the system by clicking on Register or if you want to login using google services. After doing these steps you will be welcomed by the dashboard (Image 1).</p> <p>Image 1: screenshot of the dashboard</p> <p>Creation of an organization</p>

*You must be logged in

Once you are in the dashboard you must go to the **Organizations** tab > **Create new organization** and fill in the data (Image 2), once you have finished click on **Create**.

Image 2: Window for organization creation

Team creation

*You must be logged in and have previously created an organization.

In the **Organizations** tab, select your organization and click on the **Create new team** button where you can define teams of collaborators, what type of stakeholders they are and invite them to participate by entering a list of their emails by importing them with the **Import from CSV** button or by typing on the input where it appears "Type here to add users". To finalize the team creation, you must click on **Create** (Image 4).

Image 4: Team creation window

Creation of process

*You must be logged in.

You must be at the dashboard start, click on **Go to process list** then on **Create new process** and define the fields shown below

Image 5: Process creation

Process configuration

*It is required to be logged in and to have created a process.

On the left side we find the following sections:

- **Front Page:** In this page you will be able to visualize the description, objectives, challenges and proposed ideas.
- **Overview:** Screen to visualize everything you need to be able to carry out your co-production process.
- **Resources:** You will find all the resources generated in the process.
- **Guide:** (You need to have defined an outline before) This section allows you to visualize the overview screen.
- **Leaderboard:** (you must have activated the reward system) In this screen you will be able to see the scores of each collaborator according to their participation in the co-production process.
- **Workplan:** (It is necessary to have defined a scheme before) It allows an easy visualization of phases and tasks defined in the process, which you can see by means of a Gantt chart, along the defined milestones.
- **Team:** Section where you can add collaborators/administrators and visualize all the users that want to be part of the co-production process.

- **Settings:** Allows to define everything described in the Front Page, add co-production process administrator, delete all the resources related to the process, delete the process, clone the process, activate the reward system, show "tour" to all the users and allow new collaborators.

From the dashboard we click on Go to process list and select the process we defined, then we go to Overview located on the left sidebar, where we can configure the process while we see the roadmap (Image 6).

Image 6: Configuration overview

The roadmap consists of the following elements:

Settings: General edition of the project

Type: Defines the process characteristics, type of process based on the stakeholders.

Schema: Defines the schema to be used for the co-production process.

Organizations: Definition of the organization of the co-production process and the teams that compose it.

Resources: In this section you will be able to see the resources that have been created and assign them to a collaborator.

Permissions: Manage the permissions of the teams defined within the co-production process.

Rewards: Activate and define how contributions will be gamified.

Finish: Step to finalize all the necessary configuration before starting the co-production process.

Development of the co-production process

Once the configuration part of the co-production process is finished, we can start to perform the tasks defined within each objective. To do this we will go to "Guide" and select a task, as shown in the image below.

In the upper part of the process, you will see the name of the stages predefined by the loaded schema. While on the left side you will find the phases, objectives and tasks and you can add more with the + sign at the top.

Phase

When you click on the phase, you will see the name of the phase, the description, the status and the planning time (when it starts and when it ends). It also allows you to define the necessary permissions for a specific team.

Objective

A phase can be composed of several objectives, when we click on one of them, as well as the phases, we can visualize the name, description, current status and planning time. On the other hand, you can also define the permissions required for each team.

Task

It is the smallest and most fundamental unit of the production process, in this section you can visualize the name, description, task complexity (defined by the coordinating team), current status and planning time. In the next tab called Resources you can see the resources created to finish the task, you can also instantiate new resources such as "Template for use case scenarios". In the Contributions tab, we can add the actions performed by the users, in order to have a record and/or to be able to gamify these actions later.

Once the coproduction process has been completed, all we have to do is go to Settings and change the "State of the project" to "Finished".

Documentation

The full documentation of the Collaborative Environment is available in this link: <https://demo.greengage-project.eu/docs/en/>

The collaborative environment fosters Citizen Science (CS) and contributes to forming Citizen Observatories (COs) through several mechanisms:

Facilitating Co-production Processes: The environment serves as a platform where citizens (participants in a Citizen Observatory) can actively participate in co-production processes, which is a cornerstone of Citizen Science. It encourages citizens to be directly involved in collaborative processes or Citizen Science projects that matter to them, fostering a sense of ownership and engagement.

Resource Management and Sharing: By offering a centralized system for the management and sharing of resources created during the co-production process, it promotes transparency and accessibility. This feature is vital in Citizen Observatories where various resources like training materials, communication materials, data sets and research findings (e.g. visualization or policy briefs) can be shared and managed efficiently, promoting collaborative research and knowledge sharing.

	<p>Task Management and Tracking: The functionalities to manage phases, objectives and tasks and track the progress of various activities within a co-production process help in organizing and managing citizen-led initiatives. This ensures that tasks are completed efficiently, and objectives are met, which is crucial for the success of Citizen Science projects. Although, there can be a guideline or process schema to which many Citizen Observatory co-production processes may comply, each specific Citizen Observatory may adapt such process, removing tasks, adding new tasks or renaming them, among other things.</p> <p>Community Engagement and Collaboration: The environment promotes community engagement by allowing the creation of organizations and teams. It fosters collaboration among citizens, public administrations, non-profit organizations, and other stakeholders, facilitating a cooperative approach to problem-solving and project implementation, which is a fundamental aspect of Citizen Observatories.</p> <p>Integration with External Tools: The ability to integrate with external tools and assets, referred to as "INTERLINKERS" or CO enablers using GREENGAGE jargon, facilitates a seamless flow of information and functionalities between different platforms. This integration is essential in forming a cohesive Citizen Observatory where various tools and resources can be linked and combined effectively.</p> <p>Gamification Engine: The platform offers a gamification/incentivization engine that provides points to users depending on their contribution to different assets. The gamification engine and the points each task provides are activated by the administrator of the process. The platform also provides a leaderboard to compare your contribution with other participants.</p> <p>In summary, the collaborative environment serves as a comprehensive tool in fostering Citizen Science and forming Citizen Observatories, facilitating collaboration, resource management, and community engagement, and creating a seamless and efficient ecosystem for citizen-led initiatives and projects.</p>
<p>Support</p>	<p>The platform has two forms to provide support and give feedback. The links to the forms are at the top right part of the platform as you can see in the image:</p> <p>Open user manual</p> <p>Support form</p> <p>Feedback form</p>
<p>Complementarity / Interoperability</p>	<p>The Collaborative Environment is designed to foster active multistakeholder (public admin representatives, citizen observatory organizers and participants) participation in co-production processes. This platform does not only facilitate the creation and management of these processes but also allows citizens to be directly involved in collaborative processes/projects that resonate with them. Key features include a "Resources" view for centralized management and sharing of resources like data sets and research findings, task management functionalities to track progress, and the ability to create organizations and teams for enhanced community engagement and collaboration.</p>

	<p>Furthermore, the environment is equipped to integrate with external tools, termed "INTERLINKERS" or CO enablers, which can be connected to various tasks and resources. This ensures a smooth flow of information across different platforms. Another notable feature is the option to clone successful co-production processes, acting as a repository of best practices. This can be paired with other tools to replicate success in diverse contexts. The platform also emphasizes effective communication with its "NOTIFICATIONS" view and promotes active participation and accountability of individuals' contributions through reward systems.</p> <p>In essence, the CE is a comprehensive tool to guide, manage and support a Citizen Observatory co-production process. It champions collaboration, efficient resource management, and robust community engagement. When combined with other third-party resources and tools, e.g. tools from GREENGAGE toolset, paves the way for a seamless ecosystem tailored for citizen-led initiatives and projects.</p>
<p>Open Standards & Protocols</p>	<p><u>Authentication endpoints</u></p> <p>/auth/login: Redirects to the OIDC (OpenID Connect) provider where users can log in. It accepts a redirect_on_callback parameter.</p> <p>/auth/logout: Logs the user out. Accepts a redirect_on_callback parameter.</p> <p><u>Implementation</u></p> <p>Uses OIDC for authentication, which is an open standard.</p> <p>The code shows how redirects are handled and how authentication cookies are set and removed.</p> <p><u>Open Standards and Protocols</u></p> <p>OIDC (OpenID Connect): is an open standard for authentication.</p> <p>SameSite Cookies: Uses the SameSite directive to enhance security.</p> <p><u>Micorservices architecture with RESTful interfaces</u></p> <p>Collaborative Environment's back end is composed by a set of orchestrated microservices. Each microservice offers a documented RESTful API following Open API 3.0 standard.</p>
<p>APIs & Interfaces</p>	<p>The platform has two different APIs to deal with two databases in it: coproduction and catalogue.</p> <p>The coproduction API details the methods that perform actions on the following objects:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Coproduction processes Metadata Description Phases, objectives and tasks Users Teams Permissions Notifications Assignments

The [catalogue](#) API details the methods that perform actions on the following objects:

- Process schemas
- External modules and addons
- Problem profiles
- Interlinkers
- Ratings of interlinkers

Modularity & Extensibility	<p>The collaborative environment is built as a microservice architecture which supports the connection of new modules called INTERLINKERS. The connection of new modules is supported by the creation of middleware that allow to use and leverage the API of the proposed modules. Furthermore, in the Collaborative Environment some of the installed modules are specifically developed by the University of Deusto to meet some of the requirements of previous projects in which it has been employed. It is envisaged that some additional CO enablers will be added to the Catalogue of INTERLINKERS or CO enablers that the tool already features.</p>
Metadata & Data Discovery	<p>The "Internal interlinkers" component supports the creation and management of metadata for citizen observations, as well as mechanisms for data discovery.</p> <p>Interlinkers Overview</p> <p>Software Interlinkers: These are software-based interlinkers that create assets. For example, a "forum" interlinker can be instantiated to create a forum where users can create channels and send messages.</p> <p>Knowledge Interlinkers: These refer to assets made by users that can be used as templates. For example, a user can create a Google Drive word document representing a Business Model Canvas using a "Business Model Canvas software INTERLINKER" and add some text to it. This document could then be reused as if it were a template.</p> <p>Metadata Creation and Management</p> <p>Asset Instantiation: Interlinkers allow for the instantiation of assets, which could include metadata for citizen observations. For example, a "survey" interlinker could be used to create survey templates that include metadata fields for capturing citizen observations.</p>
Data Collection & Integration	<p>The tool itself does not support data collection analysis but can link to external tools that do. Furthermore, it can support the storage (upload and download) of multiple data file types which can be downloaded or accessed later. Indeed, a co-production process can have linked a repository with files generated for a CO campaign. Guide to Data Charter for Citizen Science.</p>
Visualization & Analysis	<p>The tool itself does not support visualization and analysis but can link to external tools that do.</p>
Security & Privacy	<p>Authentication: The project uses Keycloak which works under OpenID Connect (OIDC) for authentication, which is an open and secure standard.</p> <p>Secure Data Transfer: HTTPS is used and added to the fact that OIDC is used, the data transfer is secure.</p> <p>Secure Cookies:</p> <p>Cookies are set with the httponly=True directive, which means that they cannot be accessed through client-side scripts, improving security against attacks such as cookie theft.</p> <p>Cookies are also configured with the secure=settings.PRODUCTION_MODE directive, suggesting that cookies are only sent over HTTPS when production mode is enabled.</p> <p>Access Control: Authentication and access control are handled through microservices, and there is a mechanism to redirect users after authentication.</p>
Deployment model: Scalability & Performance	<p>Overview</p> <p>The CE project is designed to be deployed in various environments, each serving a different purpose:</p> <p>Local: For local private machine deployments, mainly for development.</p> <p>Demo: Central demo or staging environment to demonstrate new features.</p>

	<p>Pilot Environments: Production-like environments for specific Pilots</p> <p>All these environments are containerized using Docker and orchestrated with Docker Compose.</p> <p>Scalability</p> <p>The current deployment model is based on a single machine using Docker Compose. This setup is not inherently scalable across multiple machines. However, the project is designed with containerization in mind, making it easier to transition to a more scalable orchestration solution like Kubernetes in the future.</p> <p>Performance</p> <p>The project consists of various FastAPI applications and a React frontend, each serving different functionalities. FastAPI is known for its high performance, which should provide good response times for API calls.</p> <p>Handling Increasing Data Volumes, Concurrent Users, and System Load</p> <p>Data Volumes: it's containerized, integrating with scalable storage solutions should be straightforward.</p> <p>Concurrent Users: The FastAPI backend should be able to handle multiple concurrent users efficiently.</p> <p>System Load: The system is not designed for auto-scaling. However, since it's containerized, manual scaling of individual components is possible.</p> <p>System Requirements</p> <p>Software: A working installation of Docker and Docker Compose.</p> <p>Hardware: No minimum hardware specifications are provided, but the system should support standard amd64 architecture images.</p> <p>Network: For publicly available environments, a machine with a public IP is necessary.</p> <p>Constraints</p> <p>Single Machine: Currently, the deployment is limited to a single machine.</p> <p>No Auto-Scaling: The system does not automatically scale with user load or data volume; scaling must be configured manually</p>
<p>Social rating</p>	<p>In our platform, we highlight two main resources to facilitate the collaboration and co-production process with social rating features: the INTERLINKERs catalogue and the Stories.</p> <p>INTERLINKERs Catalogue</p> <p>In the catalogue, you will find a variety of INTERLINKERs/CO enablers designed to support the collaboration process. Each INTERLINKER can be rated by users on a scale of 1 to 5 stars, with 1 being the lowest rating and 5 being the highest. In addition, users have the option to leave a detailed review to share their experience with the INTERLINKER. As an additional feature, you can share your favourite INTERLINKER with others via the "share" button.</p> <p>Stories</p> <p>This section collects stories of successful co-production cases, providing inspiration and valuable reference points for other users. As in the catalogue, each story can be evaluated with a star rating system and allows users to leave detailed reviews. You can also take advantage of the "share" function to share stories you find valuable with other users. This could be useful to share Citizen Observatory campaigns' experiences.</p>

	<p>Claims Functionality</p> <p>As a complement to the resources, we have incorporated an additional social aspect through the "claims" functionality. Here, users can report the actions they have taken in the co-production processes. Although not a social feature per sé, claims can significantly influence the contribution scoring system, fostering a collaborative and competitive environment using gamification to value each user's contributions. Besides, claims can be used to understand what contributions each CO member has undertaken. User claims are moderated and validated by co-production process managers.</p>
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The Collaborative Environment offered by the University of Deusto provides comprehensive technical documentation to assist users in effectively utilizing the platform for Citizen Observatory and co-production processes. The key manuals available are as follows (Figure 42):

Figure 42: Collaborative Environments user manual view

Initial Configuration and Deployment (for Developers)

This [manual](#) outlines the steps required to set up the platform for initial configuration and deployment, primarily targeting developers. It provides instructions for downloading the source code from the repository and guides users through the development and demo environment setup.

Creation of Organizations and Teams

Users who are logged in can follow this [manual](#) to create a new organization within the platform. It offers guidance on filling in the necessary data and creating organizations for collaborative purposes. Furthermore, the manual also teaches how to build teams, specify stakeholder types, and invite team members, either by importing a list of emails or manually adding them.

Creation of a process

This [manual](#) walks users through the process of creating new co-production processes. Users are guided on defining the phases, objectives and tasks of a process via a guide view. In the sidebar, the manuals for all other views (leaderboard, workplan, teams and settings) are available, too.

System Configuration and Administration

This [manual](#) explains how to configure the settings and parameters of the entire project. It covers settings, process types, schema definitions, organization details, resource management, permissions, rewards, and finalizing the configuration.

Figure 43: Collaborative Environments settings view of a process

5.1.4 UrbanTEP / VISAT (GISAT)

Name	UrbanTEP/VISAT
URL	Production URL is currently unavailable DEV URL: https://greengage-dev.gisat.cz/
Description / abstract	<p>The UrbanTEP/VISAT web application, developed by GISAT for the GREENGAGE project, serves as a vital platform for data analysis and visualization, providing users with valuable insights and supporting the integration of project technologies into the policy-making lifecycle.</p> <p>NB: UrbanTEP/VISAT is complementary to the Superset platform: While Superset offers a creative and flexible data analysis platform for raw data collected in the Observatories, UrbanTEP/VISAT is providing a map-based interface that shall communicate the “Data Story” of an Observatory to the broader public via visualising findings and results in a more standardized and comprehensible way.</p> <p>Comprehensive technical manuals are available to help users fully leverage the application’s capabilities and maximize its impact.</p> <p>Key Features</p> <p>Data Integration and Provision: UrbanTEP/VISAT supports the integration of large and complex datasets based on Earth Observation data. It also facilitates data provision for analysis.</p> <p>Data Visualization: Users can effectively visualize geospatial data through both the interactive Explorer and curated User Stories, enabling comprehensive urban analysis and deeper understanding of real-world scenarios.</p>

Snapshots

visat urban

Tool Overview Use-cases Explorer

ABOUT

VISUALISATION & STATISTICS

WELCOME TO GREENGAGE URBAN THEMATIC EXPLOITATION PLATFORM

Gain deeper insights into the GREENGAGE pilots' use cases — showcasing how data can empower policymakers on the path toward sustainable urban development and an improved quality of life.

Dive into interactive maps, charts, and scenario-based models that highlight key thematic areas such as:

- Air Quality
- Area Attractiveness
- Mobility

[LEARN MORE IN STORY →](#)

EXPLORE THE DATA THROUGH INTERACTIVE VISUALIZATIONS AND USER STORIES

Explore the data interactively through the UrbanTEP / VISAT explorer and user stories, or access expert tools provided by GREENGAGE—such as Apache Superset and Apache Druid—to query, process, or manually download the data.

USE CASES

INTERACTIVE USER STORIES

Explore Land Use and Land Cover-based Integrated Sustainability Assessment together with Air Quality in a format of user stories

Select a pilot city

Turano (3 use-cases)

AREA ATTRACTIVENESS

Analysis of the attractiveness of the area for residents and visitors.

ENTER STORY

AIR QUALITY

Monitoring and assessment of air quality in the Turano region.

ENTER STORY

MOBILITY

Evaluation of mobility and transportation options in Turano.

ENTER STORY

DATA EXPLORER

ACCESS TO THE DATA

Select a dataset to explore within a specific pilot region and topic. To dive into a particular use case, choose one from the [use-cases](#) section.

Pilot city

Select pilot city [EXPLORE](#)

Figure 44: UrbanTEP/VISAT web application's home page

Authorship

GISAT

Audience	Website users, Citizens, Academia, Government institutions and authorities, Public audience.
Date creation	Jan 2023
Date modified	August 2025
Latest updates	The UrbanTEP/VISAT is constantly updating in order to address Pilot's needs by including new user stories and adding fresh-new datasets.
Keywords	GIS, Remote Sensing, Visualization, Interpretation, Dissemination
Category	Web application
License	ISC, open-source
Publisher	GISAT
Date published	May 2023
Theme	Engagement, Communication
Languages	English, Italian, (can be extended)
DOI	N/A
Nature	Internal software, dissemination material
Problem profile	Data integration, data visualization, data exploration, data analysis, data provision
Usage Examples	<p>Example: User wants to access a specific user story</p> <p>Step 1: Select a specific pilot</p> <p>Step 3: Access the user story by scrolling content and interacting with data via maps, charts and buttons</p>

	<p>GREENGAGE / UrbanTEP / Use cases / Turano / Area attractiveness</p> <p>TURANO VALLEY'S NATURAL ATTRACTIVENESS</p> <p>The Turano Valley is a representative example of the challenges faced by many rural and inner areas across Europe. It is composed of small, dispersed villages, often with only a few hundred residents.</p> <p>This low population density, combined with aging demographics and ongoing depopulation, limits access to basic services, infrastructure, and digital connectivity. These conditions make community engagement and the long-term participation of citizens more complex.</p> <p>That is why the use of the innovative and collaborative GREENGAGE app is particularly valuable — it offers a simple, accessible tool to involve residents, collect local data, and strengthen the connection between people and their environment. Through citizen observatories, even small communities can actively contribute to monitoring and improving sustainability in their territories.</p>
Documentation	<p>UrbanTEP/VISAT is designed with a user-friendly interface and intuitive workflows, making it largely self-explanatory even for first-time users. Most users can navigate and begin using the platform without prior documentation. However, for those seeking deeper insight into its background, features, and capabilities, comprehensive documentation is available on the official website at https://greengage-project.github.io/Documentation/tools/urbantep-visat/</p>
Support	<p>gisat@gisat.cz – GISAT</p> <p>andrii.khrystodulov@gisat.cz – Product owner</p> <p>tomas.soukup@gisat.cz – Commercial-related questions</p>
Complementarity / Interoperability	<p>UrbanTEP/VISAT plays a pivotal role in supporting Citizen Observatory co-production processes in three main areas: data integration and provision, data visualization, and data exploration and analysis of Observatory results. The extent of support required from UrbanTEP/VISAT for different Citizen Observatories depends on their specific needs and requirements.</p>
Open Standards & Protocols	<p>OGC, Raster data (Cloud-Optimized GeoTIFF), vector data (CSV, GeoJSON)</p>
APIs & Interfaces	<p>Graphical User Interface as a web application</p>
Modularity & Extensibility	<p>Backend is realized in microservice architecture, allowing easy interoperability. All core functions are format-agnostic and support for new data formats and sources can be added without disturbing existing code. Frontend is modular, based on React architecture, and allows for integration with new or existing tools.</p>
Metadata & Data Discovery	<p>Supports most common datasets types, such as raster and vector.</p>
Data Collection & Integration	<p>Doesn't collect data (except visitors' analytics). Integrates pilot-related datasets to support user stories.</p>
Visualization & Analysis	<p>VISAT facilitates easy exploration and comparison of geospatial data with the possibility to customize the display of data, compare one or more data sources in multiple synchronized map windows. It allows for easy work with both the spatial and temporal dimensions. In addition, attribute / indicator data can be visualised with various charts with possibility of simple addition of new ones. The interface can be adapted for various use cases to make understanding and working with specific datasets as easy as possible.</p>
Security & Privacy	<p>All data transfer happens via secure HTTPS connections, and authorization is implemented following OAuth 2.0 standards, ensuring robust security and privacy measures.</p>

Deployment model: Scalability & Performance	<p>UrbanTEP/VISAT employs a microservices architecture on the backend, ensuring easy interoperability and support for various data formats and sources. The frontend is modular, built on React architecture, and allows integration with both new and existing tools.</p> <p>The platform is designed to be scalable, with the ability to handle increasing data volumes, concurrent users, and system load. It is adaptable to different user needs and project requirements, whether deployed on a local machine, a demo environment, or production-like environments.</p>
Social rating	Not collected jet

5.1.5 MODE (AIT)

Name	MODE
URL	https://www.ait.ac.at/en/solutions/sensing-travel-behavior/mode
Description / abstract	<p>MODE software technology uses smartphones to automatically track the distances travelled and transport modes used, thus enabling software developers, system integrators and transport operators to design innovative mobility services. MODE provides the missing link for the development of innovative mobility services: automatic, reliable recognition of the means of transport used, and travelled routes using smartphones.</p>
Snapshots	<p>MODE is only a library which does not have a real screenshot. In the example below, one can see the usage where it prints out the activity on the command line.</p> <pre> 19 public class SimpleMain { 20 private static final String MODEL_FILE="instantModel.bin"; 21 private static final String HERE_appId = "a_valid_appId"; 22 private static final String HERE_appCode = "a_valid_appCode"; 23 24 public static void main(String[] args) throws Exception { 25 ActivityRecognition activityRecognition = createActivityRecognition(); 26 DataChunk data = DataChunkIO.FromAppData.parseFullData(Paths.get("dataCollectedBy 27 28 List<Activity> result = activityRecognition.analyze(data, /*params=*/emptyMap()); 29 for(Activity act: result) { 30 System.out.println(act); 31 } 32 } 33 34 private static ActivityRecognition createActivityRecognition() throws IOException { 35 InstantModel model = InstantModelIO.Binary.readInstantModel(Paths.get(MODEL_FILE) 36 Router router = HereAPI.createRouter(HERE_appId, HERE_appCode); 37 return new HybridActivityRecognition(model, router); 38 } 39 } 40 41 </pre> <p>The screenshot shows the following output:</p> <pre> Score: 0.6685806880179732 StandardTravelActivity [mode=WALK, modeDetails=null, getBegin()=2019-02-21T06:52:19.090Z, getE StandardTravelActivity [mode=SUBWAY, modeDetails=Line U1 (railMetro) from Keplerplatz to Kagra StandardTravelActivity [mode=WALK, modeDetails=Walk@16.443454, 48.2503974, NaN), getBegin()=2 StandardTravelActivity [mode=BUS, modeDetails=Line 31A (busPublic) from Kagraner Platz U to Si StandardTravelActivity [mode=WALK, modeDetails=Walk@16.4279294, 48.2673168, NaN), getBegin()= </pre>
Authorship	AIT
Audience	Researchers & Academics

Date creation	2015-2022
Date modified	2022
Latest updates	N/A
Keywords	Folksonomy created by those publishing new tools/resources to GREENGAGE catalogue. Mode detection Travel mode Library Software
Category	Software
License	Private license only to be used within the project or with written consent from AIT
Publisher	AIT
Date published	2022
Theme	Engagement
Languages	All languages (only a library without any user-visible text)
DOI	N/A
Nature	Internal software
Problem profile	Related to keywords with fixed taxonomy. We should consider defining a taxonomy of Citizen Observatory terms and categories. Possibly merge with "Metadata & Discovery" field
Usage Examples	The main usage of MODE is to be integrated in smartphone apps to track user travel behaviour. E.g. it was used in apps which incentivize "green" transport modes where you start the app and if it detects that you did the trip via bicycle or public transport you could earn "tokens" which could be spent on culture events. Example source code of MODE integration and basic explanation of all needed components is in the "Documentation" section of this document. The source code is NOT publicly available but is made accessible on request.
Documentation	Ensure comprehensive documentation is available, including installation guides, configuration instructions, API documentation, and usage examples. It should include the following sub-sections: <u>Overview</u>

MODE is a trip recording and mode detection framework. It consists of two main software components: a data recording module for iOS and Android Apps and a backend data analysis module. The above figure shows a high-level overview and demonstrates how to embed the MODE components into a system (AIT components are highlighted in blue, other components must be provided by a partner). Client-side tracking and data recording functionality can be added to an existing App by including the libMODE library. Once the library is configured and activated (libMODE API, see section “Frontend” below), it tracks user activity and records relevant movement data. The library transmits completed trips to a backend server using REST calls (REST API, see section “REST API”). On the server side, the transmitted trip data can be processed using the AIT JMDCA library. The JMDCA library is written in Java and provides core data structures, processing routines and analysis algorithms which allow application programmers to easily analyse trips and perform mode detection on the recorded data (JMDCA API, see section “Backend” below). To deliver high-quality results, the JMDCA mode detection algorithm requires access to a third-party public transit routing engine (such as HERE or Google routing).

Instructions

Frontend:

The MODE smartphone library (libMODE) provides a complete, out-of-the-box solution for mobility data collection via smartphone. It is built as an autonomous component that can easily be integrated into third party apps. For the standard use-case (trip data collection) the library can be integrated into existing Apps with little effort:

1. Add the library to the App as a build dependency

The most recent version of the libMODE library will be provided by AIT. The library can be added to the App by adding a corresponding dependency to the build. The following example shows how to add libMODE to the build.gradle of an Android App

```
30 dependencies {  
31     implementation 'at.ac.ait.mode:libmode:1.1.2'  
32 }
```

2. Initialize the library and start data collection

The library needs to be initialized before it can start recording data.

The following steps must be taken by the client code:

- request permission to record location data
ANDROID_PERMISSION_ACCESS_FINE_LOCATION
- initialize libMODE
- start recording

```
private void initLibMode() {  
    Context ctx = getApplicationContext();  
  
    Mode.initialize(ctx);  
  
    // Optional: allow data uploading via cellular network (otherwise data only gets uploaded when on WiFi)  
    Mode.getConfigurationEntry(Configuration.CONFIG_METERED_UPLOADING_ALLOWED).setBooleanValue(ctx, true);  
  
    // set Backend Server  
    Mode.setBaseServerURL("http://10.0.2.2:8080/smartsurvey/");  
  
    // Set OAUTH2 token manually  
    Mode.setAuthorizationToken("MY_OAUTH2_TOKEN");  
  
    // Start  
    Mode.startSurvey();  
}
```

The figure above shows a simple Java example how to initialize libMODE and start data collection¹. First libMODE is initialized, connected with the application context of the App and an API key is set. As different surveys can be hosted on different backend servers, a specific **survey must be selected** by calling Mode.setSurvey(). The MODE library performs a lookup of the survey name and determines the address of the backend server for all further communication. Once the correct backend server has been selected, a login is performed by providing a username and password². If the login was successful (and the required Android system permissions are granted by the user), data recording can be started by calling Mode.startSurvey().

After the survey has been started, **no further interaction with libMODE is required**. The library will take care of detecting, recording and uploading trips automatically.

REST API:

MODE's REST API consists of two parts, one for User management and one for Data handling. For collaboration, only the Data handling part is relevant, as user management is expected to be done by the host App:

Therefore, the REST backend only needs to provide these 2 methods (only upload(token, data) is really needed, uploadFragment() is for partial uploads which is not needed).

A potential implementation of the /upload endpoint using Spring framework could look like this:

```
/**
 * REST call which receives a trip file recorded by libMODE.
 *
 * Additional HTTP Headers: header field "Authorization" must
 contain a valid security Token
 *
 * @param file - the data file with the filename in @RequestParam
 "file" and the gzipped binary data as application/octet-stream
 * @return ResponseEntity(200, "success") if upload was
 successful
 *
 * @response 200 Upload successful
 * @response 401 User not authorized or Authentication Token
 missing
 * @response 420 User has not accepted the current privacy
 declaration
 */
@PostMapping("/upload")
public ResponseEntity<String>
uploadDataFile(@RequestHeader("Authorization") String authToken,
MultipartFile file) throws AuthenticationFailedException {
    User user = securityService.authenticateByToken(authToken);
    if(!user.isPrivacyDeclarationAccepted()) {
        log.warn("Rejecting data upload from {} : Privacy declaration
not accepted", user.getName());
        return ResponseEntity.status(420).body("Please accept privacy
declaration before uploading data!");
    }

    log.info("Got dataChunk from user {} with size {}kB",
user.getName(), file.getSize() / 1024.0);

    //TODO: storeData(user, file) somehow. for example:
    // Files.write(file.getBytes(),
Paths.get(String.format("/tmp/dc_%s_%s.dat.gz", user.getName(),
System.currentTimeMillis())).ToFile());

    // Example : on-the-fly analyze
    try {
        ARResult result = modeApi.analyze(file.getBytes());
    }
}
```

```

        System.out.println("Result:");
        for(Activity act: result.getActivities()) {
            System.out.println(act);
        }
        System.out.println("isPlausible=" +
result.getMetaInfo().getPropertyOrDefault(IS_PLAUSIBLE, false));
    } catch(Exception e) {
        log.error("Activity Recognition failed", e);
    }
}

// HTTP response code must be between 200 and 299 (otherwise
the App will think the upload failed and will try uploading again)
return ResponseEntity.ok("success");
}

```

Backend:

The **ActivityRecognition Library** (JMDCALib) is provided by AIT as a JAR file (or maven dependency). A simple Java usage example for performing an activity recognition on trip data recorded by the app looks like this:

```

19 public class SimpleMain {
20     private static final String MODEL_FILE="instantModel.bin";
21     private static final String HERE_appId = "a_valid_appId";
22     private static final String HERE_appCode = "a_valid_appCode";
23
24     public static void main(String[] args) throws Exception {
25         ActivityRecognition activityRecognition = createActivityRecognition();
26         DataChunk data = DataChunkIO.FromAppData.parseFullData(Paths.get("dataCollectedByLibMode.dat.gz"));
27
28         List<Activity> result = activityRecognition.analyze(data, /*params=*/emptyMap());
29         for(Activity act: result) {
30             System.out.println(act);
31         }
32     }
33
34     private static ActivityRecognition createActivityRecognition() throws IOException {
35         InstantModel model = InstantModelIO.Binary.readInstantModel(Paths.get(MODEL_FILE));
36         Router router = HereAPI.createRouter(HERE_appId, HERE_appCode);
37         return new HybridActivityRecognition(model, router);
38     }
39 }
40
41

```



```

<terminated> SimpleMain [Java Application] /usr/lib/jvm/java-8-oracle/bin/java (Jun 26, 2019, 2:42:54 PM)
* Segment[ 2019-02-21T07:45:23Z, WALK, Line none (none),2019-02-21T07:48:54Z, LINESTRING(16.4278865 48.2688984,
)]
Score: 0.6685806880179732
StandardTravelActivity [mode=WALK, modeDetails=null, getBegin()=2019-02-21T06:52:19.090Z, getEnd()=2019-02-21T06:59:37.05
StandardTravelActivity [mode=SUBWAY, modeDetails=Line U1 (railMetro) from Keplerplatz to Kagraner Platz, getBegin()=2019-
StandardTravelActivity [mode=WALK, modeDetails=Walk@{16.443454, 48.2503974, NaN}, getBegin()=2019-02-21T07:17:26.090Z, ge
StandardTravelActivity [mode=BUS, modeDetails=Line 31A (busPublic) from Kagraner Platz U to Siemensstr./Heinrich-von-Buol
StandardTravelActivity [mode=WALK, modeDetails=Walk@{16.4279294, 48.2673168, NaN}, getBegin()=2019-02-21T07:35:58.090Z, c

```

First, the ActivityRecognition method is instantiated. This requires an InstantModel³ (which is loaded from a file) and a connection to an external router (in the example the HERE routing engine is used).

The binary data recorded by the App is parsed by the utility class DataChunkIO. The generated DataChunk object contains a compact representation of the collected trip data and is used as input for the ActivityRecognition method. The ActivityRecognition output is a list of activities which represent the identified stages of the trip. The lower part of the figure shows the output of the example program. The identified stages ("TravelActivities") are printed in a simple text form (including detailed public transport information in the attribute "modeDetails").

	<p>For a real implementation, this backend code is integrated in the “REST API” service from the previous section (replace “modeApi” there with an instance obtained by this createActivityRecognition()).</p> <p>Reviews</p> <p>N/A</p> <p>Related resources</p> <p>Detailed sample code and SDK documentation on how to use the library are in private Gitlab repositories hosted by AIT. Credentials to access them will be given to partners on request.</p> <p>Preview</p> <p>N/A</p> <p>Make sure that you answer to the following questions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What role does it cover withing GREEN Engine? <p>To be used by other apps to find out exact trips and the travel mode of users with a smartphone.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How does it foster CS and contribute to form COs? <p>Using MODE, we can monitor people (who opt-in for these things!) to see their travel behavior.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What part of the data processing pipeline covers if any? <p>Data collection of raw (GPS) data and data processing of generating grips out of the raw data</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Where and how it should be used? <p>To see if users choose different routes and/or different mode of transports before and after certain measures (closing roads, parking changes, ...) have be implemented.</p>
Support	E-Mail: martin.stubenschrott@ait.ac.at
Complementarity / Interoperability	The library is a “standard” Android .jar file and iOS Swift package which can be easily integrated into the respective smartphone host apps.
Open Standards & Protocols	Authentication is done by sending “Authorization” headers in each HTTP request
APIs & Interfaces	As documented in the source code repository which is given access to on demand. An easy-to-use guide is also published at https://greengage-project.github.io/Documentation/tools/mode/
Modularity & Extensibility	N/A – the library is meant to be integrated “as-is”.
Metadata & Data Discovery	N/A
Data Collection & Integration	MODE collects heterogenous smart phone data (GPS, cell tower IDs, accelerometer, ...) and processes it to gather high-level data of the time and travel mode which was used for a trip, and the full GPS path. The output only exists in a Java API and must be stored by the host of the library in a database or any other format like JSON.
Visualization & Analysis	No built-in visualization of the resulting travel data. That must be done by another app which uses our library.

Security & Privacy	The endpoint which uses our library MUST use HTTPs to protect the transfer. Once a transfer is done, the raw data is automatically deleted from the smart phone itself. The backend must then make sure that the resulting travel data is stored according to GDPR law. All communication between the frontend library and backend library shall use the “Authentication” header to identify the user.
Deployment model: Scalability & Performance	The system requires a Java-based host which integrates our library. Processing of the data on the backend is not real-time critical, therefore it is easy to batch processing of the incoming raw data according to free resources on the host.
Social rating	N/A

The MODE software technology, developed by AIT, leverages smartphone capabilities to automatically track travel behaviour, including distances travelled and modes of transportation used. As MODE is a software library, it is integrated within the GREENGAGE app and cannot be accessed directly, but is triggered via the “Track Me” button within the app. Below is a detailed overview of the resource:

Description / Abstract

MODE provides automatic and reliable recognition of transportation modes and travel routes using smartphones. This facilitates the analysis of the efficiency and effectiveness of urban mobility, as well as identification of overall travel mode usage.

Usage Examples

The MODE library is integrated into the GREENGAGE app to track user travel behaviour. For instance, it has been employed in apps incentivizing "green" transport modes, allowing users to earn rewards for choosing environmentally friendly transportation options. Example source code for MODE integration is available upon request.

Documentation

Overview: It provides a high-level understanding of MODE's components, including data recording modules for iOS and Android apps, and the backend data analysis module. It illustrates how MODE components can be embedded into a system.

Instructions (Frontend): The instructions guide developers through the integration of the MODE's smartphone library (libMODE) into existing apps. This involves steps like adding the library as a build dependency, initializing the library, and starting data collection.

REST API: Details the REST API used for data handling, focusing on user management and data transmission. It includes an example implementation of the /upload endpoint.

Backend: Offers a Java usage example for performing activity recognition on trip data recorded by the app. It outlines the instantiation of the Activity Recognition method and its integration with an external router.

Complementarity / Interoperability

MODE complements Citizen Observatory co-production processes by enabling the precise tracking of trips and travel modes using smartphones.

Open Standards & Protocols

MODE uses HTTP headers for authentication in each request.

Modularity & Extensibility

While MODE is meant to be integrated as-is, it allows for seamless incorporation into existing applications, demonstrating a level of modularity.

Security & Privacy

MODE ensures data security and privacy by using HTTPS for data transfer, automatically deleting raw data from smartphones after transfer, and implementing user authentication through its "Authorization" header.

Deployment Model: Scalability & Performance

The system requires a Java-based host for integration. Data processing on the backend is not real-time critical, allowing for batch processing based on available resources.

5.1.6 Data Quality Dashboard (VRVis)

Name	Data Quality and Structure Dashboard
URL	https://qualitydashboard.greengage-project.eu/
Description / abstract	<p>Data Quality Dashboard is a modular system composed of 4 interactive linked views (a spatial map, a heatmap, histogram, and a line plot) that allow for an informed quality check of time-series data.</p> <p>The Trend Line serves to inspect the completeness of the imported time-series by visually highlighting missing values (e.g., with vertical blue markings) and provides an overview of a time-based development (e.g., hourly) of the inspected parameter (e.g., air quality, noise levels, traffic flows).</p> <p>The Heatmap helps with inspecting the evolution of the inspected parameter across two axis variables (i.e., hour vs. day, day vs. month) in a calendar view manner as a grid of coloured cells, where each cell's colour indicates an aggregated value of the inspected parameter.</p> <p>The Spatial Map allows for plotting the geographical location of the data collection points, alongside providing the overview of individual values for the selected parameter.</p> <p>The Histogram provides insight into the distribution of the data, showing how frequently different values occur and allowing for interactive filtering.</p> <p>The tool offers a drill-down functionality to lower granularities of the time series, such as the inspection of yearly, monthly, daily values. The tool also offers descriptive statistics of the data with an overview of a number of measures (i.e., max, min, mean, standard deviation, etc.). The tool is meant to support the initial quality assessment of the citizen-collected data, as well as the existing authoritative datasets.</p>

Snapshots	<p>The screenshot displays a comprehensive data analysis dashboard for PM2.5 (ug/m3) in Rome. It includes a geographical map of monitoring stations, a histogram of the frequency distribution, a 'Data Quality Metrics' section with circular gauges for Temporal Uniqueness (100%), Completeness (98.33%), and Validity (100%), and a Value Uniqueness gauge (87.28%). Additionally, there is a heatmap for temporal distribution and a time series analysis plot showing data points over time.</p>
Authorship	VRVis Zentrum für Virtual Reality und Visualisierung Forschungs-GmbH
Audience	Community Members & Citizens, Policy & Decision Makers
Date creation	01.05.2023 (the tool has been conceptualized specifically for the purpose of the GREENGAGE project, based on the existing VA framework developed by VRVis)
Date modified	May 2023 – April 2025
Latest updates	April 2025
Keywords	Data Quality, Data Analysis
Category	Software
License	Open source (Apache 2.0)
Publisher	VRVis Zentrum für Virtual Reality und Visualisierung Forschungs-GmbH
Date published	Q1 2024
Theme	Data quality and standards
Languages	English
DOI	N/A
Nature	External software
Problem profile	Data Quality Assessment
Usage Examples	<p>Upon establishing a connection to the dataset (here Atmotube PRO - air quality dataset), users are greeted with an interactive map interface. This map showcases the locations of air quality monitoring stations in the region, providing a geographical context for data exploration.</p> <p>Users can engage with the map to gain immediate insights into current air quality measurements at each monitoring station. Real-time data previews are accessible through simple interactions with the map, making it easy to grasp the current air quality conditions.</p>

Furthermore, users have the capability to select specific stations and time periods to retrieve historical air quality data. Once a station is chosen, the tool generates relevant visualizations and performs calculations of statistical and data quality indices. (See “Snapshot” section for overview of the dashboard)

By default, the tool displays recorded measurements for the current month. However, users have the freedom to delve deeper into the dataset by selecting different timeframes and dates through the options window, enabling exploration of various data intervals, if the data is available.

SiteID: 672 Time period: Month Pollutant: NO2 Aggregation interval: Daily Hourly

2023 February

2023		
Jan	Feb	Mar
Apr	May	Jun

The tool empowers users to tailor their analysis precisely. They can select between annual or monthly visualization modes, each offering (in this example) unique perspectives on air quality trends.

The heatmap visualization is a standout feature of the tool. It transforms data into an intuitive calendar heatmap format, showcasing the concentration of air pollutants over time. This format unveils subtle patterns and trends within the data, contributing to a more insightful analysis of air quality dynamics.

Users can fine-tune their analysis by choosing between hourly and daily data aggregations of measured values. For daily aggregation, it presents mean pollutant concentration values for each day within the selected timeframe.

To complement the heatmap, the tool includes component to create an interactive line chart. This chart reveals the evolution of measurements throughout the chosen period. Notably, it highlights missing data points with distinctive color solids, aiding users in identifying gaps in the dataset.

Data quality dashboard informs user on the quality of explored dataset by provision of relevant data quality metrics applicable to its type and nature of variable in question.

	<p>This example showcases how using the available tool's components one can create immersive and informative data exploration experiences. Through interactive maps and dynamic visualizations, users can gain valuable insights into real-time and historical air quality conditions while tailoring their analyses to specific needs. Additionally, the tool's robust data quality detection features, highlighting data gaps and outliers, enhance the reliability of the analyses and insights generated.</p>
Documentation	https://greengage-project.github.io/Documentation/tools/DataQualityDashboard/
Support	Continuous support by VRVis during the project.
Complementarity / Interoperability	Through integration with the project's Druid datastore, the dashboard provides seamless access to stored time-series datasets.
Open Standards & Protocols	No standards in place, but development based on open-source libraries and protocols.
APIs & Interfaces	Interfaces to data sources will be implemented upon request and agreement, we are not restricted to any type of interface, we are able to comply with all available open protocols for data transfer.
Modularity & Extensibility	Two possibilities of how to intergrade the tool: 1. The tool consists of a collection of ReactJS functional components that can be integrated into an existing web application or customized to create a dashboard that aligns with specific implementation requirements. 2. We provide a Docker container with interfaces to data sources.
Metadata & Data Discovery	N/A
Data Collection & Integration	We can provide connection to any data source that is needed.
Visualization & Analysis	The tool provides several relevant visualizations to help detect quality issues and gain insights from imported data. Specifically, for the analysis of data generated by sensors and monitoring stations, which primarily consists of time series data of measured values, we offer the following ReactJS functional components: trend lines, calendar heatmaps, histograms, and map charts. These visualizations are complemented by a range of statistical metrics and data quality indicators.

Security & Privacy	We comply with all standards regarding web security.
Deployment model: Scalability & Performance	The dashboard is a client-side application that runs in a web browser and can be served from any modern web server. Developers can easily create new connectors to support additional data sources such as REST, SQL, or CSV.
Social rating	N/A

The Data Quality Dashboard (DQD) by VRVis provides a comprehensive set of tools and resources to monitor the quality and structure of data in the context of Citizen Observatory projects. It serves as a critical component in maintaining data integrity and usability within a Citizen Observatory project. Its user-friendly interface and powerful features empower data managers and administrators to efficiently control datasets before further analysis and utilization.

Documentation

The documentation is available as part of the GREENGAGE project on its GitHub documentation page (<https://greengage-project.github.io/Documentation/tools/DataQualityDashboard/>).

User Guide

The GREENGAGE documentation page also includes a detailed walkthrough of the features and functionalities of the Data Quality Dashboard. This includes step-by-step instructions on tasks such as data validation, issue detection, and quality assessment.

Modularity & Extensibility

The dashboard follows a component-based architecture that provides some flexibility for customization. Its structure allows for extension of visualization panels, data analysis tools, and quality assessment features. Developers can adapt the dashboard to specific requirements by adding new visualization components, modifying existing ones, or integrating additional data quality metrics. The system's utility functions and configurable components provide a foundation for implementing custom data processing and analysis features, making it adaptable to various use cases and requirements.

Security & Privacy

DQD ensures data security and privacy by using HTTPS for data transfer,

5.1.7 GREENGAGE app (Sushi Dev/Digitalsunray)

Name	GREENGAGE app
URL	https://console-stage.greengage.dev
Description / abstract	<p>The GREENGAGE app, including its console, is a powerful tool designed to capture data in the form of missions and tasks, making it accessible through standardized interfaces such as GEOJSON. It provides a variety of parameters and tools—such as surveys, spots, and image uploads—that can be used to collect relevant information efficiently and in a structured manner. This flexibility allows users to adapt the app to a wide range of scenarios, ensuring that data is captured consistently and can be seamlessly integrated with other systems.</p> <p>The GREENGAGE console serves as the central platform for administering and managing the collected data. It is built with ease of use in mind, requiring no technical expertise to set up or configure. In just a few minutes, users can customize the console to meet their specific needs, making it a practical solution for teams and organizations looking to streamline data collection and management workflows without the need for extensive training or IT support.</p>
Snapshots	iOS/Android APP

Visualisation of the tasks within the GREENGAGE App. This app is made for endusers – that means for those users who will submit the data you are looking for.

Console / Administration

A tool that allows tasks, POIs, spots, surveys, and other observatory data to be managed and administered quickly and easily.

Authorship	Digitalsunray Media GmbH (iOS/Android App) Sushi Dev GmbH (API, Console)
Audience	Anyone who wants to aggregate data on a geo level.
Date creation	2025-09-04
Date modified	2025-09-04
Latest updates	2025-09-04 (continues development so this might be already outdated)
Keywords	App, Survey, Geo Tracking, Photo Input, User generated content
Category	Software
License	Closed source – Console can be used as free SaaS

Publisher	Sushi Dev GmbH and Digital Sunray GmbH
Date published	2024
Theme	Engagement / Survey
Languages	English / German
DOI	-
Nature	-
Problem profile	Getting user input (survey data etc) on certain geo coordinates + provide geo tracking data from used routes.
Usage Examples	<p>The GREENGAGE app is a mobile application designed to be highly adaptable, enabling seamless integration into a wide range of usage scenarios. It is important to emphasize that while the core functionality of the application (Tasks, Points of Interest (POIs), Spots, and Geo-Tracking) provides a solid foundation, the system can be extensively customized to match the specific needs of different projects or organizations.</p> <p>Scenario 1: Problem Detection and Reporting</p> <p>Traditionally, reports about local issues or incidents reach municipal authorities via outdated communication channels such as telephone calls, emails, or even physical letters. These methods are often unsatisfactory: they are slow, prone to errors, and lack structured data.</p> <p>With the GREENGAGE app, this process can be modernised and made significantly more efficient. Using the Spot functionality, citizens can quickly and easily submit problem reports directly from their mobile devices. Each submission is automatically linked to a precise geo-location, ensuring that authorities immediately know the exact position of the reported issue.</p> <p><u>Key advantages:</u></p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Contextual descriptions for detailed reporting. 2. Linkage to user accounts for follow-up communication. 3. Centralized administration interface for oversight. 4. Integration into third-party systems through dashboards, exports, and APIs.

Scenario 2: Environmental Monitoring

Citizen Observatories often focus on monitoring environmental conditions such as air quality, water quality, or biodiversity. The GREENGAGE app provides a flexible framework for such activities:

POIs (Points of Interest) can mark designated monitoring stations or sampling areas.

Tasks can be done by participating citizens or research groups, guiding them to collect specific data (e.g., temperature, pollution levels, or wildlife sightings) via surveys.

Spots allow contributors to submit field observations, enriched with geolocation and supporting descriptions.

This scenario demonstrates how GREENGAGE can empower communities to contribute meaningful data to environmental projects, complementing professional research efforts with large-scale citizen engagement.

Scenario 3: Mobility Tracking and Transportation Analysis

The GREENGAGE app also integrates with the **MODE tool developed by AIT**, which enables precise geo-position tracking combined with automated transportation mode detection. This functionality is particularly valuable in urban regions where citizens have access to a wide variety of transportation options.

A typical use case could involve analyzing **how students travel to school**: where they come from, which routes they take, and which modes of transport (e.g., walking, cycling, public transport, or car) they rely on.

How it works:

Users simply start tracking at the beginning of a journey and stop it upon arrival at their destination. The system automatically processes the recorded movement data and assigns the most likely transportation mode based on behavioural patterns and location data. For example, it can distinguish between a student cycling on a busy road versus using a safer parallel bike path located just 100 meters away.

Key benefits:

- **Granular insights** into how mobility infrastructure is used in practice.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Real-time visibility: Data streams can be monitored through the GREENGAGE dashboard almost in real time. • Contextual enrichment: Collected mobility data can be combined with surveys at the destination (e.g., schools or workplaces) to gain deeper insights into travel behavior and decision-making. <p>This scenario highlights how GREENGAGE supports evidence-based planning for urban mobility, helping decision-makers identify patterns, evaluate infrastructure, and design safer, more sustainable transport solutions.</p>
Documentation	https://docs-stage.greengage.dev/
Support	support@sushi.dev
Complementarity / Interoperability	Mindview APP for GREENGAGE MODE by AIT
Open Standards & Protocols	GraphQL, GeoJSON
APIs & Interfaces	<p>The GREENGAGE App is built on a flexible GraphQL API, which can be seamlessly integrated into existing tools. Thanks to GraphQL Federation, the API can also be incorporated into your own toolset in a simple and efficient way.</p> <p>Documentation on how to use the API interface is available at: https://docs-stage.greengage.dev/docs/api/how-to-use-the-api</p>
Modularity & Extensibility	Software landscape can be included via GraphQL Federation into your own application.
Metadata & Data Discovery	Use the api playground api-v2.greengage.dev to explore the possible option of data types.
Data Collection & Integration	Provides an API (GraphQL) for collection and reading the data.
Visualization & Analysis	The console provides a simple and intuitive interface for reviewing aggregated data.
Security & Privacy	Data is organized by observatories and can be deleted at any time. Image data is hosted in the Digital Asset Management System fairu.app , where it remains available. The software is continuously being improved and updated.
Deployment model: Scalability & Performance	<p>Ready to use within minutes. Solution is available as a SaaS and includes a free tier.</p> <p>iOS and Android App is free.</p>
Social rating	-

Administrator Manual

The Administrator Manual delves into the backend functionalities of GREENGAGE app, focusing on system configuration, user management, and access control, empowering administrators to efficiently manage the platform. The documentation is accessible via <https://docs-stage.greengage.dev>.

API Documentation and Playground

As of the nature of GraphQL the documentation can be automatically created based on the schema files. Because the GREENGAGE app's API is strongly based on the concept of federation (<https://www.apollographql.com/docs/federation/>) a final documentation cannot be provided because all the connected APIs automatically contribute to this.

NB: Due to the nature of the provided service the API (and the complete schema) can be explored via the “Playground”, which is an interactive tool which guides a user through the process of interacting with the data.

Figure 45: Screenshot of the “API playground” © Digitalsunray

5.1.8 Text analysis – sentiment / summarisation (UWE)

Name	Text Analysis – Sentiment / Summarisation
URL	N/A
Description / abstract	<p>Using Large Language Models (LLMs) - Flan-T5, sentiment analysis is performed on transcripts from videos, interviews, and written texts from citizens. Inputs are processed by the LLM to detect emotional tone and classified with a binary label (1 for positive sentiment and 0 for negative).</p> <p>A text summarization service, leveraging LLaMA 3, was developed to summarize content from qualitative comments submitted by citizens through the EBLN25 platform. This tool is designed to help the Pilot owner and other stakeholders quickly grasp key themes from large volumes of textual survey data.</p>
Snapshots	Refer to section 4.1.8 (Figure 22)
Authorship	UWE Bristol
Audience	Public authorities and other organisations who conduct surveys
Date creation	August 2023
Date modified	Ongoing
Latest updates	Ongoing
Keywords	Sentiment analysis, summarisation
Category	Software
License	TBD
Publisher	N/A
Date published	N/A

Theme	Analysis, Evaluation, Impact
Languages	English, Italian
DOI	N/A
Nature	Internal Software but with potential to be hosted as a service
Problem profile	Data analytics
Usage Examples	<p>Currently, sentiment analysis takes place in offline mode. A prototype web interface was developed to test perform end-user testing and refinement of the summarisation service. The interface currently only supports summarisation but is being extended to support both sentiment classification as well as thematic analysis. These extensions include inputting text directly, select their preferred sentiment categories, and receive results without needing to interact with code or command-line interfaces. The interface is simple to use. Once the web interface is rendered in a web browser, users have three input fields:</p> <p>Context: This is the text field, and user can enter specific thematic context for which they would like to generate a summary. This is optional field and can be left blank.</p> <p>Data file: This is a file type field. Here an end user can upload raw data e.g., an .xlsx file with all comments. User can drag and drop a file or browse their computer to select a file.</p> <p>Submit: On clicking submit button, all data is sent to backend summarisation service to perform summarisation on the raw data file i.e. .xlsx file. The summarised output is generated on the bottom of the web page.</p>
Documentation	N/A
Support	Kamran.Soomro@uwe.ac.uk Elisa.Covato@uwe.ac.uk Zaheer.Khan@uwe.ac.uk Mohammad.Bilal@uwe.ac.uk , Mohammad.Bilal@bcu.ac.uk
Complementarity / Interoperability	<p>With RAG extension and service hosting this can be an impactful service, not only for GREENGAGE pilots but for other organisations as well.</p> <pre> graph LR subgraph Input_data [Input data] A[Load survey responses] --> B[Generate embeddings all-MiniLM-L6-v2] end subgraph Knowledge_Base [Knowledge Base] C[Load Knowledge Base data] --> D[Generate embeddings all-MiniLM-L6-v2] end B --> E[Retrieval cosine similarity, top-5] D --> E subgraph RAG_system [RAG system] E --> F[Augment prompt with retrieved-context] F --> G[Generate response return classification label] end </pre> <p><i>Figure 46: Retrieval Augmented Generation (RAG) workflow implemented for the sentiment analysis.</i></p>
Open Standards & Protocols	N/A
APIs & Interfaces	N/A
Modularity & Extensibility	N/A
Metadata & Data Discovery	N/A

Data Collection & Integration	In the current version, the input data is in .xlsx or csv format but have the potential to extend it for images
Visualization & Analysis	Output is in the form of summarised text or sentiment score
Security & Privacy	N/A
Deployment model: Scalability & Performance	<p>Currently, sentiment analysis and summarization run in off-line mode. For text summarization a streamlit web app (see below) was developed for testing.</p> <div style="text-align: center;"> <h3>Summary Generator</h3> </div> <p><i>Figure 47: Summarisation service web interface allows to upload comments file with user prompt to generate the summary</i></p>
Social rating	N/A

5.1.9 Video analytics (UWE)

Name	Video Analytics – Dashcam Road Defects Detection
URL	N/A
Description / abstract	The image analysis has been applied to dashcam footage, aiming to spot a wide range of roadway defects for the Turano Pilot, including potholes, surface cracks, faded road markings, and vandalised road signs.
Snapshots	Refer to section 4.1.9 (Figure 23)

Figure 48: Dashcam footage analytics dashboard view

Authorship	UWE
Audience	Public Authorities
Date creation	March 2025
Date modified	Ongoing
Latest updates	Ongoing
Keywords	Dashcam footage, Segmentation, Road defects, Analytics
Category	Software
License	TBD
Publisher	N/A
Date published	N/A
Theme	Engagement, Evaluation, Communication, Impact
Languages	English, Italian
DOI	N/A
Nature	Internal Software
Problem profile	Auto detection of road defects through Dashcam footage
Usage Examples	Currently, all video processing takes place in offline mode. The processed videos are returned to users as shown in Figure 48. For a sustainable service, a video analytics dashboard is currently under development that aims to allow end users to upload and visualise road inspection videos as well as explore, assess and identify road defects. The dashboard was developed using Oracle APEX and will be made available to end users once ready. Appropriate training videos will be prepared as needed once this is completed (autumn 2025). For labelling and training CVAT platform was deployed and configured for users. Several training sessions and usage instructions were provided to users for CVAT.

Figure 49: CVAT platform for labelling dashcam images for selected classes

Documentation	N/A
Support	Muhammad.Bilal@uwe.ac.uk / Muhammad.Bilal@bcu.ac.uk Kamran.Soomro@uwe.ac.uk Zaheer.Khan@uwe.ac.uk
Complementarity / Interoperability	The tool takes a video as input and then selects specific frames for analysis and generates a JSON file as output that includes defects with spatial coordinates.
Open Standards & Protocols	N/A
APIs & Interfaces	N/A
Modularity & Extensibility	N/A
Metadata & Data Discovery	N/A
Data Collection & Integration	The tool takes a dashcam video as input for processing.
Visualization & Analysis	The output is also visualised as a video highlighting road defect and their types.
Security & Privacy	Video frames are pre-processed to anonymise identifiable objects such as car registration, faces etc.
Deployment model: Scalability & Performance	The current proof of concept would require high performance service hosting to be able to process videos and identify defects on a large scale.
Social rating	N/A

5.2 Pilot specific tools used in GREENGAGE

5.2.1 Verplaatsingsdata app used by North Brabant

Name	Verplaatsingsdata App
URL	https://play.google.com/store/apps/details?id=nl.mobidot.sesamo&hl=nl

Description / abstract	<p>We provide you a full-service to collect and manage a detailed data set of the travel behaviour of your target groups. For longer or shorter times. For small or very large groups. It's up to you. The data gives unmatched insights on how people move over the day providing valuable answers for your market research, panel surveys and urban policy development and impact evaluation.</p> <p>The app automatically starts measuring with minimal load for the respondent. Our web-based data management portal gives all you need to manage your user-base, create data overviews and statistics, perform drilldowns and leverage the flexible data export and audit capabilities. It delivers GPS-based tracking data of your respondent base. What are trip origins and destinations and what modalities are favourite? What times do people travel, what routes do they take and what is the purpose of their travel?</p>
Authorship	Mobidot B.V.
Audience	Project Participants; Panel Members
Date creation	(month/year – example: October 2023)
Date modified	(month/year – example: November 2024)
Latest updates	09/2024 – minor bug fixes and performance improvement.
Keywords	Tracking, Modalities, Mobility profile, travel & local
Category	Software
License	(List all the licenses)
Publisher	Mobidot B.V.
Date published	-
Theme	Travel & Mobility
Languages	Dutch
DOI	N/A
Nature	App
Problem profile	The Verplaatsingsdata app tracks trips by users and identifies used modalities. It provides a mobility profile of the user.
Usage Examples	<p>Verplaatsingsdata is a mobile application designed to track travel patterns in North Brabant. It is a version of the Sesamo app by Mobidot, adapted for specific use in the Verplaatsingsdata project. The app tracks the trip sections as well as the modality used, which they can subsequently review and adjust. This manual outlines how to use the Verplaatsingsdata app – Sesamo - effectively.</p> <p>This technology enables policy makers to enlist citizens in gathering mobility data – specifically routing, and origin-destination data. It thereby serves as a data gathering technology at the start of the data processing pipeline. The focus hereby is on mapping the existing network and identifying recurrent functions of links in the network.</p> <p>A deeper understanding of the travel patterns, modality use, and roads (not taken, allows COs to study the movement pattern throughout a neighbourhood and determine the accessibility of different modalities. This, for instance, includes the logging of the effect of road closures as well as the intensity of the traffic during specific months to an area.</p> <p>The app can also send out a selective survey to some of its users to enhance the gathered data with some qualitative data.</p> <p>Account Creation and Setup:</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Visit the App Store or Google Play Store and search for "Sesamo" • Download and install the app on your smartphone (Android or iOS). • Log in is only possible using the account provided for you through the project or in the mobility panel. <p>App Use:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Once installed, the app will track movement patterns automatically. • Different legs of the trip are logged as separate instances, and the modality used is identified. • Likely travel objectives are pre-filled per trip or section of the trip. • Users can search through their trips through a calendar. • Trips and sections can be reviewed, edited, validated, or removed. • Registration can be removed or stopped at any time.
Documentation	<p>https://www.movesmarter.nl/portal/faq</p> <p>For the app to function properly, it is important that the following settings are ON:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • GPS (location) without energy saving/battery mode • Wifi • Mobile data • Measuring in the app
Support	<p>info@mobidot.nl – Public Communication</p> <p>For platform-related questions: info@dat.nl</p>
Complementarity / Interoperability	<p>The gathered mobility data is the start of the data pipeline. The curation, analysis, and visualisation come after. Therefore, the gathered data can be linked to the VRVis data quality platform, or the data can be visualised in the DigiTwin. The app is specifically focused on the North Brabant region and the Limburg region. This focus decreases the interoperability in other pilots but does ensure familiarity in the North Brabant pilot.</p>
Open Standards & Protocols	<p>Unknown</p>
APIs & Interfaces	<p>Unknown</p>
Modularity & Extensibility	<p>The app is focused on gathering GPS data. It is possible to send small questionnaires through the app as well. There is no possibility to expand the user possibilities in the app, but there are links to data analysis programmes possible such as Microsoft PowerBI.</p>
Metadata & Data Discovery	<p>The data is accessible to users through a calendar function. There is no other search function for specific trips.</p>
Data Collection & Integration	<p>Within GREENGAGE, the pilot owners of North Brabant will only have access to the pseudo-anonymised, and aggregated datasets of the patterns. These travel patterns can be integrated into mapping software such as the DigiTwin or platforms like PowerBI.</p>
Visualization & Analysis	<p>The platform links with Microsoft PowerBI for visualisation options. Here it can specify:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Demography

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Modal Split • Travel Motive • Trip Duration • Origin • Distance
Security & Privacy	The app is fully GDPR compliant and ensures that partners only have access to the data that they require. Personal data is only used for the legitimate goal of the assignment. Data is furthermore encrypted when transferred, and can be deleted upon request.
Deployment model: Scalability & Performance	The app started gathering travel data from November 2023 onwards with a carefully selected representative sample of users. These were specific users from mobility panels or investigation groups. After this initial representative gathering, other users were invited to join and download the app.
Social rating	Unknown

5.2.2 Urban Belonging app used by Copenhagen

Name	Urban Belonging App
URL	https://urbanbelonging.com/ https://play.google.com/store/apps/details?id=com.urbanbelonging.app&hl=en
Description / abstract	<p>The Urban Belonging (UB) App is a photovoice-based mobile application developed within the Urban Belonging project in Copenhagen (2022). It allows participants to capture photos of their urban environment, annotate them with sentiment and tags, and react to other participants' contributions. By combining personal imagery with geolocation, timestamps, and metadata, the app creates rich qualitative and quantitative datasets that explore how marginalized communities experience "belonging" in the city.</p> <p>The app's participatory design ensured accessibility and inclusivity, incorporating feedback from researchers, Gehl Architects, citizen engagement professionals, and six marginalized communities. It is available for iOS and Android in multiple languages, and has been tested within GREENGAGE to support data collection, participatory mapping, and co-creation.</p>
Snapshots	<p>The screenshot displays the app's interface. On the left, there are filters for 'Walks', 'Photos', 'Clusters', 'Areas', and 'User Segments'. Below these are sections for 'Do people agree on their response?' (High agreement), 'What do you notice in this picture?' (Architecture, Urban Environment, Objects, Signs & symbols, Urban nature, Wind & Weather, Culture, Consumption, People community, Infrastructure, Memories & associations, atmosphere, Don't know), 'Show photos with reactions that use...' (One or more selected tags), 'Do people agree on their response?' (High agreement), and 'Search for some text' (Type a search query...). The main area shows a map of Copenhagen with numerous colored markers. On the right, there is a photo of a person taking a picture, with an 'Author's Annotation' section (Mentaly substation) and 'User Reactions (8)' section (All user segments).</p>

	<p>Map of image locations and routes walked with the UB App (left), and map of images shown as pie charts (right) to show distribution of annotations about what people notice in the image.</p>
Authorship	Aalborg University, Gehl community, The Visual Methodologies Collective, Center for digital welfare, Public Data Lab
Audience	Researchers, urban planners, citizen engagement professionals, community groups, policy-makers.
Date creation	March 2022
Date modified	Ongoing, tested in GREENGAGE (2025).
Latest updates	<p>"What is an inclusive city? Unpacking experiences of urban belonging among marginalized communities with digital geospatial photovoice" in Visual Studies (2023), by Sofie Burgos-Thorsen, Sabine Niederer, and Anders Koed Madsen.</p> <p>"The Urban Belonging Photo App: A toolkit for studying place attachments with digital and participatory methods", in Methodological Innovations (2023), by Anders Koed Madsen, Sofie Burgos-Thorsen, Carlo De Gaetano, Drude Ehn, Maarten Groen, Sabine Niederer, Kathrine Norsk, and Thorben Simonsen.</p> <p>"Crafting an Intersectional Gaze on Cities, and Three Other Reasons Why Urban Planning Needs Data Feminism", Arch Daily article by Sofie Burgos-Thorsen.</p> <p>Urban Belonging App code and documentation on GitHub</p> <p>"Urban Belonging Project - European Prize for Citizen Science" via Ars Electronica (2023): https://ars.electronica.art/citizenscience/en/urban-belonging-project/</p> <p>N/A</p>
Keywords	urban belonging, photovoice, participatory mapping, citizen science, inclusion, marginalized communities.
Category	Software (mobile application).

License	Private license (research project-specific).
Publisher	GREENGAGE Consortium / Gehl Architects.
Date published	2022 (Copenhagen project pilot).
Theme	Engagement, Participation, Inclusivity, Communication
Languages	Danish, English, Dutch, Italian.
Publications	<p>Resourced related to Urban Belonging Project</p> <p>"What is an inclusive city? Unpacking experiences of urban belonging among marginalized communities with digital geospatial photovoice" in Visual Studies (2023), by Sofie Burgos-Thorsen, Sabine Niederer, and Anders Koed Madsen.</p> <p>"The Urban Belonging Photo App: A toolkit for studying place attachments with digital and participatory methods", in Methodological Innovations (2023), by Anders Koed Madsen, Sofie Burgos-Thorsen, Carlo De Gaetano, Drude Ehn, Maarten Groen, Sabine Niederer, Kathrine Norsk, and Thorben Simonsen.</p> <p>"Crafting an Intersectional Gaze on Cities, and Three Other Reasons Why Urban Planning Needs Data Feminism", Arch Daily article by Sofie Burgos-Thorsen.</p> <p>Urban Belonging App code and documentation on GitHub</p> <p>"Urban Belonging Project - European Prize for Citizen Science" via Ars Electronica (2023): https://ars.electronica.art/citizenscience/en/urban-belonging-project/</p> <p>Inspiration & other resources</p> <p><i>Belonging: A Culture of Place</i>, af bell hooks (2009).</p> <p><i>Data Feminism</i>, af Catherine D'Ignazio og Lauren Klein (2020).</p> <p><i>Design Justice</i>, af Sasha Costanza-Chock (2020).</p> <p><i>Mutual Aid: Building Solidarity During This Crisis (and the Next)</i>, af Dean Spade (2020).</p> <p><i>"Urbino belonging: Exploring place-based community heritage with digital & participatory methods"</i>, International Journal of Heritage Studies artikel af Marco Pernarell and Anders Koed Madsen (2023).</p>
Nature	Research-driven participatory app
Problem profile	Urban belonging and inclusivity are often overlooked in city planning. The UB App tackles challenges of accessibility, trust, and representation in data collection by enabling marginalized communities to express lived experiences through photos, tags, and reactions.
Usage Examples	<p>Image Capturing and Annotation</p> <p>The UB App's fundamental feature is image capturing and annotation. This feature allows participants to take pictures and enrich them with relevant metadata. Here's how to use it:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Taking Pictures: Open the UB App and click on the camera icon. The prompt "Take a picture of a thing/place/situation in the city that you want to share" will appear. This open-ended prompt invites you to capture what matters to you in the city, whether it's a positive or negative experience. • Adding Metadata: After taking a picture, you'll be guided through two annotation interfaces:

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Sentiment Annotation: Use a 5-point slider to gauge the sentiment behind the image. This helps portray both positive and negative experiences. - Tagging Annotation: Select predefined tags that answer the question "why did you take this picture?" Tags cover various aspects of the urban experience. - Custom Tags: If the predefined tags are insufficient, you can create your own tag using the "Other" category. • Constraints: The UB App has constraints to ensure a level playing field among participants. You cannot apply filters to images or post-process them. All images are taken in a square format, and participants can only use images captured during the study timeframe. <p>Mapping Participants' Movements</p> <p>The app's ability to track participants' movements offers insights into their use of the city:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Movement Analysis: Use the dedicated output that includes walked routes and photo locations to understand how participants move between different areas of the city. • Place Making Practices: Analyse participants' routes to gain insight into their place-making practices and experiences of belonging. • Mobility and Urban Experience: Explore how participants' movement patterns reflect cultural and political aspects of mobility in the city. <p>Visualizing Reactions</p> <p>The data generated from the reaction phase provides opportunities to study how participants interpret and react to images:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Comparative Analysis: Use the CSV output to compare the annotations made by the image author with those made by reacting participants. • Relational Traces: Explore how participants perceive and interpret images differently, uncovering shared sentiments and contested perspectives. • Social Network Analysis: Use tools to study the participants as a social network, analysing how individuals with shared or differing sentiments interact.
<p>Documentation</p>	<p>The Urban Belonging App offers a robust platform for studying urban experiences from diverse angles. Its flexibility and open-source compatibility make it accessible for a wide range of research questions and analytical approaches. Through this tool, participants' perceptions and experiences of the city come to life, providing invaluable insights into urban belonging.</p> <p>The Urban Belonging (UB) App, developed and employed by the city of Copenhagen, plays a pivotal role in enabling participants to share their experiences of the city while creating a comprehensive and privacy-conscious data infrastructure. This section provides manuals on the capabilities of the UB App, what it offers, and how to use it.</p> <p>Granular Data through Geo-Tracking and Timestamping</p> <p>The UB App allows participants to choose between "snapshot mode" and "going for a walk." Here's how to navigate this feature:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Snapshot Mode: Choosing this mode enables the app to geolocate and timestamp the images captured. Participants can take individual pictures, and metadata is automatically collected about the time and place each image was taken.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Going for a Walk: Opting for this mode initiates continuous tracking of the participant's movements while taking pictures. A blue dot on a map in the app displays your current position. • Transparency: The app always seeks consent for tracking, making it clear when participants are being tracked and what data they are submitting. <p>Relational Data through Reaction Rounds The UB App fosters interaction among participants through "reaction rounds." Follow these steps:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Starting a Reaction Round: A participant can initiate a reaction round, which exposes them to 20 randomly selected images taken by other participants. • Annotation: React to these images using the same annotation methods you used for your images. • Repeat: Participants can request more batches of 20 images and continue reacting until they've engaged with all photos. • Collective Reflection: Reaction rounds are more than data collection. They encourage collective reflection and discussion. <p>Customizing the Toolkit via the Admin Dashboard Administrators can customize the UB toolkit using the admin dashboard. Here's how:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Access the Admin Dashboard: Log in as an administrator and open the dashboard in a browser. • Manage Projects: Create, edit, and manage projects, including translations, push notifications, member management, and data customization. • Create Groups: Create groups if you want to segment participants or apply different study timelines or questions. • Set up Study: Define start and end times for photo and reaction phases, questions, and preferences for each group.
Support	rasmus@miljopunkt-amager.dk
Complementarity / Interoperability	UB App data can be exported (JSON, CSV, PDF) and visualized using QGIS and open-source tools. Within GREENGAGE, it is being tested for participatory mapping and integration with the broader GREEN Engine
Open Standards & Protocols	Exports in JSON and CSV
APIs & Interfaces	N/A
Modularity & Extensibility	Admin dashboard allows configuration of projects, translations, timelines, groups
Metadata & Data Discovery	Each image contains metadata (location, timestamp, sentiment, tags)
Data Collection & Integration	<p>Data Outputs and Analytical Affordances The UB App offers a range of data outputs for analysis and exploration:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Raw Data: Export data in JSON format for versatile analysis.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Image Decks: Create PDF files that enable physical workshops and discussions among participants. • Visualizations: Utilize open-source software to visualize images and annotations, spatial patterns, and reactions for in-depth analysis. • Customized Datascape: Generate a datascape that allows participants to explore data visually and use metadata as filters. <p>The UB App and its associated data outputs offer a versatile platform for studying urban experiences, from individual sentiments to spatial patterns and community interactions.</p> <p>Use the UB App to gain valuable insights into how participants perceive and experience the city, fostering a deeper understanding of urban belonging.</p>
Visualization & Analysis	<p>Visualizing Images and Annotations</p> <p>The UB toolkit offers several methods to visualize images and their associated annotations:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CSV Output: This tabular file format allows for organized visualization of images based on their annotations. Images can be arranged in montages using software like ImageMagick. • Machine Learning Applications: Machine learning can be employed to order images by colour or other visual characteristics. Tools like t-SNE or UMAP models can be utilized for this purpose. • Physical Prompts: The UB project has developed physical prompts, such as printed image decks, to facilitate workshops and discussions among participants. <p>Visualizing Spatial Patterns</p> <p>The UB App provides geolocation data for each image, enabling the creation of visualizations that showcase the distribution of photos across the city:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • QGIS Software: Utilize open-source software like QGIS to visualize the geolocation of images. This can be done by importing the latitude and longitude data from the CSV output. • Heatmaps and Voronoi Plots: These visualization techniques can reveal density patterns between photo locations, shedding light on which areas are more frequently photographed.
Security & Privacy	GDPR-compliant, images anonymized (no filters, only square raw captures, tracking by consent)
Deployment model: Scalability & Performance	Mobile app for iOS and Android; scalable to multiple groups/projects
Social rating	Not available

5.2.3 DigiTwin used by North Brabant (Argaleo)

Name	DigiTwin: A Digital Twin for the City
URL	https://www.argaleo.com/en/DigiTwin/
Description / abstract	DigiTwin utilizes a cloud platform to amalgamate diverse datasets from various sources, enabling the visualization of static and real-time data for cities, regions, and the Netherlands as a whole. These datasets cover urban design, mobility, energy, and demography. Users can request access to specific or all datasets

	<p>to conduct multi-purpose analyses and 3D visualizations. The application is modular and customizable based on user needs. It primarily integrates reliable open-source datasets from governmental organizations like Netherlands' Cadaster, CBS, the Ministry of Infrastructure and Water Management, and municipalities. In the GREENGAGE project, GPS and questionnaire data from Citizen Observatories in North Brabant were integrated into DigiTwin for in-depth analysis of travel behaviour and its relation to socio-economic, demographic, land-use, and urban design factors.</p>
<p>Snapshots</p>	<p>Overview of building functions in an urban area</p>
<p>Authorship</p>	<p>Argaleo</p>
<p>Audience</p>	<p>Researchers & Academics; Policy and Decision Makers</p>
<p>Date creation</p>	<p>2020</p>
<p>Date modified</p>	<p>October 10th 2023</p>
<p>Latest updates</p>	<p>New Design: Dark/Light Mode Improved Controls Uncluttered Layout https://www.argaleo.com/en/2023/10/10/DigiTwinupdate/</p>
<p>Keywords</p>	<p>Digital Twin; Data Visualisation; Dataset; Mapping; Layers</p>
<p>Category</p>	<p>Interactive Resource</p>
<p>License</p>	<p>The DigiTwin is a commercial web-based portal that visualises data and aggregates datasets into separate shells. Access to such a shell requires a yearly license. The Pilot owners of the North Brabant Pilot already have such a license and can therefore focus on the data aggregation in the platform and its analysis.</p>
<p>Publisher</p>	<p>N/A</p>
<p>Date published</p>	<p>N/A</p>
<p>Theme</p>	<p>Engagement Evaluation of Citizen Science Communication Impact</p>

Languages	Dutch
DOI	N/A
Nature	DigiTwin Platform: Internal Software DigiTwin content: External data Interactions with the platform: External Knowledge
Problem profile	The DigiTwin is a data aggregation and visualisation technology. While it has several open source datasets integrated, it requires datasets gathered through other tools to be integrated. As such the profile focuses on the following activities: Data repository Data aggregation Data analysis (to some extent) Data Visualisation Discussion facilitator
Usage Examples	<p>Data Visualisation of Quantitative (GPS) Data</p> <p>As a data repository, DigiTwin allows for the visualization of CO gathered data, feeding analyses in co-creation processes, for instance when dealing with travel behaviour. Data gathering technologies like MODE can track the geospatial displacement of the citizen observers.</p> <p>These generated and gathered data and information will be integrated into the DigiTwin for further analyses and visualizations. This way, the actualised travel patterns and modality use can be superimposed on other data layers, like public transport catchment areas, or travel time optimisations.</p> <p>The DigiTwin serves as the main platform to combine the gathered data and info and existing reliable countrywide, regional, and city level datasets. It serves as a tool to analyse, together with citizens, their travel patterns, considerations and obstacles, by enriching the patterns with other layers of information. An example could be to overlay the biked routes with the public transport catchment areas: are there any unserved areas that would benefit from better bike infrastructure. Working in a dedicated shell, citizens can explore correlations around familiar infrastructure and co-create further improvements.</p> <p>Data Aggregator of Qualitative Data</p> <p>The DigiTwin can also serve as an aggregation of qualitative data. When analysing infrastructural and subjective safety for instance, photos and interview or survey answers related to geolocated areas can be gathered and mapped into the twin. Using DigiTwin's internal DataHub, photos can be mapped out and the network in the DigiTwin can be enhanced with geolocated data. These can subsequently be overlaid with different datasets, such as existing bike infrastructures, or incident reporting. This way, citizens can add concrete qualitative examples to existing quantitative datasets.</p> <p>Summary</p> <p>DigiTwin Visualises data and can be expanded with provided datasets. This tool can be used under the following circumstances</p> <p>Datasets have been gathered and curated that need to be visualised</p> <p>Geospatial datasets need to be correlated to other demographic, infrastructural, or built environment data</p> <p>An existing dataset needs to be enriched with qualitative data</p>

(The focus is on the Netherlands)

Documentation

An overview can be found here: <https://www.argaleo.com/en/DigiTwin/> An overview can be found here: <https://www.argaleo.com/en/digitwin/>

DigiTwin uses Environment Server (“Omgevingsserver” in Dutch) which is a cloud platform developed by Geo ICT experts. This modular web application contains different data sets from various sources to visualize the static and dynamic/real-time data for cities, regions and the whole Netherlands. Users, based on their needs and objectives, could link their data sets into available and integrated data sets, to perform specific analyses and customize their visualization by adding different layers of information.

With a license, you will receive access to a specific shell of the programme, communicated through a specific URL. Through your personal login, you can gain access to the environment, wherein there are several selectable options in the left drop-down menu. Here different forms of visualisation can be selected, as well as which datasets should be visualised. At times, specific datasets (relating to bike patterns for instance) can be selected, depending on their reach and timing.

The short explanations of process and main elements are as follows (SPOTinfo, 2020b):

Data sources: Environment Server is based on the spatial open data sources that the Dutch government currently offers. In addition to the system of basic registers, Environment Server uses various data sources such as the National Register of Childcare; CBS demographic data; the Risk map including the flood models; the Register of National Monuments; Spatial (zoning) plans (IMRO); the Energy Labels of homes; the Antenna Register; the Current Height Map. The DigiTwin can integrate geopackages and shapefile formats, as well as .csv, .geoTIFF, and .WFS files.

Data management: bring in the source data, enrich the data, and get it ready. To this end, the SPOTinfo solution periodically retrieves the current source data, and then combines and enriches that data. This 'data engine' is highly optimised for this data processing and is constantly being improved.

Data store: The resulting Environment Server data platform contains a large collection of datasets that cannot be found anywhere else in the Netherlands of this quality (topicality, reliability, completeness). As more (government) data

	<p>becomes available and other social themes become relevant, the Environment Server data platform reflects these developments.</p> <p><u>Data Services</u>: The managed data services ensure access to the data platform. Robust open-source techniques are used to make the data available in common ways. The following outputs are available:</p> <p><u>Map images</u>: as WMS (Web Map Service), WMTS (Web Map Tile Service), TMS (Tile Map Service), 3D vector tiles, 2D Open Layers.</p> <p><u>Datasets (tables with data)</u>: as WFS (Web Feature Service, OGC standard); via a REST API; and further (optional) in .OBJ format (for 3D objects), and in the future as CSV / Excel tables.</p> <p>OBJ export for e.g. 3D-printing and Virtual/augmented reality and gaming.</p> <p><u>Applications</u>: SPOTinfo offers with Environment Server its own 3D viewer in the browser based on Open-Source Map box technology. The OGC data services can also be used in common GIS viewers. Libraries such as Open Layers, Leaflet and Map box GL can also use the data.</p> <p>The DigiTwin is a data repository and data visualisation tool with some analysis capabilities. If datasets are gathered and curated, they can be visualised in the DigiTwin and compared to existing integrated datasets.</p> <p>COs can make use of this tool through the help of professional data curation by creating a visualisation of data patterns. The combination of different datasets can be used to identify causes, shortcomings, and fruitful directions. Thereby, the DigiTwin contributes to the signification of gathered data by COs.</p>
Support	<p>Questions regarding the platform itself can be directed at: support@argaleo.com</p> <p>Questions regarding the role of the platform in the project can be directed at: martens1.s@buas.nl</p>
Complementarity / Interoperability	<p>DigiTwin can support CO the co-production process in 3 main areas - (i) data integration and provision, (ii) data visualization (iii) data exploration and analysis.</p> <p>The main role of the DigiTwin is in Data Exploration and co-creation. The curation process, as well as the visualized analyses facilitate real life conversation with involved stakeholders – like CO members. Going through the process of exploiting the data for useful insights sets up the possibility for co-creation. This requires taking citizens through the process of data curation, and analysis, in order to enrich the quantitative visualized results with qualitative additions.</p> <p>Pre-combination</p> <p>The DigiTwin cannot gather data. Any tool that inputs large geomapped datasets, like MODE following travel pattern, can provide input for the DigiTwin.</p> <p>Post-Combination</p> <p>Given the visualisation and curation of specific datasets, further qualitative additions can be added to the map. Diving more in detail and gathering insight into the local level – like a route or a street – can enrich the sets in the DigiTwin. Here apps like the GREENGAGE’s app can come in handy or a MindEarth mission.</p>
Open Standards & Protocols	<p>Details on open standards and protocols used by DigiTwin are available at https://www.argaleo.com/en/DigiTwin/ .</p>
APIs & Interfaces	

	<p>Data Services: The managed data services ensure access to the data platform. Robust open-source techniques are used to make the data available in common ways. The following outputs are available:</p> <p>Map images: as WMS (Web Map Service), WMTS (Web Map Tile Service), TMS (Tile Map Service), 3D vector tiles, 2D Open Layers.</p> <p>Datasets (tables with data): as WFS (Web Feature Service, OGC standard); via a REST API; and further (optional) in .OBJ format (for 3D objects), and in the future as CSV / Excel tables.</p> <p>OBJ export for e.g. 3D-printing and Virtual/augmented reality and gaming.</p>
Modularity & Extensibility	In general, datasets are provided to Argaleo who will integrate it in the DigiTwin. Users themselves cannot add content directly, but can supply the required content.
Metadata & Data Discovery	There is a search function based on attributes of the specific datasets (such as looking for BUS will give you all the busstops). The metadata is related to function, location and infrastructure link. Generalised map search options are possible with specific attention to individual links.
Data Collection & Integration	The DigiTwin can integrate geopackages and shapefile formats, as well as .csv, geoTIFF, and .WFS files.
Visualization & Analysis	SPOTinfo offers with Environment Server its own 3D viewer in the browser based on Open-Source Map box technology. The OGC data services can also be used in common GIS viewers. Libraries such as Open Layers, Leaflet and Map box GL can also use the data.
Security & Privacy	The DigiTwin is not in charge of the data. GDPR regulations should be upheld by the data gathering parties Access is account-based, limiting users to those involved in the project.
Deployment model: Scalability & Performance	<p>The DigiTwin does not store any data. It creates a link to an external dataset through an API but does not require storage itself. It works with different shells that organise access to specific datasets. These shells are account based, thus allowing for a limited users at the same time.</p> <p>It is a web service, so there are no hardware specifications. However, a license is required.</p>
Social rating	N/A

5.3 Open-source tools adopted by GREENGAGE

5.3.1 Apache NiFi

Name	Apache NiFi
URL	https://nifi.apache.org
Description / abstract	<p>Apache NiFi is a powerful data integration tool that provides an intuitive user interface for designing data flows and automating data ingestion, transformation, and transfer processes. It excels in handling real-time data streaming and batch processing tasks. The following manuals provide comprehensive guidance on using Apache NiFi effectively within the GREENGAGE project. The detailed user manuals, developer manuals and other useful information can be found on official website of Apache NiFi - https://nifi.apache.org/.</p> <p>Example of a NiFi dataflow is shown in the figure below.</p>

Authorship	The Apache Software Foundation
Audience	Data engineers, integration/ETL teams, IoT & sensor data projects, platform/SRE teams, and research projects (e.g., GREENGAGE) that need secure, auditable, near-real-time data ingestion and routing.
Date creation	July 2015
Date modified	July 2025
Latest updates	2.5.0 (July 22, 2025): bug fixes, security updates, and improvements across the 2.x line (see release notes on download page)
Keywords	dataflow, ETL, streaming, MQTT, Kafka, REST, IoT, provenance, lineage, OIDC, clustering
Category	Software (open-source data integration / dataflow)
License	Apache License 2.0
Publisher	The Apache Software Foundation (ASF).
Date published	Open-sourced via NSA TTP in Nov 2014; Apache TLP in Jul 2015.
Theme	Analysis & Visualization for Insights Generation
Languages	English
DOI	-
Nature	External open-source software (production-grade)
Problem profile	NiFi tackles the “last-mile/first-mile” of data integration: reliably ingesting heterogeneous data (sensors, apps, APIs), transforming/harmonizing records, and delivering them to analytical stores or streams. All with back-pressure, prioritization, and full provenance for auditing and reproducibility. It solves

	common pain points such as brittle scripts, lack of lineage, ad-hoc security, and manual glue code.
Usage Examples	<p>This example demonstrates how to use Apache NiFi to ingest real-time data from IoT sensors, perform data transformations, and store the processed data in a database. It covers setting up data processors, configuring data flow, and monitoring the data pipeline for seamless data processing.</p> <p>By leveraging the capabilities of Apache NiFi, GREENGAGE project participants can efficiently manage data flows, ensuring the seamless integration and processing of diverse data sources. These manuals equip users with the knowledge and skills to harness the full potential of Apache NiFi within the context of urban mobility and sustainability initiatives.</p>
Documentation	<p>https://greengage-project.github.io/Documentation/tools/nifi/</p> <p>User Guide:</p> <p>This manual offers a detailed walkthrough of Apache NiFi's features and functionalities. It covers the basics of setting up data flows, configuring processors, and managing connections between data sources and destinations. Users will learn how to design efficient data pipelines to meet specific project requirements</p>
Support	contact@greengage-project.eu
Complementarity / Interoperability	GREENGAGE stack fit: NiFi as the ingest/ETL backbone, feeding Apache Druid (real-time analytics) and Apache Superset (dashboards). It also acts as a bridge from IoT sensors/MQTT, the GREENGAGE app (REST/GraphQL), and external open data portals, producing harmonized datasets for the toolbox.
Open Standards & Protocols	<p>AuthN/AuthZ: OpenID Connect (OIDC), OAuth2, Kerberos, LDAP; TLS/HTTPS. Apache NiFi</p> <p>Messaging/ingest: MQTT, AMQP/JMS, Kafka, HTTP/REST, SFTP/FTP. Apache NiFi</p> <p>Data: JSON, CSV, XML, Avro, Parquet; JDBC for relational stores. Apache NiFi</p> <p>Interop note: OGC services (WMS/WFS/WCS, SOS) can be consumed over HTTP via InvokeHTTP and parsed downstream (no native OGC processors required).</p>
APIs & Interfaces	<p>NiFi REST API: base path /nifi-api. Supports endpoints to list/update processors, process groups, templates/versioned flows, controller services, users/policies, provenance queries, etc. Auth via session or bearer token (OIDC). Docs: "NiFi REST API (latest)" and versioned API docs. Apache NiFi</p> <p>NiFi Registry API: manage flow versions/buckets, export/import flows for CI/CD. GitHub</p> <p>Site-to-Site: efficient NiFi <-> NiFi transport over raw or HTTP(S) for federated pipelines</p>
Modularity & Extensibility	<p>Extension model: Processors, Controller Services, Reporting Tasks packaged as NARs; develop custom Java (or Python for stateless) extensions. Apache NiFi+1</p> <p>Versioning: NiFi Registry for flow version control; promote flows across environments</p>
Metadata & Data Discovery	Data Provenance: every FlowFile change is captured; query by UUID, component, time window; interactive lineage graph for auditing & reproducibility

Data Collection & Integration	Sources: databases (JDBC), files (local/HDFS/S3), logs, APIs, message queues, IoT brokers. Transforms: Jolt, record readers/writers, Extract/Replace/Evaluate processors; schema evolution with record-aware processing.
Visualization & Analysis	Native UI for flow monitoring, back-pressure, provenance/lineage
Security & Privacy	Transport security: TLS (HTTPS) for UI, API, S2S; truststores/keystores. Authentication: OIDC (Authorization Code + PKCE, refresh tokens, RP-initiated logout), Kerberos SSO, LDAP, client certs. Apache NiFi Authorization: fine-grained, multi-tenant policies.
Deployment model: Scalability & Performance	Standalone or clustered (zero-leader design): horizontal scale with multiple nodes; ZooKeeper used in 1.x for coordination/state; Kubernetes operators available; 2.x continues cloud-native enhancements incl. stateless runtime options. Apache NiFi+2Apache NiFi+2docs.stackable.tech Kubernetes: community operators manage NiFi clusters (stateful) and stateless flows; integrate with cloud storage and secrets. docs.stackable.techGitHub
Social rating	N/A

Features of Apache NiFi

- **Data Provenance:** It tracks data provenance, recording a detailed history of data flowing through the system, which is key for auditing and understanding the lifecycle of the data.
- **Flow Management:** NiFi enables the management of data flows in real-time, allowing users to route, transform, and process data as it moves through the system.
- **Extensible Architecture:** NiFi can be extended with custom processors, services, and other components, making it adaptable to various data processing needs.
- **Scalability:** Designed to scale out across a cluster of servers to accommodate large volumes of data and high throughput requirements.
- **Flexible Scheduling:** Users can schedule when and how often data processors run, providing control over resource utilisation and timing of data flows.
- **Back Pressure and Prioritisation:** NiFi maintains system stability by applying back pressure and data prioritisation, ensuring smooth handling of data under load.
- **Visual Command and Control:** The visual command and control feature allows users to see exactly how data is flowing through their system in real-time. **Data Buffering:** NiFi buffers data between each processing step, ensuring that data is not lost in transit and can handle varying processing loads efficiently.
- **Record-Oriented Data Handling:** It supports record-oriented data handling, allowing for fine-grained data processing, which is particularly useful for complex and structured data types.
- **Integration with Diverse Systems:** NiFi integrates with a wide range of data sources and sinks, enabling interaction with numerous types of data systems and formats.

5.3.2 Apache Superset

Name	Apache Superset
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URL	https://superset.apache.org/
Description / abstract	Apache Superset (or Superset) is an open-source data visualization and data exploration platform designed for modern data teams. It empowers users to create and share interactive dashboards and engaging visualizations, offering a rich set of features to explore and understand large and complex datasets. Developed under the auspices of the Apache Software Foundation, Superset integrates effortlessly with most SQL-speaking databases, making it an incredibly versatile tool in the world of big data analytics.
Snapshots	<p>Example of Apache Superset dashboard</p>
Authorship	Apache Software Foundation (ASF)
Audience	Analysts, data/BI teams, public administrations, and projects requiring interactive dashboards without proprietary licences.
Date creation	June 2016
Date modified	June 2025
Latest updates	Jun 2025: 5.0.0 released (major UX + connectivity upgrades). Aug 2025: 6.0.0-rc1 tagged
Keywords	BI, dashboards, SQL, Druid, Postgres, BigQuery, RBAC, RLS, OpenAPI, OIDC
Category	Software (analytics / visualization platform)
License	Apache License 2.0
Publisher	Apache Software Foundation
Date published	Jan 2021
Theme	Analysis & Visualization for Insights Generation
Languages	English by default; i18n available (community translations e.g., Spanish, French, German, Chinese, Portuguese, etc.)
DOI	-
Nature	External open-source software
Problem profile	Superset addresses the need to rapidly turn heterogeneous SQL data into shareable, interactive insights - without locking into proprietary BI stacks. It centralizes metrics and calculated fields, supports row-level permissions, and scales with your existing databases/warehouses (no ingestion tier)
Usage Examples	<p>Air-quality monitoring dashboard (Druid + sensors)</p> <p>Connect to Druid: Settings → Database Connections → + Database → choose Apache Druid and supply the SQL endpoint (or Trino/Presto if used as a gateway). Test & Save. superset.apache.org</p>

	<p>Register dataset: Data → Datasets → + Dataset → pick the Druid table (e.g., aq_measurements).</p> <p>Semantic layer: open the dataset → add Metrics (e.g., avg_pm25, max_no2) and Calculated columns (e.g., quality bands). superset.apache.org</p> <p>Create charts in Explore:</p> <p>Time-series line (PM2.5 by hour; rolling 24h average).</p> <p>Deck.gl Scatter/Hex map using lat/long to visualize hotspots.</p> <p>Big Number for current AQI and Filter Box (sensor, pollutant, time).</p> <p>Assemble dashboard: Dashboards → +; drag charts; enable native filters & cross-filters.</p> <p>Access control: add a Row-Level Security rule so each pilot/city sees only their sensors. flask-appbuilder.readthedocs.io</p> <p>Performance: enable caching (Redis/Memcached) and async queries (Celery/Redis) for heavy charts.</p>
Documentation	<p>https://greengage-project.github.io/Documentation/tools/superset/</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Official Superset Documentation: The official documentation provides comprehensive guides on installation, configuration, usage, and advanced features. • Superset GitHub Repository: The GitHub repository contains the source code, issues, and contributions related to Apache Superset.
Support	<p>Slack: ASF Slack (#superset).</p> <p>Mailing list: dev@superset.apache.org (via lists.apache.org).</p> <p>GitHub: issues and discussions (apache/superset).</p>
Complementarity / Interoperability	<p>Upstream data: Superset reads directly from GREENGAGE stores (e.g., Apache Druid for sensor/time-series, Postgres for app/MODE data). Apache NiFi can ETL, standardize schemas, and land into those stores; Superset consumes without extra ingestion. Apache Lists</p> <p>Downstream sharing: dashboards can be embedded into web portals (e.g., WordPress), or shared read-only to communities.</p> <p>Auth continuity: align SSO via OIDC/OAuth/SAML/LDAP so users sign in once across tools</p>
Open Standards & Protocols	<p>AuthN/AuthZ: OpenID Connect / OAuth 2.0, SAML, LDAP, RBAC, RLS. flask-appbuilder.readthedocs.io</p> <p>APIs: REST with OpenAPI/Swagger schema. superset.apache.org</p> <p>Connectivity: SQL via SQLAlchemy dialects (DB-API ecosystem).</p>
APIs & Interfaces	<p>REST API (examples):</p> <p>Auth: POST /api/v1/security/login</p> <p>Charts: GET/POST /api/v1/chart</p> <p>Dashboards: GET/POST /api/v1/dashboard</p>

	Datasets: GET/POST /api/v1/dataset See the official API reference (Swagger UI) for parameters, auth and CSRF/token details.
Modularity & Extensibility	Visualization plugins (superset-ui), custom dashboards/themes, feature flags. Database drivers: add SQLAlchemy dialects to reach new engines. Security manager: customize authentication/authorization flows via Flask AppBuilder.
Metadata & Data Discovery	Datasets encapsulate columns, metrics, calculated columns and labeling; they power Explore and dashboards and help standardize business logic. The dataset model underpins Superset's semantic layer.
Data Collection & Integration	Superset does not collect data; it queries your databases/warehouses live. Supported sources are listed on the official site (Supported Databases). CSV/Excel upload can be enabled to seed tables in a connected database if your deployment allows it
Visualization & Analysis	40+ built-in chart types (time-series, tables, cohort, Sankey, geospatial deck.gl, etc.), interactive filters, cross-filters, drill-to-detail and Jinja templating for parameterized queries.
Security & Privacy	RBAC roles and Row-Level Security policies at dataset level; integrate with enterprise SSO (OIDC/OAuth, SAML, LDAP). Use HTTPS and network/database policies to safeguard data at rest/in transit.
Deployment model: Scalability & Performance	Single-node (Docker Compose) for pilots; Kubernetes (Helm) for HA. Caching layer accelerates dashboards; async queries via Celery + Redis prevent UI blocking. Superset leverages the scalability of your underlying databases/warehouses (no separate storage layer).
Social rating	-

Apache Superset is an open-source data exploration and visualization platform that enables users to create interactive dashboards and visualizations from various data sources. It offers a user-friendly interface for exploring and analysing data, making it a valuable tool for business intelligence and data analytics. Detailed manual documentation can be found at <https://superset.apache.org/docs/intro> which provides installation and configuration manuals, connection to databases documentation, creating charts and dashboards information, and other useful information.

Benefits and Use Cases:

- **Interactive Dashboards:** Superset allows users to create dynamic and interactive dashboards, providing real-time insights into data trends and patterns.
- **Diverse Data Source Integration:** It supports a wide range of data sources, including databases (SQLAlchemy, Presto, Druid), data warehouses (Amazon Redshift, Google BigQuery), and more.
- **Ad Hoc Data Exploration:** Users can perform ad hoc data exploration, allowing for on-the-fly analysis and visualization of data without predefined reports.
- **Collaborative Environment:** Superset enables multiple users to collaborate on dashboards and share insights, fostering teamwork and knowledge sharing.
- **Scheduled Reporting:** It offers the ability to schedule reports and dashboards, ensuring that stakeholders receive timely updates on key metrics.

User Guide:

A comprehensive [user manual](#), authored by the GREENGAGE development team, is available to the public. The document offers step-by-step instructions for installing the GREENGAGE tool, configuring

data sources, and tailoring system parameters to local pilot needs. It explains best practices for data quality assurance, provides examples of common workflows in urban-mobility scenarios, and includes troubleshooting guidance to minimise downtime. By following these guidelines, consortium members can deploy and maintain the tool confidently, ensuring consistent performance and full alignment with project requirements on sustainability and GDPR-compliant data handling.

5.3.3 Apache Druid

Name	Apache Druid
URL	https://druid.apache.org
Description / abstract	Apache Druid is an open-source, high-performance real-time analytics database designed for sub-second queries on streaming and batch data at scale. It combines column-oriented storage, automatic time-based partitioning, and an MPP architecture (Brokers, Historicals, MiddleManagers/Indexers, Coordinators, Routers) to deliver interactive OLAP on event data with high concurrency
Snapshots	<p>Example of data in Druid</p>
Authorship	Apache Software Foundation
Audience	Data platform engineers, analytics developers, SREs, BI/observability teams
Date creation	October 2012
Date modified	August 2025
Latest updates	August 2025 — v34.0.0 released (maintenance + many improvement)
Keywords	real-time analytics, OLAP, time-series, columnar store, streaming ingestion
Category	Software - real-time analytics database (open source)
License	Apache License 2.0
Publisher	Apache Software Foundation
Date published	August 2025
Theme	Analysis / Insight Generation / Data Infrastructure
Languages	English (doc(documentation & UI& UI)).
DOI	-
Nature	Open-source software (distributed database for analytics)
Problem profile	Interactive analytics on rapidly arriving streams plus historical data, at sub-second latencies and high concurrency.

	Efficient storage of time-series/events via columnar segments, time partitioning, and roll-up; scalable ingestion from streams/files.
Usage Examples	<p>Download data from Apache Druid</p> <p>Step 1: Go to query section</p> <p>Click on the QUERY button at the top menu.</p> <p>Step 4: Download the data</p> <p>Finally, at the right-most part of the screen, click on the down pointing arrow and download the data in the desired format.</p>

Documentation	https://druid.apache.org/docs/latest/design/
Support	<p>Users mailing list: users@druid.apache.org</p> <p>Developers mailing list: dev@druid.apache.org</p> <p>Issue tracking: GitHub issues on apache/druid.</p>
Complementarity / Interoperability	<p>Upstream ingestion & prep: Apache NiFi to fetch/clean data, publish to Kafka/Kinesis, then Druid supervisors ingest streams. druid.apache.org</p> <p>Catalog & governance: DataHub can catalog Druid datasources using Druid's SQL metadata and APIs for discovery. druid.apache.org</p> <p>Visualization: Apache Superset connects to Druid for interactive dashboards. Stack Overflow</p> <p>Downstream apps: Serve sub-second APIs for citizen-facing dashboards; integrate with Trino/Presto and other JDBC/ODBC tools via SQL.</p>
Open Standards & Protocols	<p>SQL (ANSI-like via Apache Calcite) exposed over HTTP & JDBC (Avatica). druid.apache.org</p> <p>HTTP/JSON for native queries and all admin operations; TLS supported. druid.apache.org+1</p> <p>Kafka/Kinesis streaming protocols for ingestion. druid.apache.org+1</p> <p>LDAP/LDAPS for auth; commonly integrated with OIDC via deployment tooling/proxies (e.g., Stackable).</p>
APIs & Interfaces	<p>SQL over HTTP: POST <code>/druid/v2/sql</code> — submit SQL queries. druid.apache.org</p> <p>Native JSON Query API: POST <code>/druid/v2/</code> — timeseries, groupBy, topN, scan, etc. druid.apache.org</p> <p>Tasks API: manage ingestion tasks (<code>/druid/indexer/v1/task</code>); Supervisor API: manage streaming supervisors. druid.apache.org</p> <p>Data management/retention/compaction/lookups/dynamic config endpoints — see API index. druid.apache.org</p> <p>JDBC: Apache Avatica driver for BI tools and apps.</p>
Modularity & Extensibility	<p>Druid has a pluggable extensions system: add deep storage (S3/HDFS/GCS/Azure), metadata stores (MySQL/PostgreSQL), new input formats, and aggregator</p>

Metadata & Data Discovery	<p>Query metadata via INFORMATION_SCHEMA and sys tables (columns, tables, segments, tasks, servers).</p> <p>Browse and manage datasources/segments in the web console (timeline, compaction, rules).</p> <p>Programmatic access via the API</p>
Data Collection & Integration	<p>Streaming: Kafka, Kinesis supervisors (exactly-once).</p> <p>Batch: Load from HDFS/S3/GCS/Azure/local.</p> <p>Formats: JSON, CSV/TSV, Parquet, ORC, Avro, Protobuf (via extensions where applicable).</p>
Visualization & Analysis	<p>Use Druid SQL for aggregations, joins, and metadata queries; native JSON for specialized patterns.</p> <p>Web console includes a SQL/native query workbench; most dashboards are built in tools like Superset.</p> <p>Approximate analytics (distincts, quantiles, set ops) via DataSketches for fast insights at scale.</p>
Security & Privacy	<p>Authentication/Authorization: Basic auth + RBAC, or LDAP/LDAPS; map groups to roles & permissions.</p> <p>Transport security: TLS recommended; follow least-privilege, rotate secrets, restrict endpoints.</p> <p>Compliance: Druid provides the technical controls; data controllers must implement GDPR/PII processes on top.</p>
Deployment model: Scalability & Performance	<p>Scale-out MPP architecture with independent roles; add Brokers for concurrency, Historicals for capacity, Indexers for ingestion throughput.</p> <p>Streaming elasticity by scaling indexing tasks/supervisors; compaction to optimize segment size and query speed.</p> <p>Runs on bare metal, VMs, Kubernetes, or cloud; deep storage on S3/GCS/Azure/HDFS. Follow AWS solution guidance for TLS and autoscaling patterns as needed.</p>
Social rating	N/A

Apache Druid is an open-source data store designed for real-time analytics on large datasets. It provides fast query response times and is optimized for sub-second querying. Druid is commonly used to power interactive dashboards and real-time analytics applications.

Documentation:

- [Official Documentation](#): The primary resource for learning about and working with Apache Druid is the official documentation. It covers a wide range of topics including installation, configuration, data ingestion, querying, and advanced features.
- [Druid GitHub Repository](#): The GitHub repository contains the source code, issues, and contributions related to Apache Druid.

Benefits:

- **Real-Time Analytics**: Apache Druid is well-suited for applications that require real-time analytics, where users need to query and visualize data with minimal latency.
- **Interactive Dashboards**: It powers interactive dashboards that allow users to explore and analyse data dynamically.
- **Event Monitoring**: Druid is commonly used for monitoring events, such as tracking user behaviour on a website or app in real-time.

- IoT Data Processing: It can handle large volumes of data generated by Internet of Things (IoT) devices in real-time.

User Guide:

The development team has also put together a hands-on [guide](#) for Apache Druid that focuses on speed, scalability, and day-to-day operations. Starting with a cookbook-style walkthrough for launching a small test cluster, the manual then details ingestion specs, roll-up strategies, and segment compaction so partners can keep storage footprints lean without sacrificing query latency. Clear diagrams illustrate how historical and real-time nodes cooperate, while annotated examples of the JSON query API help users craft sub-second interactive analytics on live mobility feeds. Practical checklists—for capacity planning, tiering, backup, and graceful upgrades—round out the document, giving GREENGAGE teams the confidence to run Druid in production and to expand seamlessly as data volumes grow.

By leveraging Apache Druid's capabilities, organizations can process and analyse large volumes of data in real-time, enabling timely decision-making and the creation of interactive data-driven applications. Explore the extensive documentation and engage with the Druid community for further insights and best practices.

5.3.4 Kepler.gl

Name	Kepler.gl
URL	https://kepler.gl/
Description / abstract	<p>Kepler.gl is an open-source geospatial data visualization tool, developed for intuitive and interactive exploration of location-based datasets. It enables the creation of multi-layered maps directly in the browser without coding skills. Within GREENGAGE, it was introduced as an additional visualization tool during datathons to present mobility and air quality data.</p> <p>Its role is complementary: it allows pilots and citizen observers to quickly visualize Copernicus datasets, air quality indicators, and mobility patterns in participatory settings, before more structured workflows in UrbanTEP/VISAT are ready.</p>
Snapshots	
Authorship	Uber Visualization Team
Audience	Researchers, urban planners, policy makers, and citizen observers
Date creation	Not specified
Date modified	Not specified

Latest updates	Depends on community
Keywords	open source, geospatial visualization, interactive maps, citizen science, Copernicus data
Category	Open-source software
License	MIT
Publisher	Uber Visualization Team
Date published	Not specified
Theme	Visualization and Analysis
Languages	English (tool interface)
DOI	Not available
Nature	Open-source visualization software
Problem profile	Some GREENGAGE pilots needed a quick, user-friendly way to visualize mobility and environmental data when other integrated tools (like VISAT/UrbanTEP) were still in development. Kepler.gl addressed this by enabling immediate map-based visualization of diverse geospatial datasets
Usage Examples	<p>During the Turano Valley datathon, Kepler.gl was used to visualize Copernicus Air Quality and Land Cover data directly with citizens.</p> <p>MindEarth used it to present mobility dynamics data, engaging participants in co-creation workshops.</p> <p>The interface allowed multi-layer maps showing relationships between air quality, land use, and mobility patterns.</p> <p>Citizens and stakeholders could interactively filter and explore geospatial layers without complex software installation</p>
Documentation	Official documentation is available on the Kepler.gl website .
Support	Community support via GitHub and Kepler.gl documentation
Complementarity / Interoperability	Kepler.gl complements VISAT/UrbanTEP and Superset. While Superset supports general dashboards and VISAT integrates storytelling, Kepler.gl provides rapid standalone visualizations of geospatial datasets. It is built on DeckGL, the same framework used in VISAT's frontend, ensuring visual consistency.
Open Standards & Protocols	Supports common open geospatial formats: CSV, GeoJSON.
APIs & Interfaces	<p>Browser-based GUI for visualization.</p> <p>No GREENGAGE-specific API integration described</p>
Modularity & Extensibility	As open-source, Kepler.gl can be extended or embedded in other platforms. Within GREENGAGE, it was used as-is for visualizations
Metadata & Data Discovery	Via web interface supported
Data Collection & Integration	Not relevant

Visualization & Analysis	Interactive, multi-layered maps. Enables filtering, layering, and exploration of large-scale geospatial datasets. Used for participatory exploration of environmental and mobility data
Security & Privacy	N/A
Deployment model: Scalability & Performance	Kepler.gl runs in-browser, scalable for datasets manageable on client-side machines. Not server-based within GREENGAGE
Social rating	Not available.

Kepler.gl is an open-source geospatial data visualization tool developed by Uber. It enables users to create interactive and customizable maps to visualize and analyse location-based data.

Manuals:

- **Official Documentation:** The primary resource for learning about and working with Kepler.gl is the official documentation. It covers topics such as data ingestion, map customization, and visualization techniques.
- **GitHub Repository:** The GitHub repository contains the source code and additional resources for developers looking to customize or extend Kepler.gl.
- **Community Forum:** The Kepler.gl community forum is a platform for asking questions, sharing experiences, and seeking assistance from other Kepler.gl users.

Use Cases:

- **Spatial Analysis:** Kepler.gl is used for performing spatial analysis on various datasets, helping users gain insights into location-based patterns and trends.
- **Data Exploration:** It enables users to explore geospatial datasets interactively, allowing for the discovery of hidden insights within the data.
- **Storytelling with Maps:** Kepler.gl is a powerful tool for creating compelling visual narratives using location-based data.
- **Data Sharing:** It facilitates the sharing of geospatial visualizations and analyses with stakeholders and the wider public.

Getting Started:

- **Data Ingestion:** Learn how to import different types of geospatial data (CSV, GeoJSON, etc.) into Kepler.gl for visualization and analysis.
- **Map Customization:** Understand how to customize the appearance of the map, including layer styling, colour schemes, and map legends.
- **Filtering and Aggregation:** Explore techniques for filtering data and performing aggregations to focus on specific aspects of the dataset.
- **Interactivity and Tooltips:** Discover how to add interactivity to maps, including tooltips and pop-ups to provide additional information about map features.

Best Practices:

- **Data Preparation:** Ensure that geospatial data is properly cleaned and formatted before importing it into Kepler.gl for visualization.
- **Layer Organization:** Organize map layers logically to make it easier for users to understand the relationships between different elements on the map.
- **Colour Palette Selection:** Choose a suitable colour palette that enhances the visualization and effectively communicates the information.

Kepler.gl empowers users to create stunning and informative geospatial visualizations. By leveraging the extensive documentation and community resources, users can maximize the utility of Kepler.gl for their specific geospatial data analysis and visualization needs.

5.3.5 DataHub

Name	Datahub
URL	https://datahub.com
Description / abstract	DataHub is an open-source metadata platform (data catalog) for data discovery, lineage, governance, and observability across the modern data stack. It stores a richly-typed “metadata graph” and exposes it via a UI plus GraphQL, REST.li, and SDKs so teams can search assets, understand lineage, assign ownership, apply glossary terms/tags, and automate governance
Snapshots	<p>The diagram illustrates the DataHub ecosystem. On the left, 'Source Systems' (represented by icons for Snowflake, Databricks, and others) connect to the central 'DataHub Metadata Platform' via 'Push + Pull' mechanisms. The platform features a 'Metadata Explorer' UI. On the right, the platform connects to 'API & Stream Integrations' (including GraphQL, REST, Kafka) and other services like 'Alerts' and 'Users'.</p> <p>Datahub ecosystem</p>
Authorship	DataHub Project (community)
Audience	Data platform teams, data engineers, analytics engineers, data stewards/governance, BI developers, and domain owners
Date creation	August 2019
Date modified	August 2025
Latest updates	v1.2.0.1 (Aug 2025): patch for Schema Registry integration
Keywords	data catalog, metadata, lineage, governance, glossary, tags, domains, search, GraphQL, REST.li, Kafka, Elasticsearch/OpenSearch
Category	Software (open-source platform)
License	Apache License 2.0
Publisher	DataHub Project
Date published	August 2019 (initial public announcement)
Theme	Data Management & Discovery (Evaluation/Communication/Governance)
Languages	English (UI & docs).
DOI	--
Nature	Open-source software / deployable platform (self-hosted or managed).
Problem profile	Solves data discovery across fragmented systems; provides trust & context (owners, docs, quality); impact analysis via lineage; policy-driven governance with roles & fine-grained access; and unifies metadata from warehouses, BI, pipelines, and ML tools.
Usage Examples	Data Discovery and Search

You can search for any asset located in DataHub using the search bar located on the main page or at the top of any other page within DataHub. The search bar, as shown in the figure below, enables users to quickly find relevant datasets, metrics, and dashboards.

Metadata Management

DataHub offers comprehensive metadata management capabilities. It aggregates and manages metadata from a variety of data sources, maintaining details about datasets, schemas, data lineage, and ownership. This feature is illustrated in the Metadata Management interface, providing a clear overview of all metadata assets.

Data Lineage and Governance

DataHub visualises data lineage, showing how data flows through various systems. This feature is crucial for understanding the transformation and lifecycle of data, aiding in governance and compliance. The Data Lineage interface provides a graphical representation of these data flows.

Documentation	https://docs.datahub.com/docs/
Support	Community: Slack & forum (how-to, troubleshooting), GitHub issues;
Complementarity / Interoperability	<p>Apache Druid — catalog Druid sources for discovery and lineage.</p> <p>Apache Superset — ingest Superset dashboards & charts; show lineage to upstream datasets.</p> <p>Apache NiFi — register NiFi-produced datasets via CLI/SDK or custom source; use Actions to propagate terms/tags as flows publish datasets.</p> <p>Sensors/Apps — onboard warehouse/lake tables receiving sensor/app data; assign domains & ownership to improve governance and reuse.</p>
Open Standards & Protocols	GraphQL for querying the metadata graph; REST.li for CRUD of metadata aspects; OpenAPI references for REST; OpenID Connect/OAuth 2.0 for SSO; core infra relies on open projects (Kafka, Elasticsearch/OpenSearch, MySQL).
APIs & Interfaces	GraphQL at /api/graphql (queries/mutations); REST.li endpoints (e.g., /gms/..., /restli/docs); Python & Java SDKs; Ingestion via REST or Kafka sinks. Auth via tokens/SSO. Include endpoints and examples in docs and forum
Modularity & Extensibility	Pluggable ingestion sources (dbt, Snowflake, BigQuery, Redshift, Postgres, Druid, Superset, Kafka, etc.), sinks (REST/Kafka), Actions framework

	(automations like term propagation), and extensible GraphQL schema/REST.li aspects
Metadata & Data Discovery	Global search with filters, result ranking, domains, tags; asset profile pages (schema, owners, docs, usage); glossary terms; institutional memory links; analytics of catalog usage. Programmatic search via SDK.
Data Collection & Integration	DataHub catalogs metadata (not raw payloads). It connects to sources and BI tools to ingest schemas, lineage, dashboards, owners, and usage via UI/CLI/SDK recipes (YAML/JSON).
Visualization & Analysis	Built-in: search result views, dataset profiles, lineage graphs, impact analysis, and analytics pages. It's not a BI tool but links to BI (e.g., Superset) and shows lineage to them.
Security & Privacy	Roles (Admin/Editor/Reader) and fine-grained Access Policies (platform & metadata policies) for who can view/edit specific entities & aspects. Supports SSO (OIDC/OAuth), token auth, and PII classification/tagging automations.
Deployment model: Scalability & Performance	Local/dev: Docker Compose (2 vCPU/8 GB+). Prod: Helm on Kubernetes; scale Elasticsearch/OpenSearch, Kafka/MSK, and MySQL/RDS; AWS blueprint recommends 3+ nodes for running the storage layer in-cluster (or use managed services)
Social rating	

DataHub is an open-source metadata management tool developed by LinkedIn. It provides a platform for discovering, documenting, and sharing datasets within an organization, making it easier for data professionals to collaborate and leverage available data resources.

Manuals:

- Official Documentation: The primary resource for learning about and working with DataHub is the official documentation. It covers topics such as setting up DataHub, using its features, and best practices for metadata management.
- GitHub Repository: The GitHub repository contains the source code and additional resources for developers looking to customize or extend DataHub.
- Community Forum: The DataHub community forum is a platform for asking questions, sharing experiences, and seeking assistance from other DataHub users.

Use Cases:

- Dataset Discovery: DataHub is used to search and discover datasets available within an organization, promoting data reuse and collaboration.
- Metadata Management: It allows users to document and manage metadata associated with datasets, providing context and lineage information.
- Data Governance: DataHub supports data governance efforts by enabling the establishment of policies, data stewardship, and compliance monitoring.
- Data Lineage and Impact Analysis: Users can trace the lineage of datasets, understanding how data flows through the organization and assessing the impact of changes.

Getting Started:

- Setting Up DataHub: Follow the instructions provided in the official documentation to install and configure DataHub within your organization.
- Registering Datasets: Learn how to register new datasets in DataHub, including adding metadata, descriptions, and establishing relationships.
- Searching for Datasets: Understand how to use DataHub's search and filtering capabilities to discover relevant datasets based on various criteria.

- Managing Metadata: Explore the features for documenting and managing metadata, including tags, labels, and data quality information.

Best Practices:

- Consistent Metadata Standards: Establish and enforce consistent metadata standards to ensure that information is uniformly documented across all datasets.
- Regularly Update Metadata: Encourage data owners and stewards to regularly update metadata to reflect any changes or updates to the underlying datasets.
- Collaborative Documentation: Foster a culture of collaboration by allowing multiple stakeholders to contribute to dataset documentation and metadata management.

DataHub plays a crucial role in enabling effective data collaboration and management within organizations. By leveraging the extensive documentation and community resources, users can maximize the benefits of DataHub for their specific metadata management and dataset discovery needs.

5.3.6 KeyCloak

Name	Keycloak
URL	https://www.keycloak.org
Description / abstract	Keycloak is an open-source Identity and Access Management (IAM) server that provides Single Sign-On (SSO), identity brokering, user federation, and fine-grained authorization. It implements open standards including OpenID Connect (OIDC), OAuth 2.0, SAML 2.0, and WebAuthn/Passkeys
Snapshots	<p>The screenshot shows the Keycloak Admin Console interface. On the left is a navigation sidebar with options like 'Realms', 'Clients', 'Users', etc. The main content area shows the configuration for a realm named 'greengage'. Fields include 'Name' (greengage), 'Display name', 'HTML Display name', 'Frontend URL', 'Enabled' (checkbox), 'User-Managed Access' (checkbox), and 'Endpoints' (OpenID Endpoint Configuration, SAML 2.0 Identity Provider Metadata). 'Save' and 'Cancel' buttons are at the bottom.</p>
	Admin's dashboard in Keycloak
Authorship	Keycloak Community (CNCF incubation)
Audience	Platform/IAM engineers, security teams, SRE/DevOps, app developers needing SSO & identity federation
Date creation	September 2014
Date modified	August 2025
Latest updates	August 2025 – 26.3.0/26.3.3: recovery codes for 2FA, simplified WebAuthn/Passkeys registration
Keywords	IAM, SSO, OpenID Connect, OAuth 2.0, SAML 2.0
Category	Software (server / platform)
License	Apache License 2.0
Publisher	Keycloak Project (CNCF incubation)
Date published	September 2014

Theme	Security / Authentication & Authorization / Interoperability
Languages	English (docs); UI supports theming and i18n.
DOI	-
Nature	Open-source server software (self-hosted or containerized)
Problem profile	Centralizes authentication and authorization across many apps/services; enables SSO; supports heterogeneous identity providers (OIDC/SAML/social), LDAP/AD federation, multi-factor auth (including WebAuthn/Passkeys), and fine-grained access control—reducing custom auth code and improving security, UX, and compliance.
Usage Examples	<p>Create a Realm and a Client (OpenID Connect)</p> <p>Create a New Realm:</p> <p>Navigate to Clients and click Create.</p> <p>Provide a Client ID, and select the Client Protocol as openid-connect.</p> <p>Select the Client Access Type as confidential if your client is a web application that can secure the client secret. Otherwise, select public if your client is a native app or a JavaScript app running in the browser.</p>

Set Standard Flow Enabled to ON if you want to use the Authorization Code Flow which is recommended for most scenarios.

Configure OpenID Connect Protocol:

For each client, you can tailor what claims and assertions are stored in the OIDC token by creating and configuring protocol mappers.

You may need to set up JSON mapping for certain claim keys in your application to handle roles or other claims passed by Keycloak.

Client Adapters:

Install a Keycloak Adapter in your application environment to communicate and be secured by Keycloak. Keycloak provides adapters for different platforms, and there are also third-party adapters available.

Test Your Setup:

At this point, it would be prudent to test your setup by attempting to authenticate using OpenID Connect. There are various grant types supported by Keycloak for authenticating users including authorization code, implicit, and client credentials.

Additional Configuration (Optional):

The screenshot shows the Keycloak Admin Console interface for configuring a client. The 'Clients' page is open, and the 'Settings' tab is selected. The configuration includes fields for Client ID, Name, Description, and Login Theme. Several toggle switches are visible: 'Enabled' (ON), 'Always Display in Console' (OFF), 'Consent Required' (OFF), 'Standard Flow Enabled' (ON), 'Implicit Flow Enabled' (OFF), 'Direct Access Grants Enabled' (ON), and 'OAuth 2.0 Device Authorization Grant Enabled' (OFF). There are also dropdown menus for 'Client Protocol' (set to 'openid-connect') and 'Access Type' (set to 'public'). A 'Root URL' field and a 'Valid Redirect URIs' field are also present.

Depending on your application's requirements, you might need to configure additional settings in Keycloak or in your application. For instance, you might need to set up user roles, groups, and permissions, or configure multi-factor authentication.

Documentations and Tutorials:

There are various resources available that provide step-by-step guides or tutorials on integrating OpenID Connect with Keycloak, including the Keycloak official documentation.

This extended step should provide a more thorough understanding of how to integrate OpenID Connect with Keycloak

Documentation	https://www.keycloak.org/documentation
Support	CNCF Slack (#keycloak), Discourse forum, GitHub Discussions/Issues; mailing list links from the Community page.
Complementarity / Interoperability	Upstream/inbound: federates with OIDC/SAML IdPs (e.g., government eID, corporate IdPs, Google/GitHub), or with LDAP/Active Directory user stores. Downstream/outbound: secures apps/APIs via OIDC/OAuth2 or SAML; issues JWTs used by API gateways, service meshes, and dashboards; provides claims for BI tools. Ops: integrates with Prometheus metrics, Kubernetes Operators, external DBs (PostgreSQL/Aurora), Infinispan for clustering.
Open Standards & Protocols	OIDC (Discovery /.well-known/openid-configuration, auth, token, userinfo, logout, JWKS), OAuth 2.0 (incl. token introspection; optional OAuth 2.1 profiles), SAML 2.0, WebAuthn/Passkeys, JWT/JWS/JWE/JWK. Brokering with generic OAuth 2.0 providers (26.3).
APIs & Interfaces	Admin REST API (/admin/realms/...) for full administration (OpenAPI links). OIDC endpoints: Authorization, Token, UserInfo, Logout, Introspection, JWKS; auto-discoverable via .well-known. Identity Brokering imports provider metadata; JWKS used for key discovery.
Modularity & Extensibility	Pluggable SPIs for custom authenticators, user storage, event listeners, protocols; themes for login/admin/account UIs.
Metadata & Data Discovery	Publishes OpenID Provider Metadata for clients via /.well-known/openid-configuration, enabling automatic client configuration. User attributes and role mappings become claims in tokens for downstream services.
Data Collection & Integration	Acts as IdP: collects/authenticates user credentials and factors, federates from LDAP/AD and external IdPs; issues standards-based tokens (JWT) consumable by apps, APIs, and dashboards.
Visualization & Analysis	Not a BI tool, but exposes Admin Console dashboards (events, sessions) and metrics for Prometheus via Micrometer (from recent releases) for external observability stacks.
Security & Privacy	TLS in transit; signed/encrypted tokens; MFA including WebAuthn/Passkeys; password hashing defaults aligned to OWASP; fine-grained admin permissions; rotates realm keys via JWKS. Compliance support depends on deployment (e.g., GDPR).
Deployment model: Scalability & Performance	Container images and Kubernetes Operator for install/upgrade; HA blueprints with multi-site designs, Aurora/PostgreSQL backing DB, and Infinispan caches; rolling updates (patch stream) supported. Size CPU/memory per guide.
Social rating	

KeyCloak is an open-source identity and access management solution developed by Red Hat. It provides features for secure user authentication, authorization, and identity federation, making it a powerful tool for managing user access to applications and services.

Manuals:

- **Official Documentation:** The official documentation provides comprehensive guides on setting up, configuring, and using KeyCloak for various identity and access management scenarios.
- **GitHub Repository:** The GitHub repository contains the source code and resources for developers interested in customizing or extending KeyCloak.

- **Community Forum:** The KeyCloak community forum is a platform for discussions, questions, and sharing experiences among KeyCloak users and developers.

Use Cases:

- **Single Sign-On (SSO):** KeyCloak enables SSO, allowing users to log in once and access multiple applications without the need for separate logins.
- **User Authentication:** It provides a secure and customizable authentication process, supporting various authentication mechanisms, including username/password, social logins, and multi-factor authentication.
- **Authorization and Permissions:** KeyCloak offers fine-grained access control, allowing administrators to define roles, groups, and permissions for users and applications.
- **Identity Federation:** KeyCloak supports identity federation, allowing users to log in using credentials from external identity providers like LDAP, Active Directory, or social identity providers.

Getting Started:

- **Installation and Setup:** Follow the instructions provided in the official documentation to install and set up KeyCloak in your environment.
- **Realm Configuration:** Learn how to create and configure realms, which serve as security domains where applications and users are managed.
- **User Management:** Understand how to create and manage users, define roles, and assign permissions within KeyCloak.
- **Client Configuration:** Configure applications (clients) to integrate with KeyCloak for secure authentication and authorization.

Best Practices:

- **Regular Updates:** Keep KeyCloak updated to the latest version to benefit from security patches and new features.
- **Secure Configuration:** Implement recommended security practices, such as using HTTPS, strong passwords, and encryption, to protect user credentials and data.
- **Role-Based Access Control (RBAC):** Use RBAC to manage permissions and access control in a structured and organized manner.

KeyCloak serves as a robust solution for managing user identities and access control in applications and services. By referring to the official documentation and engaging with the community, users can effectively implement KeyCloak for their specific identity and access management requirements.

5.3.7 Zenodo

Name	Zenodo
URL	https://zenodo.org/communities/greengage
Description / abstract	<p>Zenodo is an open-access repository supported by CERN and OpenAIRE. Within GREENGAGE, it has been adopted as the primary platform for hosting and disseminating datasets and deliverables. It ensures that outputs from Citizen Observatories (COs) are preserved, citable, and aligned with FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable).</p> <p>The GREENGAGE Zenodo community provides a centralized hub where datasets, anonymized survey data, photos, air quality measurements, and project publications are openly accessible to researchers, policymakers, and the public</p>

Snapshots	
Authorship	OpenAIRE Consortium, CERN
Audience	Researchers, policymakers, citizen scientists, wider public
Date creation	N/A
Date modified	N/A
Latest updates	GREENGAGE datasets and deliverables published progressively (ongoing during project lifetime)
Keywords	open access, repository, FAIR data, datasets, publications
Category	Open-source repository / service
License	Open-access repository (licenses are dataset-dependent)
Publisher	OpenAIRE Consortium, CERN, GREENGAGE Consortium
Date published	N/A
Theme	Dissemination, Transparency, Data Sharing
Languages	English
DOI	Yes – DOI assignment per dataset/publication
Nature	Open-access repository
Problem profile	Citizen Observatory outputs need transparent publication and long-term preservation. Zenodo addresses this by providing open access to datasets, metadata, and publications, ensuring reproducibility and public trust
Usage Examples	<p>Uploading datasets from Citizen Observatories (e.g., Atmotube sensor data, anonymized participant demographics).</p> <p>Publishing GREENGAGE deliverables and research papers with DOI assignment.</p> <p>Organizing datasets by theme (air quality, mobility, biodiversity).</p> <p>Providing citable references for policymakers and researchers to reuse project outputs</p>
Documentation	Deliverable 4.9 refers to Zenodo as the repository for GREENGAGE. Full manuals are external: Zenodo Help Documentation (account setup, upload, metadata, licensing).
Support	<p>Zenodo Helpdesk: https://help.zenodo.org</p> <p>GREENGAGE contact: contact@greengage-project.eu</p>

Complementarity / Interoperability	Zenodo integrates with the GREEN Engine data pipeline. Data from apps (GREENGAGE app, Atmotube, MindEarth) can be curated and then published. Metadata schema aligns with GREENGAGE internal cataloguing. Supports versioning and thematic grouping.
Open Standards & Protocols	DOI for dataset identification. FAIR principles for interoperability. Metadata aligned with OpenAIRE standards
APIs & Interfaces	Zenodo REST API available
Modularity & Extensibility	Datasets grouped into GREENGAGE community; supports thematic organization by campaign, pilot, or domain
Metadata & Data Discovery	Metadata-based search and thematic grouping. GREENGAGE datasets discoverable by campaign, pilot, or theme
Data Collection & Integration	Zenodo does not collect data; it ingests curated datasets from GREENGAGE tools
Visualization & Analysis	Users can preview uploaded documents via web GUI
Security & Privacy	Operated by CERN and OpenAIRE; GDPR compliant. Sensitive datasets anonymized before upload
Deployment model: Scalability & Performance	Cloud-based open-access repository, scalable to large datasets
Social rating	Not available

Zenodo is an open-access repository developed by CERN for sharing research outputs across all fields of science. It enables researchers to upload, share, and preserve publications, datasets, software, and other research materials, ensuring long-term accessibility and citation.

Manuals

- **Official Documentation:** Zenodo's official documentation (<https://help.zenodo.org/docs/>) provides step-by-step guides on creating an account, uploading research outputs, managing metadata, and understanding licensing and DOI assignment.
- **GitHub Repository:** The Zenodo GitHub repository (<https://github.com/zenodo/zenodo-rdm>) contains the platform's source code, issue tracker, and resources for developers interested in contributing to or deploying Zenodo.
- **Community Support:** Zenodo offers a helpdesk, user forum, and FAQ section where users can find answers, share experiences, and seek assistance from the community and support team.

Use Cases

- **Research Data Sharing:** Zenodo allows researchers to deposit datasets, making them accessible and citable for the broader scientific community.
- **Software Archiving:** Developers can archive software releases, ensuring reproducibility and providing DOIs for citation in academic publications.
- **Publication Hosting:** Zenodo supports the upload of preprints, reports, and other scholarly works, facilitating open access and compliance with funder mandates.

Getting Started

- **Account Registration:** Follow the official documentation to create a Zenodo account and set up your profile.

- **Uploading Content:** Learn how to upload files, enter metadata, select licenses, and publish your research outputs.
- **Managing Records:** Understand how to edit, update, or delete records, and how to manage versioning for datasets and software.
- **Citing and Sharing:** Discover how to generate citations, share DOIs, and integrate Zenodo records with ORCID and other research profiles.

AWAITING VALIDATION BY THE EUROPEAN COMMISSION

6 GREEN Engine's product specification

The GREEN Engine is a comprehensive system composed of diverse tools organized into three main categories:

- **GREEN Engine Tools** – These are project-specific tools developed or enhanced within the project's lifetime. They have been tested in real-world scenarios and are intended to be reusable components that support pilots in addressing their challenges.
- **Open-Source Tools** – These widely used tools play an important role in extending the GREEN Engine. Maintained by global developer communities, they are constantly evolving. However, because of their general-purpose design, most require adaptation and integration to fit the specific needs of sustainable urban development contexts.
- **Pilot-Specific Tools** – Many pilots already use established tools that are integrated into their existing workflows. It is important to acknowledge these preferences and build on existing methodologies and toolsets. Incorporating such tools into the GREEN Engine workflow can accelerate implementation and enhance overall results.

Besides the technological components, [Thematic co-explorations in the GREENGAGE framework](#) are defined collaborative, citizen-centred investigations of environmental or social themes, executed through a co-creation model designed for Citizen Observatories. The methodology unfolds in four sequential phases:

- **Phase 1: Preparing** – The theme is selected based on community concerns, followed by training of the pilot owners and onboarding of the core team. This builds foundational awareness, defines roles across stakeholders, and ensures readiness for experimental design.
- **Phase 2: Designing** – The experiment is specified with clear research questions and objectives. Tools and resources are selected, adapted, and tested in collaboration with stakeholders using templates and guidance from the GREENGAGE Academy.
- **Phase 3: Experimenting** – Observers (often community members) are onboarded and trained, then tasked with data collection, followed by combination, visualization, analysis, and evaluation. This step leverages the GREEN Engine digital infrastructure to streamline data curation and insight generation.
- **Phase 4: Sharing** – Results are transformed into storytelling, communication materials, and advocacy to influence policy and promote sustainability. The process emphasizes long-term impact and experiment sustainability.

Underlying this methodology for co-creating thematic co-explorations (illustrated in Figure 50) is the Collaborative Environment (CE) component, the digital backbone supporting the co-creation process. It provides tools for project management, team coordination, resource management, crowdsourcing data, curation, and visualization. The CE, paired with discussion forums like Discourse, enables ongoing engagement, collaboration, and feedback among stakeholders, supporting mutual learning, ownership, and policy impact as core assets of the GREENGAGE approach. In essence, thematic co-explorations are operationalized through a structured co-production model—preparing, designing, experimenting, and sharing—tailored to each campaign's purpose and supported digitally by the CE and the GREEN Engine, all bolstered by knowledge assets from the [GREENGAGE Academy](#). This ensures that citizens, scientists, policymakers, and other actors can collaboratively generate actionable insights, build community capacity, and foster sustainable environmental policy interventions

Figure 50: Project timeline

6.1 Summary of Core Features

Mapping of GREENGAGE technological tools provides consolidated overview of the whole portfolio capabilities, their overlaps, and gaps as well as important characteristics for their integration and deployment in particular use case context. Following tables (Table 12-Table 17) provides summary of selected core features as analysed from technology questionnaires feedback.

Table 12: Questionnaire Summary: Role of the individual tools considered in GREENGAGE solutions.

Role of the tools in GREENGAGE	MindEarth	DEUSTO	HOPU / Moondial	GISAT	AIT	VRVis	SushiDev / Digitalsunray	Argaleo
	MindEarth for GREENGAGE app	Collaborative Environment	Portable Devices for environmental data capture	UrbanTEP / VISAT	MODE	Data Quality Dashboard	GREENGAGE app	DigiTwin
Data capture (recording and capturing data)	X		X		X		X	
Data curation & storage (validating and storing data)			X	X			X	
Data analysis (processing and analysing the data to generate new insights and knowledge)	X		X	X	X	X		X
Data exploitation (putting the outputs to use, whether internally or by trading them)	X			X				X
Co-Creation through Citizen Science		X			X			X
Incentivization / rewarding		X					X	
Crowdsourcing	X	X	X		X		X	X

Table 13: Questionnaire Summary: Programmatic interfaces of the individual tools considered in GREENGAGE solutions.

Programmatic interfaces of the tools	MindEarth	DEUSTO	HOPU / Moondial	GISAT	AIT	VRVis	SushiDev / Digitalsunray	Argaleo
	MindEarth for GREENGAGE app	Collaborative Environment	Portable Devices for environmental data capture	UrbanTEP / VISAT	MODE	Data Quality Dashboard	GREENGAGE app	DigiTwin
(Webservice) REST		X	X	X	X		X	
(WebService) GraphQL							X	
(Webservice) SOAP								
(Webservice) UDDI								
(Webservice) XML-RPC	X							
(Webservice) Other...								
(MQ/Broker) Apache Kafka								
(MQ/Broker) Apache ActiveMQ								
(MQ/Broker) RabbitMQ								
(MQ/Broker) Open Message Queue								
(MQ/Broker) Other...								
(Native library) C/C++								
(Native library) Java					X			
(Native library) Python		X		X				
(Native library) JavaScript		X		X		X		
(Native library) Other...	X		X ²					
Other interfaces								

Table 14: Questionnaire Summary: Data types and vocabularies used by the individual tools considered in GREENGAGE solutions.

Data types and vocabularies	MindEarth	DEUSTO	HOPU / Moondial	GISAT	AIT	VRVis	SushiDev / Digitalsunray	Argaleo
	MindEarth for GREENGAGE app	Collaborative Environment	Portable Devices for environmental data capture	UrbanTEP / VISAT	MODE	Data Quality Dashboard	GREENGAGE app	DigiTwin
(Database technology) SQL	X	X	X	X		X	X	X
(Database technology) NoSQL – Document oriented		X		X				
(Database technology) Social data		X						
(Database technology) Audiovisual data								
(Open Data) Copernicus	X		X	X				X
(Open Data) Public admin datasets	X			X		X		X

Table 15: Questionnaire Summary: Deployment strategy of the individual tools considered in GREENGAGE solutions.

Deployment strategy	MindEarth	DEUSTO	HOPU / Moondial	GISAT	AIT	VRVis	SushiDev / Digitalsunray	Argaleo
	MindEarth for GREENGAGE app	Collaborative Environment	Portable Devices for environmental data capture	UrbanTEP / VISAT	MODE	Data Quality Dashboard	GREENGAGE app	DigiTwin
On-premises			1	X	1	X		
Cloud (SaaS)	X	X	1	X	1		X	X

¹Not decided yet

Table 16: Questionnaire Summary: License type used by the individual tools considered in GREENGAGE solutions.

License type	MindEarth	DEUSTO	HOPU / Moondial	GISAT	AIT	VRVis	SushiDev / Digitalsunray	Argaleo
	MindEarth for GREENGAGE app	Collaborative Environment	Portable Devices for environmental data capture	UrbanTEP / VISAT	MODE	Data Quality Dashboard	GREENGAGE app	DigiTwin
Open Source		X		X		X		
Private license	X		X	X	X		X	X
Other								

Table 17: Questionnaire Summary: Technology Readiness and GDRR compliancy by the individual tools considered in GREENGAGE solutions.

Others	MindEarth	DEUSTO	HOPU / Moondial	GISAT	AIT	VRVis	SushiDev / Digitalsunray	Argaleo
	MindEarth for GREENGAGE app	Collaborative Environment	Portable Devices for environmental data capture	UrbanTEP / VISAT	MODE	Data Quality Dashboard	GREENGAGE app	DigiTwin
Technology Readiness Level (TRL)	7	6	8	7	6	8	6	9
GDPR compliancy	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X

7 Usage scenario of GREEN Engine in future Citizen Observatories

Summarizing the above chapters, a typical usage scenario for the GREEN Engine is as follows:

Phase 1: Preparing phase

An Observatory owner/creator initiates one or more thematic co-explorations based on the identification of local planning challenges and community concerns and formulates actionable research questions. A Stakeholder mapping is performed to identify key contributors, followed by an onboarding and training of a core team. Both, GREENGAGE's [Academy](#) and Collaborative Environment (CE)'s [catalogue](#) provide access to training materials, stakeholder canvases. Collaborative platforms such as the CE and Discourse ensure all participants are equipped with the necessary knowledge and tools.

Phase 2: Designing phase

The core team, leveraging the GREEN Engine toolbox, specifies the experiment(s), identifies data gaps and selects appropriate tools and resources for data generation, and customizes them to fit the Observatory's objectives. Workshops facilitate the co-design of activities, KPIs, and data protocols. The Collaborative Environment enables transparent governance and traceability of the co-production process, while the DataHub supports inventory and registration of datasets.

Phase 3: Experimenting phase

Citizen Observers are onboarded and trained using asynchronous materials and interactive sessions. Data collection is executed through integrated apps and sensors (e.g., MODE via the GREENGAGE app, MindEarth for GREENGAGE app, AtmoTube), with tasks configured to address identified data gaps. The GREEN Engine's data crowdsourcing and capture layer ensures ethical and secure data acquisition, while qualitative insights are gathered via surveys and interviews.

Collected data is ingested and processed using automated workflows (Apache NiFi, Python scripts), stored in Apache Druid, and visualized through Apache Superset dashboards. These tools enable real-time monitoring, collaborative analysis, and the creation of digital twins, supporting evidence-based decision-making and policy development.

Phase 4: Sharing phase

Findings are shared back to CO participants for validation, feedback and co-creative sense making so they can be disseminated through engaging storylines crafted with visualization tools and published on Discourse (or, if maintained by the Observatory, a dedicated Wordpress instance). Policy briefs are generated using collaborative templates, translating insights into actionable recommendations for policymakers. Sustainability is ensured by documenting lessons learned, refining objectives, and preparing for future iterations, leveraging the GREEN Engine's flexible architecture and community-driven approach.

The above process is not always linear, sometimes, hypothesis could be rejected, or the experiment results are inconclusive and need to be repeated. Also, it is important to share the results with society and other fellow CO teams so they can replicate the experiment and verify the results. This is an important step to make sure that the conclusion maximizes impact and sustainability of the effort of a Citizen Observatory.

8 Conclusions

Deliverable D4.9 GREEN Engine and Manual 3, marks the final key milestone in the iterative development and technical validation of the GREEN Engine, as it documents the delivery of the final GREEN Engine - a result of the third iteration, fully integrated into an independent and reusable set of tools tailored to assist GREENGAGE's pilots and future Citizen Observatories with their challenges.

Significant advancements have been made in stabilizing the GREEN Engine architecture, enhancing modularity, and ensuring scalability and maintainability of its components. The deliverable provides an updated overview of the GREEN Engine's evolution, including improved orchestration mechanisms, refined component interfaces, and the integration of real-world datasets in support of policy-driven use cases. Pilot-specific configurations have matured, offering a more concrete demonstration of how GREENGAGE components can be assembled and tailored to thematic objectives.

Moreover, the work has continued to emphasize the platform's flexibility and adaptability. Integration pathways between third-party tools, open-source components, and GREENGAGE-specific modules have been tested and optimized, allowing for the creation of increasingly complex and value-driven workflows. These developments directly respond to the MVP's feedback gathered from pilot teams, contributing to an evidence-based refinement cycle.

Through this phase, GREENGAGE moved from conceptual interoperability towards finalized practically operational demonstration, showcasing how data-driven, modular, and citizen-engaged approaches can support sustainable urban development at scale.

References

- Hall, S., Khan, Z., Ramsay, A., Ludlow, D., Javed, B., Zach, M., Peters-Anders, J., Kozłowska, A., Gebetsroither-Geringer, E., Vuckovic, M., Kirby, S., Reeh, R., Vignoli, A., Bordi, C., Martens, S., Nesterova, N., Mermans, E., 2025. WP2 D2.5 Smart Governance Models. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.17079179>
- Javed, B., Khan, Z., Padiya, T., Scavino, G., Green, S., Stubenschrott, M., Peters-Anders, J., Kozłowska, A., Martens, S., Khrystodulov, A., Feliciotti, A., Pirker-Ihl, M., Goels, M., Vuckovic, M., Wolosiuk, D., López-de-Ipiña, D., Sanchez-Corcuera, R., 2025. WP1 D1.12 Data Management Plan. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.17094202>
- Khrystodulov, A., Adamec, T., Soukup, T., Emaldi, M., Sanchez-Corcuera, R., Vergara Borge, F., López-de-Ipiña, D., Kozłowska, A., Gebetsroither-Geringer, E., Pirker-Ihl, M., Reitschmied, M., Marconcini, M., Vuckovic, M., Nesterova, N., Jara, A., 2023a. WP4 D4.1 GREEN Engine and manual v1. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.15745320>
- Khrystodulov, A., Soukup, T., Emaldi, M., Sanchez-Corcuera, R., Vergara Borge, F., López-de-Ipiña, D., Stubenschrott, M., Kozłowska, A., Gebetsroither-Geringer, E., Pirker-Ihl, M., Reitschmied, M., Goels, M., Alabyan, D., Marconcini, M., Vuckovic, M., Wolosiuk, D., Nesterova, N., Jara, A., 2023b. WP4 D4.2 GREEN Engine and manual. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.15754756>
- López-de-Ipiña, D., Emaldi, M., Vergara Borge, F., Martens, S., Scavino, G., Khrystodulov, A., Alabyan, D., Wolosiuk, D., Feliciotti, A., Pirker-Ihl, M., 2025. WP2 D2.7 REENGAGE Technological Requirements. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.15754820>
- Sanchez-Corcuera, R., Emaldi, M., Vergara Borge, F., López-de-Ipiña, D., Wolosiuk, D., Khrystodulov, A., Martens, S., Lizama, A., Pirker-Ihl, M., Covato, E., Alabyan, D., Peters-Anders, J., Kozłowska, A., Gebetsroither-Geringer, E., 2025. WP4 D4.6 REENGAGE experiment and monitoring system and manual. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.17079305>
- Soomro, K., Covato, E., Khan, Z., Ludlow, D., Kirby, S., Reeh, R., Vignoli, A., Bordi, C., Scavino, G., Martens, S., 2025. WP2 D2.3 Use Cases and Requirements Analysis. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.15754799>